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A PROactive approach for Communities
to enAble Societal Transformation

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ANNEX I QUESTIONNAIRE –

COMINO ISLAND, MALTA

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

Environment Ministry and managing authorities (Ambjent Malta (AM) and Environment and Resource Authority (ERA)) (National) 5

Malta Tourism Authority (National) 5

Ghajnsielem Local Council and Gozo Ministry (Regional) 3

Cleansing Department (waste handlers) (National) 3

Transport Malta (National) 3

b. Academia or groups of experts

University of Malta (Earth Systems / Geosciences / Biology) (National) 3

Malta College for Arts, Science and Technology MCAST 3

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

Kiosks and deckchairs operators (Local) 4

Boat Operators (Local) 4

Comino Hotel (Local) 2

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

Birdlife Malta (National) 3

Din L_Art Helwa (National) 3

Moviment Graffiti (National) 3

Sports related NGOs (National) 2
e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)
Residents (Local) 3
Visitors (Mostly foreign tourists + local visitors) 3

<p>2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).</p>
<p>Comino Island - N2K Management Plan (https://era.org.mt/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Kemmuna_ManagementPlan.pdf)</p> <p>5</p> <p>Malta Tourism Strategy (https://www.mtobservatory.org/files/ugd/9121fd_23901142c3434d72b9cf4748a1cfb328.pdf)</p> <p>2</p> <p>Gozo and Comino Local Plan (https://www.pa.org.mt/en/local-plan-details/gozo-comino-local-plan)</p> <p>1</p> <p>Developing a National Coastal Protection Strategy for the Maltese Islands Planning Authority (pa.org.mt)</p> <p>1</p>

<p>3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:</p>
<p>. Climate change</p>
<p>Lack of climate change mitigation plans for Comino in N2K management plan. 3</p>

a. Biodiversity

It is envisaged that through the data collection and consolidation both as part of this project and also through our long term plans related to the setting up of an Environmental Education Centre, we could have the necessary grounds to be able to advocate for policy changes and improvements in the longer term. This will impact the biodiversity of Comino in various ways, including the Comino N2K management plan review, the afforestation plans and the control of rodent population which is wreaking havoc to Comino's biodiversity. 5

Nature 2000 (N2K) Management Plan 5

b. Urban and rural planning

- Possibly through Comino N2K management plan although there is no urban area of Comino 5
- Gozo and Comino Local Plans 4

c. Mobility

N/a

d. Tourism

Comino is an important and strategic aspect of Malta's tourism. The National Tourism strategy, makes specific reference to Comino as a distinct "product" 5

Through this project we also hope to influence the hotel plans and expansion

e. Participatory research

Through this study it is planned to create a repository of existing data, take a stocktake of what already exists and the gaps in data. Through the support of National authorities, academics and Citizen science initiatives we hope that the management of the N2K site will be improved and impacted positively. 4

f. Agriculture

Currently no agricultural practices

g. Others

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

<p>THE MINISTRY FOR THE ENVIRONMENT, ENERGY AND REGENERATION OF THE GRAND HARBOUR 5</p> <p>Managing authorities (Ambjent Malta (AM) and Environment and Resource Authority (ERA) 5</p> <p>Planning Authority 5</p> <p>Ministry for Gozo and Planning 5</p> <p>Ministry for Tourism 5</p> <p>Malta Tourism Authority 5</p> <p>Transport Malta 5</p> <p>Għajnsielem Local Council 4</p> <p>Cleansing and Maintenance Division 3</p>

5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

<p>THE MINISTRY FOR THE ENVIRONMENT, ENERGY AND REGENERATION OF THE GRAND HARBOUR 5</p> <p>Managing authorities (Ambjent Malta (AM) and Environment and Resource Authority (ERA) 5</p> <p>Planning Authority 3</p> <p>Ministry for Gozo and Planning 5</p> <p>Ministry for Tourism 3</p> <p>Malta Tourism Authority 5</p> <p>Transport Malta 5</p>
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6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?

[Recommendation] Consider involving them in the governance structure of the CS.

a. Agenda setting
Comino Working group FoEM
b. Policy formulation
Comino Working group FoEM
c. Decision making

Comino Working group FoEM
d. Policy implementation
Comino Working group FoEM
e. Policy evaluation
Comino Working group FoEM

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?.
Increased awareness; data collection that will inform future policy making; bringing more attention to an important site; increased nature connection through informed tourism with the support of the environmental centre being planned; Site monitoring and increased presence for surveillance of area. In the much longer term we also hope to see policy changes but this could be in a timeframe beyond the lifetime of this project.

Environmental dimension

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation ?
<p><u>International :</u></p> <p>Natura 2000 site (terrestrial - whole island and islets): MT0000017 Kemmuna u l-Gzejjer ta' Madwarha</p> <p>Natura 2000 sites (marine area around around the island) : MT0000112 - Żona fil-Baħar madwar Għawdex MT0000105 - Żona fil-Baħar bejn Il-Ponta ta' San Dimitri (Għawdex) u Il-Qaliet</p> <p><u>National designations (areas within the site / whole island):</u></p> <p>Area of Ecological Importance</p> <p>Site of Scientific Importance</p> <p>Tree Protection Area</p> <p>Bird Sanctuary</p> <p>Nature Reserve</p>

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

Limestone coastal cliffs; rocky coast with various geomorphological features; islets; coastal caves; Sandy beach with associated dune; Cliff-top phrygana and garigue expanses with endemic species; Steppe habitats

Habitats: Key habitats

Terrestrial:

1240 – Vegetated sea cliffs of the Mediterranean coasts with endemic *Limonium* spp.

1420 – Mediterranean and thermo-Atlantic halophilous scrubs (*Sarcornetea fruticosi*)

2210 – Crucianellion *maritima* fixed beach dunes

3140 – Hard oligo-mesotrophic waters with benthic vegetation of *Chara* spp.

3170* – Mediterranean temporary ponds*

5330 – Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-desert scrub

5410 – West Mediterranean cliff-top phryganas

6220 – Pseudo-steppe with grasses and annuals of the Thero-Brachypodietea

8210 – Calcareous rocky slopes with chasmophytic vegetation

92D0 – Southern riparian galleries and thickets

9320 – *Olea* and *Ceratonia* forests

9540 – Mediterranean pine forests with endemic Mesogean pines.

Marine habitats:

1110 Coastal and halophytic habitats

1120* *Posidonia* beds* (*Posidonion oceanicae*)

1170 Reefs, Coastal and halophytic habitats

8330 Submerged or partially submerged sea caves, Rocky habitats and caves

Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats

11 terrestrial

4 marine

Habitats: Number of priority habitats
Two
Fauna: Key fauna species
Key Flora: 4114 <i>Linaria pseudolaxiflora</i> Key fauna: 1224 <i>Caretta caretta</i> ; A010 <i>Calonectris diomedea</i> ; A464 <i>Puffinus yelkouan</i>
Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC
<u>1303 Rhinolophus hipposideros</u> <u>1307 Myotis blythii</u> <u>A010 Calonectris diomedea</u> <u>A073 Milvus migrans</u> <u>A081 Circus aeruginosus</u> <u>A096 Falco tinnunculus</u> <u>A097 Falco vespertinus</u> <u>A243 Calandrella brachydactyla</u> <u>A243 Calandrella brachydactyla</u> <u>A303 Sylvia conspicillata</u> <u>A305 Sylvia melanocephala</u> <u>A351 Sturnus vulgaris</u> <u>A464 Puffinus yelkouan</u>
Fauna: Number of wild bird species
11 breeding birds + many migratory and wintering species
Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC
<u>A010 Calonectris diomedea</u> <u>A073 Milvus migrans</u>

A081 Circus aeruginosus

A096 Falco tinnunculus

A097 Falco vespertinus

A243 Calandrella brachydactyla

A243 Calandrella brachydactyla

A303 Sylvia conspicillata

A305 Sylvia melanocephala

A351 Sturnus vulgaris

A464 Puffinus yelkouan

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.

A Natura 2000 management plan has been in place for about 10 years for the terrestrial part of Comino with apparent limited implementation. Some site interventions were done for relocation of the camping site to initiate restoration of one rare habitat in one small part of the island.

No management plan is in place for the Marine Natura 2000 sites that we know of. Management plan is currently in the initial phases of being reviewed.

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

1 Nature walks

5 Boating

5 Mass Tourism

5 Bathing

1 Ornithological research

3 Historical heritage (includes restoration works and actual visits from tourists)

4 Camping

5 Hotel development and works

1 Small scale beekeeping

3 SCUBA Diving and similar marine sports

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the

CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

- 5 uncontrolled visitation condensed in one small area
- 5 lack of political will for carrying capacity measures, site conservation and restrictive measures related to MPA and boating
- 5 lack of implementation of management plan
- 5 total lack of management plan for the marine protected area
- 4 lack of consultation by authorities
- 5 mass tourism party style with consequent waste generation, noise and light pollution
- 5 lack of waste management plan for the whole site
- 5 uncontrolled anchoring by high density of boats and potential spills and damage to the seabed , issues of noise and light pollution
- 5 mushrooming food stalls with dubious licensing - with resulting impacts on waste generation, sound pollution, air pollution from generators and taking up of public land
- 4 sprawling umbrella operators taking up public land
- 4 increasing number of motorised vehicles
- 5 trampling
- 5 deterioration of the only sand dune remnant and lack of proactive measures
- 5 disproportionate funds - little funding goes into the island compared to the huge turnover tourist operators get from the site
- 5 lack of awareness by private tourism operators, and consequent lack of awareness of visitors
- 5 no environmental enforcement on site
- 5 no environmental education on site or on any tourism info materials
- 5 no environmental taxes to go towards conserving area.
- 5 uncontrolled and widespread rat population (with some exceptions carried out by local ENGO Birdlife Malta / ERA)
- 4 sporadic infrastructural works carried out without sensitive respect of the status of the site

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

- 5 extremely high human impact - some areas are chronically way over their carrying capacity
- 5 biodiversity loss
- 5 habitat degradation on land and at sea
- 5 noise and light pollution from boats
- 5 pollution from waste on land and at sea
- 4 soil erosion
- 4 invasive species
- 5 rat populations
- 5 increasing droughts
- 4 dust pollution from dirt roads and increased vehicular movement
- 4 hunting at sea and in adjacent islands
- 5 trampling on sensitive habitats
- 5 increased land take up for commercial activities

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of

public engagement, measured variables, etc).

h. Yes, no?

1. Yes. These are generally sporadic measures, including a biodiversity survey done by FoE Malta in conjunction with BINCO, and other one time surveys by NGOs, Academics and Authorities.

0. A carrying capacity study was also done but was not published publicly.

0. Longstanding ornithological research on bird migration and seabird breeding sites

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

All local

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?

1. NGOs and academics
2. Environment and Resource Authority
3. BirdLife Malta

d. How long is it being implemented?

1. sporadic
2. over one summer
3. migrating birds: around 30 years / seabirds: 10 years +

e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/ habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?

1. Species populations
2. pressures
3. Species and habitats

15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

a. spatial coverage

3

b. temporal coverage	
5	
c. data quality and resolution	
5	
d. monitoring frequency	
5	
e. stakeholder engagement limitation	
4	
f. accessibility and availability of data	
5	
g. data integration and interoperability	
2	
h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders	
2	
i. funding	
5	
j. infrastructure and supporting services	
4	
k. other	

Technological dimension

16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?

a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)

Surveys

Email

Social media

Educational Centre (not within CS timeframe but keeping in mind CS when designing and implementing)

Website - kemmuna.org

b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)

Citizens Science initiatives (pollinators app, Herptrust app)

National initiatives

Engaging with academic researchers (Student dissertations, fieldwork)

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?

a. Public institutions

Face to face

Online meetings

Emails

b. Academia or groups of experts

Face to face

Online meetings

Emails

Websites: Kemmuna.org / PRO-COAST

c. Private enterprises

Face to face

Online meetings

Emails

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

<p>Face to face</p> <p>Online meetings</p> <p>Emails</p>
<p>e. Citizens</p>
<p>Face to face meetings</p> <p>Workshops</p> <p>Surveys</p> <p>Interviews</p> <p>Social Media</p> <p>Public communications / educational campaigns (including websites and video clips)</p> <p>Setting up of Environmental Education Centre</p> <p>Radio / TV programs</p>

<p>18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?</p>
<p>Focus group surveys by FoEM;</p> <p>Data sheet produced as part of N2K Management plan;</p> <p>Literature review and past dissertations.</p>
<p>a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?</p>
<p>Available for the public</p>
<p>b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?</p>
<p>Carrying capacity exists but is not made public; data on waste; data on rat population; vehicles; data on permitting of commercial activities</p>

<p>19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?</p>
<p>Visitor surveys</p> <p>Survey on local bats</p> <p>More detailed flora survey</p> <p>Rat population hotspots</p>

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

TBC

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

TBC

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives? If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

a. Topic of the initiative

Bees diversity and distribution in the Maltese islands
Ecologica - Malta Biodiversity Survey Project
Focus groups

b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)

General public
A community group bringing together people interested in safeguarding Biodiversity in Malta, and achieving a biodiversity monitoring network.

c. Communication channels

Website
Social media
Leaflets

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

Overcrowding of the Blue Lagoon (on land and at sea)
Uptake of public land by kiosk owners and umbrella providers
Lack of transparency on carrying capacity results which remain unpublished
Review of the N2K management plan
Hotel redevelopment in the two main bays of the island

Lack of management and enforcement on land and at sea

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

Not specifically , but open to ideas as above

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

Social media

Press statements

Newsletter

Travel portals (e.g. Tripadvisor)

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

eNGOs concerned - site conservation

Maltese general public and ENGOS - right to access the coast freely

Tourists - bad reviews of their experience on tourism websites and social media

Hotel developers - to justify redevelopment

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

The only 2 persons residing on Comino

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

In situ protests have been held by NGOs together with members of the public

0. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

The remaining 2 elderly residents who have grown up and always lived here

29. Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

Minimum 5000 daily - in summer season mainly (summer season is now getting longer so it covers at least 6 months)

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

This should have been determined by carrying capacity studies which have yet to be published

30. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

Retired from employment

ANNEX II QUESTIONNAIRE - AQUATINA DI FRIGOLE, ITALY

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

i. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

Consultation is running – 5

b. Academia or groups of experts

Consultation is running – 5

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

Consultation is running - 5

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

Consultation is running – 5

e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)

Consultation is running - 5

2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Better explanation needed in Bergen meeting

3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:

j. Climate change
NIS, coastal erosion increase with sea level rise and storms, etc..
b. Biodiversity
Local, macro-regional and global scale pressures (e.g., marine litter)
c. Urban and rural planning
Building of new urban infrastructures (e.g., roads)
d. Mobility
Increased affluence enables more people to trampling dunes and forget litter
e. Tourism
Increased affluence brings to the need for more new beach resorts, restaurants, etc..
f. Participatory research
Untrained citizen science
g. Agriculture
No bio-agriculture
h. Others
Effectiveness of biodiversity monitoring, deficiency of education

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
University of Salento, Municipality of Lecce, Apulia Region

5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
Consultation is running

6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?

a. Agenda setting

University of Salento

b. Policy formulation

University of Salento

c. Decision making

University of Salento

d. Policy implementation

University of Salento

e. Policy evaluation

University of Salento

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?

Inputs from Stakeholder Joint Task Force

Environmental dimension

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation ?

NATURA 2000

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

Coastal lagoon, sandy beach, dunes
b. Habitats: Key habitats
<i>Baseline of biodiversity is required – Basic info are available in the N2K SDF</i>
c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats
<i>Baseline of biodiversity is required - Basic info are available in the N2K SDF</i>
d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats
<i>Baseline of biodiversity is required - Basic info are available in the N2K SDF</i>
e. Fauna: Key fauna species
<i>Baseline of biodiversity is required - Basic info are available in the N2K SDF</i>
f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC
<i>Baseline of biodiversity is required - Basic info are available in the N2K SDF</i>
g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species
<i>Baseline of biodiversity is required - Basic info are available in the N2K SDF</i>
h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC
<i>Baseline of biodiversity is required - Basic info are available in the N2K SDF</i>

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.
<i>Better explanation needed in Bergen meeting – Yes, it is elaborated but need implementation</i>

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
Biodiversity Conservation, Innovative ecological research supporting biodiversity, education

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Local, macro-regional, global pressures

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Better explanation needed in Bergen meeting – Marine plastics, climate changes, local impacts on dune, NIS

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).

a. Yes, no?

No, routinely monitoring programs are running on established spatial-temporal scales. Just spot initiatives linked to research aims can be reported.

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?

d. How long is it being implemented?

e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?

15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

a. spatial coverage

Yes – a baseline is needed

b. temporal coverage

Yes – a baseline is needed
c. data quality and resolution
Yes – a baseline is needed
d. monitoring frequency
Yes – a baseline is needed
e. stakeholder engagement limitation
Yes – a baseline is needed
f. accessibility and availability of data
Yes – a baseline is needed
g. data integration and interoperability
Yes – a baseline is needed
h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders
Yes
i. funding
Yes
j. infrastructure and supporting services
Yes
k. other
A baseline is needed within PRO-COAST

16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?
a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)

Need to be implemented
b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)
Need to be implemented

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?
a. Public institutions
A direct access to the PRO-COAST website section called "EU CS2 Apulia Italy Partner: University of Salento" will provide effective communication directly from CS2-Aquatina di Frigole Responsible ⁹
b. Academia or groups of experts
A direct access to the PRO-COAST website section called "EU CS2 Apulia Italy Partner: University of Salento" will provide effective communication directly from CS2-Aquatina di Frigole Responsible
c. Private enterprises
A direct access to the PRO-COAST website section called "EU CS2 Apulia Italy Partner: University of Salento" will provide effective communication directly from CS2-Aquatina di Frigole Responsible
d. NGOs or other third sector groups
A direct access to the PRO-COAST website section called "EU CS2 Apulia Italy Partner: University of Salento" will provide effective communication directly from CS2-Aquatina di Frigole Responsible
e. Citizens
A direct access to the PRO-COAST website section called "EU CS2 Apulia Italy Partner: University of Salento" will provide effective communication directly from CS2-Aquatina di Frigole Responsible

18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?
A baseline is needed within PRO-COAST
a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?
A baseline is needed within PRO-COAST

b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?

A baseline is needed within PRO-COAST

19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?

A baseline is needed within PRO-COAST

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

It is needed within PRO-COAST

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

Darwin Core Standard

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives?
If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

a. Topic of the initiative

Yes

b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)

Yes

c. Communication channels

Yes – Youtube

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

No debates arose concerning PRO-COAST

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

No, but open to ideas

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

No debates arose concerning PRO-COAST

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

Not Available

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

Not Available

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

Not Available

29. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

Number will be calculated in relation to boundaries

30. Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

Number will be calculated in relation to boundaries

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

A specific research is required

31. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

The mapping is required within PRO-COAST

ANNEX III QUESTIONNAIRE -

AREA OF STRUNJAN, SLOVENIA

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

Public Institutions:

1. Landscape Park Strunjan (5) – local: Main stakeholder: Collaboration involves contribution to estimate locations where camera traps will be set, organizing workshops, informing local communities and tourists regarding biodiversity monitoring, help with the surveys, and promoting the SRNA app in visitor centre. Their interest lies in improving the state of the park, raise awareness about issues with pollution, tourism. Involvement of this stakeholder is very important as they are the main target and potentially benefit the most out of the CS. The park has already been consulted and has agreed to collaborate.
2. Municipality of Piran (2) – local: informing the municipality about the project and possibly start a collaboration to achieve the goals of the CS. Helping with promotion of the App.
3. Slovenia Forest Service and Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (4) – national. Improve the monitoring of wildlife for better management plans. Contributing to the app improvement
4. Ministry of the Environment, Climate and Energy (3) – national. One of the main objectives of the ministry is environmental protection. Contribution to the management of the Natura 2000 area in Park as well as involving data collected in PRO-COAST .

b. Academia or groups of experts

1. European Observatory of Wildlife and ENETWILD consortium (3): collaboration with this consortium (including European universities and institution) and project will help us better define the planned camera trapping activities and water body sampling.
2. ERGA (European Reference Genome Atlas) – involving community of universities and research institution in collection specimens from the areas analysis Reference genome.
3. Faculty of Environmental protection- private faculty, which also collect data by camera traps.

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

LOGOS (5): Upgrade of the SRNA app to improve user experience.

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

Hunting Association of Slovenia (HAS): Area of Strunjan (5): Main stakeholder: Collaboration involves setting camera traps and collecting data using the SRNA app. Benefit from wildlife monitoring to improve management and decrease conflict with local citizens and farmers.
e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)
Farmers (3): local citizens that farm in the Park of Strunjan or in close proximity. Consult to find a way to mitigate the negative impact of tourism on the area and find ways to decrease conflict with wildlife present in the area.

2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
<p>Nature Conservation Act (Zakon o ohranjanju narave) (3) – national</p> <p>This law sets out biodiversity conservation measures and a system of protection for natural values, with the aim of contributing to nature conservation. Biodiversity conservation measures are measures that regulate the protection of wild flora- including their genetic material, habitats, and ecosystems; enable the sustainable use of components of biodiversity; and ensure the maintenance of the natural balance.</p> <p>Regulation on the Strunjan Landscape Park (Uredba o Krajinskem parku Strunjan) (4) – local</p> <p>The conservation objectives of the park are: to conserve natural values, to maintain high biodiversity, to conserve populations of endangered and internationally protected wild flora and fauna species, the conservation of at least the existing range of habitat types, which shall preferably be maintained in a favorable condition, the conservation of the landscape with a mosaic distribution of landscape structures, the conservation of the ecological characteristics of the salt marshes, the lagoon and the seashore, and the natural processes and connections between the intertidal zone and the infralittoral.</p> <p>Game and Hunting Act (Zakon o divjadi in lovstvu) (3) – national</p> <p>This law regulates game management, which includes planning, conservation, sustainable management and monitoring of game, and the ways in which they are carried out.</p>

3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:
a. Climate change (1)
There are no plans to significantly impact climate change.
b. Biodiversity (4)
With our activities we could potentially impact biodiversity conservation in terms of recognition of its importance, its long-term monitoring and conservation actions. This could have a potential impact at the policy level in which certain areas of higher biodiversity might have limited access. In terms of wildlife management, we might also see

a difference in management practice, by identifying areas where more conflicts with other stakeholders appear and focusing management efforts to those areas.

c. Urban and rural planning (1)

There is little potential for impact on urban and rural planning.

d. Tourism (3)

While impacting tourism at the policy level is difficult, we could impact it at the local level as it is very important economically for the studied area. Potential impacts on tourism can be linked to biodiversity and natural landscape of the area, which we can improve with nature conservation activities and raising awareness. Increased tourism, however, can have a negative impact on the area increasing air and water pollution and increasing of illegal waste sites, which can become foci for disease transmission. By studying the impact of tourism on the area, we can propose changes at the local level.

e. Participatory research (4)

Participatory research is key in the CS3 study. One of our goals is to monitor wildlife with a citizen science app we developed called SRNA, which can be upgraded to include more species and topics relevant for nature conservation such as information on waste and pollution. With the app we aim to collect data about wildlife and potential illegal waste sites in the area. For example, by providing this information to the locals we can improve the waste management and behaviour of tourist by organizing cleaning activities will be organized. We hope to have a positive impact on participatory research by showcasing its potential to the general public.

f. Agriculture (4)

Agriculture is an important aspect of our CS, as one of the main stakeholders are the farmers whose land is located within the boundaries of the landscape park. Farmers in the area are impacted by tourism and wildlife damages of crops and are under pressure due to the regulations in the park area. Our efforts could contribute to lowering the impact of tourism and wildlife on their farming areas.

g. Wildlife management (5)

In our CS one of the main objectives is to monitor wildlife species that often come in conflict with the locals, such as farmers, or can be a potential vector of diseases. By studying the game animals and some selected wildlife in the area, we can mitigate the human-wildlife conflicts and better understand the potential risks associated with certain species, that might carry diseases.

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Municipality of Piran - local government (3).

Slovenia Forest Service and Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (4).

Ministry of the Environment, Climate and Energy (3).
University and Schools

5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Landscape Park Strunjan (5), Hunting Association of Slovenia (HAS) (3)

6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?

a. Agenda setting

b. Policy formulation

c. Decision making

d. Policy implementation

e. Policy evaluation

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?

While we do not expect to make significant changes in policies, we can influence decision making process, at least at the local level. The biggest benefit our CS can have been on the Landscape Park Strunjan and the way it operates. This can be as simple as to better inform the visitors of the park and raise awareness or restrict some areas that would be harmed by too much human pressure. Another potential benefit is related to hunters and farmers, namely to lower conflicts between wildlife and farmers.

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation?

Landscape Park Strunjan is a protected area based on the Regulation on the Strunjan Landscape Park (Uredba o Krajinškem parku Strunjan), with four Natura 2000 special protection areas.

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

Sea, cliff, lagoon, salt pans, Strunjan peninsula.

b. Habitats: Key habitats

1. River outlets, estuaries
2. Silty and sandy fields, tidal flats
3. Coastal lagoons
4. Pioneer stands of *Salicornia* and other annuals on mud and sand
5. Mediterranean salt-tolerant shrubs (*Sarcocornetea fruticosi*)
6. Marine reefs
7. Annual plant communities on coastal erratics
8. Mediterranean coastal cliffs coasts covered with endemic species of the genus *Limonium*

c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats

6

d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats

Seven priority habitats.

e. Fauna: Key fauna species

Total number of key fauna species in Landscape park Strunjan is:

- 95 vertebrates
- 85 invertebrates

For example:

1. Marine and terrestrial mammals: Common bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*), Striped dolphin (*Stenella coeruleoalba*), Risso's dolphin (*Grampus griseus*), Fin whale (*Balaenoptera physalus*), Humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*), Red foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*), European roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*), Wild boar (*Sus scrofa*), Etruscan shrew (*Suncus etruscus*)

2. Birds: Mediterranean gull (*Larus melanocephalus*), European shag (*Phalacrocorax aristotelis desmarestii*), Sandwich tern (*Thalasseus sandvicensis*), Little egret (*Egretta garzetta*), Great egret (*Egretta alba*), Black-winged stilt (*Himantopus himantopus*), Mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*), Common shelduck (*Tadorna tadorna*), Common kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*), white wagtail (*Motacilla alba*), Sardinian warbler (*Sylvia melanocephala*), Woodlark (*Lullula arborea*), Cirl bunting (*Emberiza cirlus*), Red-backed shrike (*Lanius collurio*), European goldfinch (*Carduelis carduelis*), European serin (*Serinus serinus*), European turtle dove (*Streptopelia turtur*)
3. Reptiles: Loggerhead sea turtle (*Caretta caretta*)
4. Fishes: Mediterranean killifish (*Aphanius fasciatus*)
5. Invertebrates: 15 protected insect species and 19 threatened butterfly species.

f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC

1. Habitat type: 1
2. Bird Directive: 16

g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species

40 wild bird species.

h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC

1. Little egret (*Egretta garzetta*),
2. Greater white-fronted goose (*Anser albifrons albifrons*),
3. Mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*),
4. Osprey (*Pandion haliaetus*),
5. Water rail (*Rallus aquaticus*),
6. Common moorhen (*Gallinula chloropus*),
7. Eurasian coot (*Fulica atra*),
8. Black-winged stilt (*Himantopus himantopus*),
9. Common greenshank (*Tringa nebularia*),
10. Black-headed gull (*Larus ridibundus*),
11. Sandwich tern (*Sterna sandvicensis*),
12. Common tern (*Sterna hirundo*),
13. Little tern (*Sterna albifrons*),
14. Eurasian collared dove (*Streptopelia decaocto*),
15. Common kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*)

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.

A management plan has been elaborated for Landscape Park Strunjan and is being implemented. This plan covers various domains, including nature conservation, visitor management, sustainable development, and administrative tasks, ensuring the park's protection and sustainable use.

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

- Tourism (5)
- Agriculture (3)
- Fishing (3)
- Hunting (3)
- Urban development (4)

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Considering the current situation inside the CS area:

- Conflict of uses (2),
- Fragmentation of management competencies (2),
- Climate change (2)
- Types and intensity of economic activities within the area (3),
- Lack of financial resources for protection and management (4),
- Uncontrolled visitation (5).

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Considering the current situation inside the CS area

- Climate change impacts (2)
- Soil erosion (2)
- Biodiversity loss (3)
- Invasive species (3)
- Habitat degradation (4)

- Pollution (5)

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).

a. Yes, no?

YES

Ongoing *POSEIDONE Project* - encompasses various activities focused on marine and terrestrial habitats. In the Landscape park Strunjan, numerous events will take place, both in collaboration with partners and as independent initiatives within the park area.

To promote sustainable tourism, the project will involve monitoring anchored boats in the park to quantify their impact on the seabed, informing future tourism planning. Additional visitor counters will be installed at key points to track coastal visitation.

A significant project effort includes renovating a dry-stone house known as "kažeta," a cultural heritage element of Slovenian Istria. These houses, part of green infrastructure, are important for biodiversity. Activities will be organized with the Agricultural Chamber of Slovenia and the Scientific Research Center of Koper to encourage the cultivation of native plants and sustainable agriculture.

The project will also monitor seabird species across borders, using the data to plan future conservation strategies. Cross-border cooperation includes educational and research activities on the "Goletta Verde" sailing ship, with summer schools for Slovenian and Italian students to learn about innovative marine monitoring technologies.

Workshops for local school children will introduce the diversity of the coastal marine environment and the threats it faces. The project also addresses pollution through clean-up campaigns involving divers, local residents, and the public.

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

POSEIDONE - Promotion of green and blue infrastructure for a new environment (international: Interreg Italia-Slovenia)

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?

- Region of Veneto
- Consortium for Land Reclamation of Eastern Veneto
- Consortium for Coordination of Research Activities Related to the Venice Lagoon System – CORILA
- Municipality of Staranzano – Managing Authority of the Isonzo River Mouth Nature Reserve
- WWF Italy Foundation
- Regional Development Center Koper
- Landscape Park Strunjan

- DOPPS-Birdlife Slovenia
- Municipality of Ankaran
- Science and Research Centre Koper
- Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia, Agriculture and Forestry Institute Nova Gorica

d. How long is it being implemented?

1. 1. 2023 – 1. 1. 2026

e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?

The POSEIDONE Project collects various types of data, including:

1. Physicochemical Parameters: Impact of anchoring on the seabed.
2. Biological Parameters: Status of several seabird species.
3. Species/Habitats Variables: Conservation status of habitats and species in the project area.
4. Pressures: Visitor impact on natural coastlines.
5. Pollution levels and its impact on the marine environment.

These data types are collected to support sustainable tourism planning, biodiversity conservation, and environmental monitoring strategies.

15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

a. spatial coverage (3)

No challenges, area is monitored on a weekly basis by employees of the park.

b. temporal coverage (3)

No challenges, area is monitored on a weekly basis by employees of the park.

c. data quality and resolution (2)

No challenges, as the area is not large.

d. monitoring frequency (3)

Monitoring occurs weekly.

e. stakeholder engagement limitation (3)

Local stakeholders are engaged (inhabitants, farmers), but engagement could be broadened to include additional stakeholders.
f. accessibility and availability of data (2)
National data available for all - data collected by the park is available upon request.
g. data integration and interoperability (1)
Unknown.
h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders
Expected very high technical expertise by members of the park and ministries. The expertise of others stakeholders could probably be improved through collaboration and workshops.
i. Funding
Funding is always a problem. Mainly occurs through projects and from the government.
j. infrastructure and supporting services
Infrastructure and supporting services are limited due to the size of the area, however more infrastructure would negatively impact the area of the park and wildlife.
k. Other

16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?
a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn) - Promotional material will be placed in the visitor centre
b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizen science (CS) App SRNA (Monitoring and Researching Nature through Application) - Camera traps - Sampling of water bodies to recover environmental DNA.

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?

a. Public institutions

- Social media platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn) of Molecular Ecology UP group, University of Primorska and Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Information Technologies)
- Website (University of Primorska and Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Information Technologie)
- email
- Face to face meetings

b. Academia or groups of experts

- Social media platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn) of Molecular Ecology UP group, University of Primorska and faculty FAMNIT
- Website (University of Pirmorska and faculty FAMNIT)
- Email
- Face to face meetings

c. Private enterprises

- Email
- Phone calls
- Face to face meetings

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

- Email
- Face to face meetings
- Social media platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn) of Molecular Ecology UP group, University of Primorska and faculty FAMN

e. Citizens

- Social media platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn) of Molecular Ecology UP group, University of Primorska and faculty FAMNIT
- Face to face meetings
- SRNA app
- workshops, seminars

18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?

Reports from the Landscape park Strunjan, hunting bag data, previously collected data by Apps

a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?

Hunting bag data is very transparent and available online. The data in the reports is usually already analysed, and does not need further analysis.

b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?

Yes, with our monitoring efforts we can improve knowledge about the species in the area, determine their abundance/density (using camera traps and Random encounter model), study behaviour and get a general sense of the biodiversity of species that are not specifically of interest to the park.

19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?

Density of wildlife species (specifically larger mammals, e.g. wild boar, roe deer, golden jackal), that can be of interest for management of these species. Biodiversity of small mammals and potential abundance and position of illegal waste sites.

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

Data analysis of spatial data occurs in GIS softwares (ArcGIS Pro). Other data is usually processed and analysed in either Program R or MS Office Excel. Camera trapping data is analysed with the Agouti webtool and later with Program R.

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

Data is usually stored as CSV, shapefile (for spatial data), Excel spreadsheet. Camera trapping data is stored online on the Agouti servers and exported as CSV in Camera Trap Data Package format. Metadata consists of time and date, coordinates, researcher (i.e., who sampled, who analysed the samples...), method used.

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives? If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

a. Topic of the initiative

Wildlife conservation in Slovenia
b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers, - Students from universities, - Pupils from primary and secondary schools, - Teachers from primary and secondary schools, - Hunters, - Farmers, - Mountaineers, - Photographers - Visitors of the park - Tourist in the nearby resorts - Older adults
c. Communication channels
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn) of Molecular Ecology UP group, University of Primorska and faculty FAMNIT - Website (University of Primorska and Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Information Technologies) - Email - Phone calls and SMS - Face to face meetings - SRNA app

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

Conflict between farmers and wildlife, issues related to tourism and negative impacts of too many visitors (e.g., pollution).

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

We have already gained valuable experience from previous citizen science projects, such as H2020 Step Change project. This approach has provided successful strategies that we have developed and continuously improved over time.

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

TV, radio, social media, newspapers.

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

Debates about issues related to wildlife conflicts are expressed by local residents and local farmers towards hunters. Local residents are also expressing issues with too many tourists, pollution and traffic.

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

Usually, hunters are blamed for damages done by wildlife.

Tourism is often debated, and only local representatives of tourism workers (e.g., hotel owners) can attend.

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

Very rarely regarding the issues in question with our CS.

29. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

The settlement of Strunjan has around 650 inhabitants, but most are not living inside the park area.

The Municipality of Piran has around 18,500 inhabitants mostly living in the towns of Piran and Lucija.

The Coastal-Karst region (NUTS 3) has around 115,000 inhabitants.

30. Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

In 2022 in the Municipality of Piran there were 1.83 million tourists recorded.

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

This is out of our dimension to estimate. We are not trained in this respect.

31. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

Tourism and hospitality, retail and commerce, agriculture.

ANNEX IV QUESTIONNAIRE -

BOKA KOTORSKA, MONTENEGRO

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

In accordance with the Regulation on the Organization and Operation of State Administration:

Ministry of Tourism, Ecology, Sustainable Development and Development of the North performs the tasks administrations related to: preparation and monitoring of regulations and strategic planning of the system in areas of tourism, ecology, sustainable development and development of the north; development of tourism; Catering; tourist offer; business conditions in tourism, selective forms of tourism; connection coastal and continental tourism; formation of tourist places and areas; categorization and classification of tourist facilities; tourist flows on the domestic and foreign market; cooperation with tourist associations in Montenegro and abroad; sustainable valorisation of the potential and ecological advantages of national and protected parks nature areas from the aspect of tourism development; realization of investment programs from interest in sustainable tourism development; monitoring infrastructure projects in the function of development tourism; monitoring and promotion of investments in the tourism sector; coordination of activities for preparation and monitoring of tourist seasons; keeping records on the number of tourists, accommodation

capacities, financial effects and business results in tourism; organizing tourist-informative propaganda activities; improvement of cooperation between tourism sector and complementary sectors; cooperation with the National Tourist Office organization and organization of tourist offices in other countries; the system integral environmental protection and sustainable use of natural resources; assessment area impact and strategic assessment of environmental impact, integrated prevention and control pollution; nature protection; air quality; climate change and approval and monitoring of projects that are implemented with the aim of mitigating the effects of climate change; protection of the ozone layer; noise and vibration protection; chemicals; radiation protection (radioactive substances and ionizing radiation); non-ionizing radiation; soil protection from pollution; integrated coastal zone management; integrated protection of the sea from pollution; industrial pollution control and risk management; application of new and cleaner production technology; adoption, implementation and monitoring of policy in the area monitoring of water conditions, with the exception of water sources and flood events, as well as water protection from pollution, except for the protection of water sources and protection during flood events; management waste and waste water; system of communal activities; regional coordination water supply system; genetically modified organisms under the jurisdiction of this ministries; hydrographic activity; development of environmental protection standards; monitoring environmental conditions; integral planning, management and valorisation of space; sustainable development; coordination of the implementation of the National Strategy for Sustainable Development of Montenegro and making a report on its implementation; cooperation with international financial institutions and funds of the European Union in the implementation of projects in the area for which it is competent ministry; realization of scientific research national and international environmental projects; international cooperation and international agreements from competences of the

ministry; administrative supervision in the areas for which the ministry was established; as well as other tasks assigned to him. (Relevance:5)

Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Management- performs tasks related to the protection, utilization, and improvement of freshwater and marine fisheries and aquaculture; strengthening the competitiveness of food producers; sustainable management of agricultural resources; applying modern techniques and technology in agriculture; development policy in water management, conducting program for monitoring the quality of surface and groundwater, as well as bathing waters; systemic solutions for ensuring and using water, water land, and water sources for water supply, water protection from pollution, watercourse regulation, and protection from harmful water effects; systemic and other incentive measures for improving these areas; preparation of regulations in the fields of agriculture and rural development, food safety, veterinary medicine, phytosanitary matters, fisheries, forestry, water management, and other areas for which the ministry is established; harmonization of domestic regulations within its competence with the *acquis communautaire* of the European Union. (Relevance 3).

The Ministry of Culture and Media performs administrative tasks related to: development

cultural and artistic creativity; protection, preservation, valorisation and presentation of cultural heritage; development of creative industries; realization of public interest in culture; preparation proposals for laws, other regulations and general acts in the field of culture, giving opinions on proposals for laws and other regulations regulating issues related to culture; making and implementation of the culture development strategy and program; research in culture; providing material bases, conditions and incentive measures for the development of culture and creative industries; construction, maintenance, technical-technological equipment and use of cultural objects; preparation of proposals for regulations in the field of cultural heritage, second-degree proceedings and supervision in the field of cultural heritage and others. (Relevance: 4)

The Ministry of Transport and Maritime Affairs performs administrative tasks related to:

preparation and assessment of development investment projects that are of interest to Montenegro and analyzing investment opportunities and administrative barriers and preparing proposals for measures for the improvement of the investment environment, which are under the jurisdiction of this ministry; analyzing the possibilities for the implementation of public-private partnership, which are within the competence of this ministry; compliance of the investment policy with the goals of sustainable development; cooperation with representatives of the private and public sector in order to create policies and measures intended to attract investments, which are within the competence of this ministries; rail, road, sea and air traffic; railway safety, road, sea and air traffic; security protection of merchant ships and ports open to international traffic; determination of indicators, prevention and

taking urgent measures in case of sea pollution from vessels; transportation of dangerous goods matter in rail, sea and air transport and on inland waterways roads in accordance with a special law; domestic and international transport of persons and things; state roads; railway infrastructure, civil air traffic infrastructure and navigation safety facilities; railway, road and maritime industry; inland navigation; safety of maritime and inland navigation, keeping the registry of carriers; registration and certification of harmonized international timetables liner transport; issuing and revoking licenses for international scheduled passenger transport; issuance and cancellation of a transit permit; issuance of permits for off-line passenger transportation; monitoring and studying economic and economic conditions the position of business entities in these areas; proposing ongoing and developmental measures policies and analyzing their impact on the economic position of economic entities in the area which refers to state roads, traffic and maritime;, including equipment and individual parts with adopted standards at the level of safety, economic and environmental requirements; monitoring the state of current and development policies; monitoring the situation and initiating activities in the field of quality management;

harmonization of domestic regulations within the framework of its jurisdiction with the legal acquis European Union; implementation of inspection supervision within the scope of competence and authority determined by the law regulating inspection supervision and regulations in the field of traffic and seafaring; administrative supervision in the areas for which the ministry was established; as well as others tasks assigned to him. (Relevance 4)

Environmental Protection Agency-organizing, planning and participating in environmental monitoring in the field of quality air (including monitoring of pollen suspended in the air), hazardous contents and of harmful substances in the soil, the state of the coastal sea ecosystem, the state of biodiversity, noise in the environment, ionizing and non-ionizing radiation and radionuclides in the environment the middle; reporting on the state of the environment, proposing measures for reduction negative impact on the environment; issuance of an act on the conditions of nature protection for the needs of making plans, bases and programs; preparation of the Protection Study for declaration protected natural asset; issuance of IPPC permits; issuing permits for cross-border movement of waste, processing and/or disposal of waste; issuing permits for performance of maintenance and/or repair activities, as well as exclusion from use of the product containing substances that damage the ozone layer and/or alternative substances; issue permission to monitor fuel quality, air quality; issuing permits for measurement emission on permitted emissions of polluting substances in the air, import or export of the substance which damages the ozone layer, alternative substances, products containing them; issue permission to measure noise levels in the environment and to create strategic noise maps; issuance of permits based on the law regulating nature protection; issuance of permits for the production, circulation and use of sources of ionizing radiation and radioactive materials; issuance of permits for the performance of professional work on protection against non-ionizing radiation, for using sources of electromagnetic fields, devices that emit or contain optical radiation sources of optical radiation and devices that emit ultrasound, as well as a professional license training of persons responsible for the implementation of protection measures against non-ionizing radiation; issuing permits for the import and export of chemicals that are on the classified list

substances, for the import and export of detergents, for the performance of dangerous goods trade activities chemicals, import and export of biocidal products; implementation of the strategic assessment procedure impact and the procedure for assessing the impact of projects on the environment; implementation of the procedure determination of immediate danger of damage to the environment and liability for damage in environment; issuing consent to waste management plans; giving an opinion in the process of issuing permits; keeping records on waste production and management; assessment of the radiological burden of the population; development of liquid quality monitoring programs fuels of petroleum origin; data collection for updating LRTAP and GHG Inventory; reporting to international organizations (European Agency for the Environment, to MedPOL (UNEP/MAP); monitoring the condition and endangerment of habitat types, abundance and the state of wild bird populations, as well as other indicator species that indicate and enable assessment of the state of nature; management of the prior notification procedure (PIC procedure); cooperation with appropriate international institutions and organizations in the field environment, as well as other bodies and organizations of the European Union; tracking the best international practices in the areas under the jurisdiction of this body and in accordance with it proposing measures to protect and improve the environment; execution of international contracts under the jurisdiction of this authority; preparation of professional documents for the preparation of regulations from areas of environmental protection; management of the information system in the field of environment; managing the cadastre of pollutants; maintaining a registry in the field of protection against ionizing radiation and non-ionizing radiation; the preparation and realization of projects in the field of the environment that partially or fully financed from the budgets of Montenegro, the EU and other international ones funds, loans, donations, initiatives and other funds; giving opinions on planning documentation and nature protection measures that those acts should contain; as well as other jobs which are determined in its jurisdiction. (Relevance:5)

Administration of Maritime Safety and Port Management carries out related tasks on: safety of navigation in the coastal sea of Montenegro in connection with arrangement and maintenance maritime waterways, by installing

navigation safety facilities on waterways

roads and ensuring their proper functioning, performing radio tasks services on maritime waterways for the needs of maritime traffic, by collection hydrographic, oceanographic and meteorological data and their broadcasting by radio connection; determining the seaworthiness of ships and other navigable floating objects, namely: performing technical supervision, issuing ship's documents, books and certificates, by calculating the tonnage during the calibration of vessels; carrying out technical expertise in case of maritime accidents; organizing and conducting search actions and rescues at sea; protection of the sea from pollution from navigable and floating objects; yacht registration in the Yacht Registry; implementation of international and European conventions, protocols and agreements from

the scope of the established jurisdiction; cooperation with authorized international organizations and authorized bodies of other states from the administration's scope of work; ports from the national importance; taking care of construction, reconstruction, maintenance, management, protection and improvement port; supervision over the use of the port, the provision of port services and the performance of others activities in ports; control over construction, reconstruction, maintenance and protection port infrastructures and superstructures; provision of conditions for maritime activities traffic and port services in ports and at port anchorages; application of domestic regulations, international agreements and standards related to ports; preparation of development plans ports brought by the Government; ensuring port operations in accordance with market principles; preparation of criteria for determining the amount of fees for the use of port infrastructure; preparation of the concession act, participation in the concession award procedure and conclusion concession contract; approval of the amount of compensation for port services based on the maximum the determined amount of this fee; control of execution of concession contracts; regulation and coordination of relations and activities between concessionaires; maintaining the register of concessions; ensuring the fulfilment of conditions established by international and domestic regulations which the prevention of environmental pollution from ships, the protection of the marine environment is regulated and coastal areas and civil liability for damage caused by pollution; as well as others tasks assigned to her. (Relevance; 4)

Directorate for Statistics performs tasks related to: organization and implementation

official statistics, collection of data from administrative sources and performance of statistics from combined data sources; collection, processing, statistical analysis and publication official statistics; establishment, development, maintenance, updating and use of statistical registers exclusively for statistical purposes; development, adoption and harmonization of methodologies and questionnaires for the production of official statistics; coordinating preparation and publication program, plan and calendar of official statistics in cooperation with other entities that prepare official statistics; harmonization and application of unique methodological solutions; preparation and publication of professional-methodological publications; fulfilment of obligations from international agreements from the scope of official statistics; application of nomenclature, classification and statistical standards in accordance with Eurostat regulations which ensures comparability of data and data indicators at the national and international level; development of statistical information system of official statistics; statistical and information training of personnel; control of data accuracy of reporting units; as well as other tasks assigned to her.(Relevance: 5)

Local Government (Municipalities of the coastal region) - The Law on Local Self-Government defines the right of citizens and local self-government bodies to, within the limits established by law, regulate and manage certain public and other affairs, based on their own responsibility and in the interest of the local population. Local self-government is realized on the principles of democracy, decentralization, depoliticization, autonomy, legality, professionalism, efficiency of work of local self-government bodies and mutual cooperation between the state and the municipality. In the municipality, the needs of the immediate and common interest of the local population are met. The municipality, in accordance with the law and other regulations: arranges and ensures the performance and development of communal activities, maintenance of communal facilities and communal order,

arranges, secures and takes care of local goods of general interest; provides the conditions and takes care of the protection of the environment and its individual parts (air quality, noise protection, solid waste management, etc.); arranges and provides conditions for the management of water, water land and water facilities of local importance, takes care of their protection and use, issues water acts and keeps prescribed records; determines erosive areas, anti-erosive measures and implements protection against erosion and floods; organizes and ensures the performance of other tasks in the field of management, use and protection of water and water supply, arranges, provides and creates conditions for the development of culture and the protection of cultural heritage; regulates, organizes and creates conditions and takes care of the development of tourism, as well as the development of activities that improve the development of tourism; regulates and provides conditions for informing the local population, determines the working hours in certain activities and determines the areas in which certain activities can be performed and others. (Relevance 4)

b. Academia or groups of experts

Faculty of Maritime Studies in Kotor is higher education institution being a part of the University of Montenegro. It was established in 1959 as a Maritime College and afterwards, complying with the growing trends of maritime infrastructure of Montenegro, this educational institution, recognized in former Yugoslavia, was turned into Maritime Faculty in 1981. The aim of this institution was to educate specialized maritime personnel on the two-year studies on the following departments (Nautical, Marine Engineering and Marine Electrotechnics) and the four-year studies (Management in Shipping). In the academic year 1999/2000, Maritime – Nautical and Marine Engineering departments in duration of four years were founded at the Maritime Faculty. Today, in accordance with the Bologna declaration, Faculty of Maritime Studies in Kotor provides academic and applied studies lasting from three years (six semesters).

Secondary school for Maritime studies is VET school located in Kotor Municipality. It is operating since 1849. Institute of Marine Biology was founded in 1961. The Institute has changed its organizational structure several times under different state administrations. Today it is organizational structure of the University of Montenegro and the only scientific research institution in the Montenegro that deals with protection and study of the Adriatic Sea. The Institute comprises five laboratories and one centre: Laboratory for Marine Chemistry and Oceanography, Laboratory for Ichthyology and Marine Fisheries, Laboratory for Plankton and Quality of Marine Waters, Laboratory for Benthos and Marine Protection, Laboratory for Development Research and Mariculture, and Adriatic Biodiversity Conservation Centre with Aquarium Boka. Since 1965 the Institute of Marine Biology is publishing scientific magazine „Studia marina“.

The Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality was established on May 20, 1999, in the unique setting of the Old Town of Kotor, a UNESCO World Heritage site. At the Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality, education is organized within the academic study programs of Tourism and Hospitality at all levels of study (undergraduate, postgraduate master's, and doctoral). Providing broad theoretical knowledge in the fields of tourism management, marketing, finance, and other related activities, as well as detailed insight into their practical application in hotel-tourism organizations through guest lectures, partnerships, seminars, and internships in tourism companies, the faculty aims to enhance the competitiveness of students in the international tourism job market, encouraging the development of innovations and entrepreneurial initiatives in this sector.

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

Chamber of Economy of Montenegro - Committee of Tourism and Hospitality Associations

Local tourist organizations and operators, hoteliers, restaurateurs

Public Enterprise „Regional Water Company of the Coastal Area“, competent for ensuring a continuous water

supply to water supply systems in municipalities in the Coastal Area of Montenegro and „Vodacom“ Ltd, competent for water supply and waste water disposal in the Coastal Area and the Old Royal Capital Cetinje and provision of professional assistance in project implementation in the area of utility services.

Laboratory tests and other technical activities are performed by the Centre for Eco-toxicological Research of Montenegro (CETI) and the Public Health Institute as accredited laboratories.

Technical and research activities are carried out by the University of Montenegro, more specifically by the Institute of Marine Biology as its organizational unit in the area of marine biodiversity, and by the Natural History Museum.

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

According to the [NGO info](#), in Montenegro there are 31 NGO for environment protection. Considering the small location of Montenegro, majority of NGOs are acting on national level.

According to the records of the Ministry of Public Administration, the number of active NGOs in the municipality of Kotor is 229.(<https://www.gov.me/dokumenta/6c9088fd-e2b1-4967-ad0e-3a64f5e8d3f2>)

e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)

According to the preliminary data from latest population census from 2023, Montenegro has 633.158 inhabitants. Approximately 11,5 % of entire population is living in municipalities in Boka Bay Area (Tivat 17.120, Kotor 22.857 and Herceg Novi 33.022).

When it comes to the migration within Montenegro, according to the Montenegrin Statistical Office Monstat there has been noted some migration to the coastal area which is bigger than Boka Kotorska bay area. In addition to this, in the last couple of years, there has been noted a significant migration from Russia, Ukraine and Turkey to Boka Kotorska bay area but no statistical data is available.

Local self-government bodies are obliged to provide citizens with the necessary data, explanations and notifications in order to exercise their rights and interests. Notification is also provided through technical means, brochures and public information means.

Forms of direct participation of citizens in declaration and decision-making are: initiative, citizens' initiative, assembly of citizens, referendum (local and municipal) and other forms of declaration and decision-making established by statute. The statute, in accordance with the law, regulates in more detail the way and procedure of participation of the local population in declaring and deciding on matters of common interest.

2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Montenegro, as a signatory of numerous conventions and international agreements in the field of nature and environmental protection, as well as a candidate country for EU membership, has created its own legal framework which represents a solid basis for further upgrading and improvement of legal solutions on the

protection of the marine biodiversity and ecosystem. The importance of the Montenegrin legal regime lies in the fact that it represents an important mechanism for the protection of the coastal sea of Montenegro, which complements and improves the entire legal regime for the protection of the Adriatic Sea.

The drafting of the Law on the Protection of the Marine Environment was foreseen in the Montenegro's Programme of Accession to the European Union, National Strategy with the Action Plan for Transposition, Implementation and Enforcement of the EU Acquis on Environment and Climate Change for the period 2016-2020, as well as prescribed as obligation by the Action Plan for the Fulfilment of the Closing Benchmarks for Chapter 27. Through the Law on the Protection of the Marine Environment ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 73/19) and related by law legislation, provisions of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC) and Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848 of 17 May 2017 on criteria and methodological standards for the assessment of good environmental status, as well as specifications and standardized methods for the implementation of monitoring programs and assessments, have been transposed into national legislation, thereby repealing Decision 2010/477/EU. The Law regulates: the protection, preservation, remediation, and valorisation, and where possible, the restoration of the structure and function of marine and coastal ecosystems and the protection of biodiversity; the preservation of protected areas in the sea and ecologically significant areas within the Natura 2000 network; prevention, or where possible, reduction of pollution or burden on the marine environment and coastal areas, in a manner that ensures the reduction of negative impacts or risks to human health and/or biodiversity, ecosystem health, and/or the use of the sea and coast; preservation, improvement, and/or restoration of the balance between human activities and natural resources in the sea and coastal area; preservation of marine and coastal areas; sustainable use of natural resources in the sea and coastal area; preservation of the integrity of coastal ecosystems and landscapes; prevention and/or mitigation of the impacts of natural phenomena, particularly climate change, which may be caused by natural or human activities.

The Law on Nature Protection ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 54/16)- transpose the key EU legislation in the area of nature protection (such as Habitats and Birds Directives), specifically, the establishment of the Natura 2000 ecological network and regulated conditions and methods for the protection, use and preservation of nature. The decision-making process for the establishment of protected natural assets is carried out according to the following steps: evaluate the degree of importance of the natural asset to be protected: define the type of Protected Area to be established in order to ensure appropriate protection and management and start the legal procedure for proclamation, based on the selected type of PA to be established. The process of establishing protected natural assets according to the Law on Nature Protection begins with a request for development of a Study on Nature Protection. Request should be submitted by the Ministry or the local government depending on related protection category. The Agency for Environmental Protection in cooperation with the Institute of Marine Biology in the case of marine protected areas, are in charge of developing a Study on Nature Protection.

Law on Environmental Protection ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 52/16)- is the umbrella law in the area of environment and it lays down the principles of environmental protection and sustainable development, entities, environmental protection instruments and measures, access to information, public participation, and access to justice in environmental matters, environmental financing and other issues relevant for the environment. Other issues regulated by the Law include liability for environmental damage, environmental financing, and national plans and strategies required under certain multilateral environmental agreements, etc

Law on Foreign and Invasive Alien Species of Plants, Animals, and Fungi ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 18/2019)- regulates the prevention of introduction and spread of foreign and invasive alien species of plants, animals, and fungi, to mitigate and minimize the harmful impact on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and/or human health.

Water Law ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 27/07, 32/11, 48/15, and 84/18)- regulates the legal status and manner of integrated water management, water and coastal land, and water facilities, conditions and methods

for conducting water activities, and other issues of importance for water management and water resources.

Law on Protection from Adverse Effects of Climate Change ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 73/2019)- regulates protection from adverse effects of climate change, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, protection of the ozone layer, and other issues related to protection from adverse effects of climate change.

Law on Marine Fisheries and Mariculture ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 56/09, 40/11, and 47/15)- management of living resources of the sea, encompassing capture, collection, and protection of fish and other marine organisms based on sustainable development principles, in the fishing waters of Montenegro. This law also regulates aquaculture. Fish and other marine organisms in the fishing waters of Montenegro, as a common good, enjoy special protection and are used in the manner and under the conditions determined by this law and other regulation .

Law on Chemicals ("OG of MNE", 18/12)- regulates the classification, packaging, and labelling of chemicals, as well as the traffic, import, and export of hazardous chemicals, and other issues relevant to the protection of life and health of people and the environment from the harmful effects of chemicals.

Law on Environmental Noise ("OG of MNE", no: 28/11, 1/14)'- establishes measures to prevent or reduce the harmful impact of noise in the environment and other issues relevant to the protection of the environment and human health from the effects of noise.

Law on Public Maritime Doman ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No 51/08, 21/09, 73/10, 40/11) regulates the management of the narrow coastal strip designated as public maritime domain, its use, improvement and protection.

Law on Protection of the Sea from Pollution from Ships ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 027/14)- The law regulates the manner of protecting the sea from pollution caused by vessels navigating or located in the internal maritime waters and territorial sea of Montenegro, responsibility and compensation for damage in case of pollution, as well as the reception and handling of waste in ports.

Law on Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 075/18)- regulates the manner and procedure for assessing the impacts of projects that may have a significant impact on the environment, the preparation and evaluation of environmental impact assessments, and other issues relevant to environmental impact assessment .

Law on Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 080/05, No. 073/10, No. 040/11, No. 059/11, No. 052/16)- The conditions, methods, and procedures for conducting environmental impact assessments of specific plans and programs (hereinafter referred to as strategic assessments) are determined by integrating environmental protection principles into the process of preparing, adopting, and implementing plans and programs that have a significant impact on the environment.

Law on Hydrographic Activity ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 26/10)- regulated manner of conducting hydrographic activities, aimed at hydrographic-navigational support of navigation at sea and inland waterways to protect human lives and property at sea and inland waterways, research for the purpose of managing marine resources and environmental protection.

Law on Management of Municipal Wastewater ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 2/17)- regulated management of municipal wastewater, the conditions that sewerage systems and wastewater treatment plants should meet, the method of collection, treatment, and discharge of municipal wastewater, and other issues relevant to the management of municipal wastewater.

Law on Waste Management ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 64/11 and 39/16)- regulated types and classification of waste, planning, conditions, and methods of waste management, and other issues relevant to waste management.

Regulation on criteria and methodological standards for determining good status and monitoring of the marine environment ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 036/21).

Decision on the Protection of Certain Plant and Animal Species ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 76/06).

Regulation on Classification and Categorization of Waters ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 02/07).

Rulebook on the manner and deadlines for determining the status of surface waters ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 25/19).

Rulebook on the manner and deadlines for implementing measures to ensure the conservation, protection, and improvement of the quality of bathing water ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 028/19),

State Waste Management Plan 2015 - 2020 ("Official Gazette of Montenegro" No. 75/15 and 35/18).

Spatial Plan of Special Purpose for the Coastal Area (Special Purpose Spatial Plan for the Coastal Area).

Other documents:

- National Strategy for Sustainable Development until 2030
- National Biodiversity Strategy with Action Plan 2016-2020
- National Strategy on Integrated Coastal Area Management from 2015 to 2030
- National Strategy on Climate Change until 2030
- National Plan for Emergency Response in the Event of Sea Pollution from Vessels
- Numerous secondary legislation
- Legislation on tourism, maritime traffic, and others

3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:

a. Climate change

Law on Protection from the Adverse Effects of Climate Change (Official Gazette of Montenegro 73/2019) regulates the provisions and rules aimed at setting the protection against negative effects of the climate change, including the aim of reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, ozone layer protection and other issues related to the protection against known negative effects of climate change in general.

The National Climate Change Strategy until 2030 is a key instrument in the area of public policies for climate change management in Montenegro. It mandates the Government to act against climate change in an integrated and multi-sectoral manner, respecting international obligations under the UNFCCC. The strategy envisions that by 2030, Montenegro will be able to adapt to negative impacts and promote sustainable low-carbon development.

Paris agreement: Although not directly aimed at cruise tourism, this global agreement sets targets for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Signatory countries are obligated to develop and implement national plans that may include regulating emissions from the maritime sector. As a signatory to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change Montenegro has been obliged to regularly report towards UNFCCC Secretariat on, among other information: GHG Inventory, mitigation and adaptation climate actions, tracking the implementation and achievement of its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) under the Paris Agreement. Montenegro's contribution to the international community's efforts in combating climate change, expressed through the Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) to reduce GHG emissions, is at least 30% by 2030 compared to the baseline level of 1990. Therefore, the Government has clearly and ambitiously committed to joining international efforts to combat climate change by actively reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

The National Climate Change Adaptation Plan is currently being developed, covering four sectors: water, health, tourism, and agriculture, as these have been identified as the most vulnerable sectors in terms of adapting to climate change. Tourism has significantly increased over the past decade, especially in terms of the number of visitors and investment in tourist infrastructure. Consequently, Montenegro has committed to establishing a green/responsible tourism concept based on the principles of low-carbon development and adaptation measures must be taken to protect this sector.

Cruise ships use large quantities of fuel, mainly heavy fuel oil, which is a significant source of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, one of the main greenhouse gases. In addition to CO₂, ships emit other harmful gases, such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and sulphur dioxide (SO₂), which contribute to global warming, air pollution and acid rain. The expansion of cruise ship infrastructure, such as ports and resorts, can lead to deforestation and habitat destruction, further exacerbating climate change by reducing carbon sinks and biodiversity. Cruise ships require a significant amount of energy for propulsion, lighting, heating, cooling, and onboard activities. This energy is often derived from fossil fuels, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions.

Cruise ships contribute to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change and this case study can provide data on the carbon footprint of cruise tourism, aiding the development and enforcement of emission reduction targets.

Climate Indicators: Greenhouse gas emissions from cruise ships, energy consumption, and carbon footprint.

Climate Change Mitigation- Relevance 4

b. Biodiversity

Biodiversity and Conservation Policies- Relevance: 5

The National Biodiversity Strategy with Action plan 2016-2020 (NBSAP) is defined as a key document for nature conservation, establishing long-term goals and guidelines for the preservation of biological and landscape diversity. It also supports and integrates global biodiversity protection goals adopted within the framework of the UN Convention on Biological Diversity, including the Aichi Targets.

In addition to the Convention on Biological Diversity, Montenegro is a signatory country to many other international agreements closely related to the protection of nature and biodiversity such as: Convention concerning the Protection of World Cultural and Natural Heritage (UNESCO Convention), Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (Bon Convention), Convention on the Conservation of Wildlife and Natural Habitats (Bern Convention), Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES Convention), Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat (Ramsar Convention), etc.

CS can contribute achieving the following NBSAP targets:

- Strategic target A: biodiversity protection is in practice one of several most important social and political priorities in the overall development. Operational target: a) The society recognizes benefits from biodiversity and the need for priority protection, b)) Make biodiversity become a "positive" and priority topic for decision-makers.
- Strategic target D: significant reduction of identified direct pressures on biodiversity until 2020 registered. Operational target: e) Achieving sustainable tourism f) Measures to mitigate impact of invasive species g) Measures to mitigate impacts of climate change
- Strategic target E: Until 2020 preconditions created and targeted measures for biodiversity protection implemented. a) Activities implemented to protect the most endangered species, b) Activities implemented to protect the most vulnerable habitats
- Strategic target G: Knowledge of biodiversity improved, systematized and widely and equally available through developed mechanisms. Operational target: a) Develop researches and organize an efficient system of data collection and processing

Cruise tourism can lead to habitat degradation, pollution, and disturbances to wildlife. Data and findings from CS can serve as evidence to support stronger conservation efforts, including stricter regulations on tourist activities and promoting sustainable and responsible tourism practices. The CS can raise awareness among stakeholders, including policymakers, cruise operators, tourists, and local communities, about the environmental impacts of cruise tourism. Increased awareness can lead to greater support for the goals of the National Biodiversity Strategy and more responsible behaviour from all recognized stakeholders. The case study can highlight the need for improved monitoring and compliance mechanisms to ensure that cruise tourism activities do not harm biodiversity and habitats.

CS will contribute to fulfilling the measures from the *Local Biodiversity Action Plan of the Municipality of Kotor*, which is a legal obligation and aligned with the National Biodiversity Strategy:

- Establish more efficient control of maritime traffic at sea, as well as more efficient control of fisheries and mariculture.
- Raising awareness and spreading knowledge about the ecology and biology of the marine and terrestrial environment, and increasing public awareness of environmental issues.
- Promotion of compatible socio-economic development in accordance with the environmental and landscape values of the area, favouring local traditional activities with minimal impact on the environment.
- Development of guidelines and recommendations to mitigate the impact of socio-economic activities on marine and coastal ecosystems (tourism, fisheries, navigation, etc.).
- Conducting a local-level campaign to raise awareness about biodiversity protection. Educational initiatives for young people regarding environmental protection and biodiversity enhancement.

Marine Environmental Protection Policies Relevance: 5

Montenegro as signatory of the MARPOL Convention (International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships) directly regulate pollution from ships, including cruise liners. The case study can provide data on pollution levels in coastal waters, helping to assess compliance with these regulations and identify areas for improvement. This data can also highlight the effectiveness of existing policies and suggest enhancements.

CS can contribute to fulfilment obligation under Law on the Protection of the Sea from Pollution from Ships, according to whom is it prohibited :discharge of sewage from a ship, discharge of harmful substances into the air, installation of equipment or systems that use or contain substances that deplete the ozone layer, discharge of ballast water that contain microorganisms, invasive species, or other harmful substances.

Therefore, CS is according the article 3 of Law on the Protection of the Marine Environment

(Official Gazette of Montenegro, No. 73/2019) paragraphs: 1) protection, preservation, rehabilitation and valorisation and, where possible, restoration of the structure and functions of marine and coastal ecosystems and biodiversity protection; 3) prevention, when possible reduction of pollution of marine environment and coastal area, in a way that ensures the reduction of negatives impacts or risks to human health and/or biodiversity and ecosystem health and/or use of the sea and coasts in accordance with the law; 4) preservation, improvement and/or restoration of human balance activities and natural resources in the sea and coastal area; 5) preservation of the sea and coastal area for the benefit of present and future generations; 6) sustainable use of natural resources in the sea and coastal area, especially space, sea and inland waters; 7) preservation of the integrity of coastal ecosystems, landscapes and geomorphology.

Coastal Zone Management Plans Relevance : 5

CS is accordance with Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) plan, who aim to balance environmental, economic, social, cultural, and recreational objectives in coastal areas. The case study can offer insights into how cruise tourism impacts coastal ecosystems, local communities, and infrastructure, thereby supporting more sustainable coastal zone planning and management practices. The National Strategy for Integrated Coastal Zone Management sets the strategic goal of strengthening cooperation and coordination between social actors, effectively involving the public in decision-making processes, and utilizing available knowledge, thereby

contributing to the sustainability of societal development. As a specific measure, it emphasizes raising awareness about the need to preserve and enhance coastal area resources.

The CS contributes to the strategic goals of the National Strategy for Integrated Coastal Zone Management (NS IUOP) in terms of strengthening human resources and social cohesion:

- Implementing capacity-building programs
- Raising awareness about the need to preserve and improve coastal resources.

NS IUOP recognizes that tourists from cruise trips exert significant pressure on the sea and port infrastructure of Kotor (where these ships dock) and on the surrounding environment they visit. Although they are considered significant, there are no precise estimates of the economic benefits of this type of tourism for the local and national economy.

It contributes to fulfilling the measure: Contribute to the effectiveness of preventing and controlling pollution from sea-based sources, specifically the sub-measure: Determine the environmental capacity of the Bay of Kotor, primarily concerning the capacity of the marine ecosystem to accommodate large ships that negatively affect air quality, sea water quality, and disturb fish stocks, noise emissions, taking into account the fact that this activity is significant for local revenue growth.

c. Urban and rural planning

As a specific goal within the Draft Spatial Plan of Montenegro until 2040, the development and improvement of the Port of Kotor are defined, considering the possibility of relocating cruise ships from Kotor. The aim is to relocate cruise ship entries from Kotor to other locations in the Bay of Kotor, while leaving only the docking of luxury boats and yachts up to a maximum size of 150 meters in the port of Kotor. Furthermore, it is noted that the Port of Kotor represents a particularly problematic location due to its position in a part of the bay with very slow water circulation, and the pressure of pollution from the discharge of municipal wastewater and pollution from cruise ships is increasing. Therefore, it is proposed to define the acceptance capacities of the marine environment and establish a strict regime for entering and leaving the port. Furthermore, restrictions are envisaged on activities with significant impacts on the marine environment, such as shipbuilding, oil and gas exploitation (implementing the highest environmental protection measures, further away from the coast); large ships and cruise ships and monitoring their environmental impacts, positioning anchorages (avoiding locations of valuable/vulnerable habitat types); in the Bay of Kotor, and later in the entire Bay of Kotor, gradually introducing a rule allowing access only to vessels equipped with holding tanks; activities in port facilities and marinas, mineral resource exploitation, fish farming (in open sea and relocation from the Bay of Kotor), dredging activities (dredging activity should be limited to occasional dredging for deepening navigational routes and port basins); and a ban on waste disposal into the sea. Considering the data on pressures in the marine environment of the highly sensitive Bay of Kotor, the Spatial Plan of Montenegro until 2040 raises questions about further increasing the volume of nautical tourism, especially cruises, as well as further marina construction. To diminish the pressure on the most sensitive part of the Bay of Kotor, it is necessary to ensure the possibility for cruise ship reception in other ports of the Bay of Kotor, especially Zelenika, considering environmental safety and reducing the emission of harmful particles from exhaust gases (CO₂, SO₂, etc.), and ensuring the safety of the protected UNESCO area, particularly in the marine environment. Special attention in spatial planning should certainly be given to the preservation and protection of underwater springs, submarine springs, and all natural freshwater inflows into the Bay of Kotor. Besides the significant impact on the sea and marine environment, the consequent increase in the number of occasional and permanent residents in nautical tourism ports, as well as the number of visitors from ships (especially cruise ships), will lead to an increase in the amount of all types of waste and wastewater, and thus solid waste in the sea.

The Concept of Sea Utilization presents the sea as a significant potential and resource that needs to be exploited carefully and moderately. By 2040, numerous activities are planned, and the implementation of a large number of activities must be designed in collaboration with a greater number of marine biologists, who will contribute their knowledge from various fields to minimize the impacts on marine biodiversity. Negative impacts on biodiversity are reflected through the development of fisheries, construction of fishing ports, repair sites for fishing boats, increased presence of cruise ships, and other activities in the Bay of Kotor, from Petrovac towards Budva and Ulcinj.

d. Mobility

Transport Development Strategy of Montenegro 2019-2035" sets plans for enhancing the economic development, efficiency, safety, connectivity, and environmental sustainability of the country's transportation system, while simultaneously ensuring the integration of the transportation sector and completing the process of harmonizing the regulatory framework of the transportation sector with the EU's legal acquis, environmental, and safety standards and obligations. CS will contribute to the strategic goal of minimizing the negative impact of the development of transport and traffic infrastructure on the environment and society as a whole i.e., 7.1. Environmental protection and human health measures.

e. Tourism

The Tourism Development Strategy of Montenegro 2022-2025, for the municipality of Kotor recognizes the natural and cultural-historical characteristics of the Kotor-Risan Bay area as a special value and protection of cultural heritage is an absolute imperative in the further planning and development of the city. Furthermore, the Strategy envisions that the Bay of Kotor area should be developed in a targeted and controlled manner, using natural, cultural, and created potentials sustainably. It is necessary to plan the development of tourist accommodation very carefully, as the carrying capacity of the municipalities in this cluster, especially in Kotor, is almost exhausted. Additionally, when drafting strategic documents and implementing activities, international agreements and conventions should be taken into account.

The insights gained from the CS can inform the development and refinement of policies and regulations aimed at mitigating the environmental impacts of cruise tourism. This can include guidelines for sustainable tourism practices, limits on the number of cruise ships, and specific conservation measures for affected areas.

f. Participatory research

The CS will contribute to the implementation of the Smart Specialization Strategy, which aims to stimulate public and private investments in research, technological development, and innovation. It seeks to integrate research and innovative capacities, bringing together a critical mass of researchers and innovators who will collaborate on strategically important research and innovation topics, with the goal of achieving research excellence and strengthening the potential of domestic innovative products for commercialization. One of the focus areas is the application of green and smart technologies in sustainable nautical tourism in Montenegro. Information and communication technologies (ICT) in Montenegro have become essential and present in all other priority areas of development, as well as in all economic and social aspects of life, with a recognized tendency for growth in this sector. ICT is being developed in the context of improving information systems in public administration, education, industry, and healthcare, all in accordance with modern technological trends and the concept of Industry 4.0.

This case study will also include the research results of the researchers from the Maritime Faculty in Kotor who conducted extensive research on the impact of cruise ships on air quality in the Bay of Kotor. Through a series of research endeavors, using mobile devices for particle detection, the researchers analyzed the concentration of pollutants from ship exhaust systems, particularly during the cruising season.

g. Agriculture

The impact of cruise tourism on agriculture is often indirect but can still be significant, especially in regions where agriculture plays a crucial role in the economy.

In the Fisheries Development Strategy 2024-2029, conflicts between environmental protection and tourism, as well as commercial fishing, are recognized as one of the threats to commercial sea fishing. Strategic goal III: ecologically, economically, and socially sustainable fisheries and aquaculture. The marine fisheries and mariculture sector is supported through measures aimed at strengthening the professional fishing fleet, improving the mariculture sector, and sustainable management and conservation of fish resources and other marine organisms.

Cruise ships can generate pollution through wastewater discharge, air emissions, and waste generation. Pollution from cruise tourism, if not properly managed, can contaminate water affecting agricultural productivity and food safety. Therefore, CS can raise awareness how the impact of cruise tourism on marine ecosystems can affect local fisheries and highlight how cruise activities influence fish populations and habitats, supporting the development of sustainable fisheries management practices.

h. Others

National Strategy for Air Quality Management has been developed with a goal to contribute effectively to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals related to air quality and biodiversity and ecosystem protection by reducing the levels of air pollution in line with the WHO Guidelines and the UNECE Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (Air Convention). The Strategy is also expected to contribute to reducing the health-related costs of air pollution by improving the well-being of the population, as well as favouring the transition to a green economy.

One of the strategic goals of the National Circular Transition Strategy by 2030 with the Action Plan 2023-2024 is "Enhanced development of tourism based on sustainable development principles."

Among the development priorities of the Municipality of Kotor, according to the Regional Development Strategy for the period 2014-2020, is "Protection and valorisation of cultural and natural heritage and the environment."

At the heart of Montenegro's sustainable development lies the issue of sustainable management of natural resources, as a prerequisite for the long-term preservation of natural capital. Similarly, due to the importance that natural capital holds for the growth and development of the economy, it is necessary to direct economic development towards greening the economy, efficient resource management, and not jeopardizing the sustainability of the volume, quality, and potential of natural resources. Emphasis should be placed on the significance of the opportunities provided by ecosystem services, especially in protected natural areas. CS is directly connected to Goal 14: Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development. National Sustainable Development Strategy by 2030 defines goals that can be grouped into several priority areas such as: (1) better management of water resources and demand; (2) improved rational use of energy, increased use of renewable sources, and mitigation of adaptation to climate change; (3) sustainable mobility through appropriate measures in transportation; (4) sustainable tourism as a leading economic sector; (5) sustainable agriculture and rural development; (6) sustainable urban development; and (7) sustainable management of marine resources, coasts, and marinas. Montenegro, in terms of implementing the National Sustainable Development Strategy by 2030, as the overarching document for sustainable development, which is aligned with the UN Agenda 2030 Sustainable Development Goals, has committed to improving resource

efficiency in the tourism sector: promoting greening of tourism and improving resource efficiency through support for green investments in hotel and hospitality capacities, as well as capacities for water supply and waste management during their construction; reducing the amount of waste from tourist activities and improving management of existing waste; protecting sensitive ecosystems from the impacts of tourism development; stimulating the introduction of new green technologies in tourism; encouraging the preservation of destination attractiveness in the long term, including innovations through ecological management, marketing, new business or organizational forms; improving regulation in markets where price signals are inefficient (creating better price signals and market instruments that can reduce costs resulting from negative environmental externalities); introducing green public procurement to promote the development of green innovations (link with target 4.5 NDS), SDGs 6 (6.3), 7 (7.3), 11 (11.6), 12 (12.b), 15 (15.5).

Montenegro is a signatory to the Green Agenda Declaration, which is aligned with the European Green Deal, and it obliges signatory countries from the Western Balkans to implement measures in the areas of climate change and pollution prevention, energy development, transportation, and circular economy, as well as biodiversity conservation, sustainable agriculture, and food production.

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Ministry of Tourism, Ecology, Sustainable Development, and Northern Development -

Directorate for Ecology, Directorate for Tourism Development and Legislation, Directorate for Climate Change and Nature Conservation.(Relevance:5)

Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Management- Directorate for Fisheries (Relevance:3)

Ministry of Transport and Maritime Affairs- The Directorate for Maritime Affairs carries out tasks related to the development policy in the field of maritime traffic, navigation safety, pollution prevention from vessels, protection of human lives, security of ships and ports, proposing activities for the strategic development of the maritime economy, as well as tasks related to seafarers, concluding agreements on mutual recognition of maritime authorities, seafarer training, monitoring and implementation of seafarers' status.

Port Authority of Kotor (Relevance:4)

Ministry of Culture and Media-Directorate for cultural heritage (Relevance:4)

Environmental Protection Agency-Environmental Monitoring Sector (Relevance:5)

Statistical Office (MONSTAT)- Statistical sector agriculture, fisheries, business statistics, and environmental and forestry ; Social statistics and demography sector (Relevance:5)

University of Montenegro - Institute of Marine Biology, Maritime Faculty, Faculty of Tourism (Relevance:5)

Municipality of Kotor- Secretariat for the Protection of Natural and Cultural Heritage, Coordinates and participates in the alignment of criteria and the implementation of measures, regulations, and guidelines that ensure the preservation of Kotor on the UNESCO World Heritage List, as well as various other responsibilities related to the conservation of natural and cultural heritage. (Relevance 4)

Local tourist organizations and the operator- Local Tourist Organization of the Municipality of Kotor, Tourist Organization of Kotor, BCM Yacht Management Company, (Relevance:2)

5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

We will provide aforementioned institutions with detailed overview of the project, and express our interest in collaborating with them in any capacity as well as specify how their expertise aligns with the project goals and how their involvement could be beneficial. Providing detailed overviews of the project will help these institutions understand the scope and objectives clearly. By emphasizing the mutual benefits of collaboration, we will try to garner more interest and enthusiasm from them.

6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?

a. Agenda setting	Project Management Department of the Chamber of Economy of Montenegro
b. Policy formulation	Project Management Department of the Chamber of Economy of Montenegro
c. Decision making	President of the Chamber of Economy of Montenegro
d. Policy implementation	Project Management staff
e. Policy evaluation	Project Management Department Manager

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?

Even if policies cannot be changed or influenced directly, a CS can still have several benefits and outcomes for future strategies by raising awareness, empowering communities, stimulating policy discussions, promoting alternative tourism models, facilitating research and monitoring, and encouraging corporate responsibility.

The CS is highlighting the negative impacts of cruise tourism can raise awareness among stakeholders, including policymakers, local communities, and the general public, about the potential social, environmental and economic consequences associated with this industry. Increased awareness can lead to informed decision-making and more responsible tourism practices and sustainable tourism development in the future.

In addition, CS can empower local communities affected by cruise tourism to voice their concerns and advocate for their rights. By providing evidence of negative impacts, communities can mobilize support, build alliances with other stakeholders, and work towards sustainable tourism development that prioritizes community well-being and environmental conservation. Lack of local community involvement and awareness about conservation efforts can undermine protection measures.

While direct policy change may not be feasible, the CS can contribute and stimulate policy discussions and advocacy efforts aimed at regulating the cruise tourism industry and mitigating its negative impacts. Policymakers may be prompted to consider alternative approaches, such as implementing stricter regulations, imposing environmental taxes, limit the number of cruise ships that can dock during the week or promoting destination diversification to reduce dependency on cruise tourism and CS can highlight the need for further research and monitoring of the impacts of cruise tourism on coastal communities, natural environments, and cultural heritage and by identifying knowledge gaps and research priorities facilitate evidence-based decision-making in the tourism sector.

Environmental dimension

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation ?

Establishing Marine Protected Areas in Montenegro is essential for preventing further threats to marine biodiversity and natural resources. Priority locations for establishing new Marine Protected Areas have been established in coastal waters at Platamuni, Katič and Stari Ulcinj. Biodiversity in these zones is mainly threatened by: habitat loss and fragmentation, the overexploitation of wildlife, and climate change. In 2021, three protected marine areas were established - Platamuni, Katič, and Stari Ulcinj - which were declared as nature parks. In addition, the sites of Dražin vrt and Sopot in the Bay of Kotor were placed under preventive protection as special nature reserves. The total area of protected marine areas amounts to 4,765 hectares.

UNESCO site- the Natural and Cultural-Historical Region of Kotor is located in the Boka Kotorska Bay, on the Adriatic coast of Montenegro. Boko Kotorska Bay has been inscribed on the World Heritage List meeting criteria: (i)(ii)(iii)(iv). The property encompasses the best preserved part of the bay covering its inner south-eastern portion. The inscribed property comprises 14,600 ha with a landscape composed of two interrelated bays surrounded by mountains rising rapidly to nearly 1,500 metres. The property is linked to the rest of the Boka Kotorska Bay through a narrow channel forming the principal visual central axis of the area. The Outstanding

Universal Value of the Cultural -Historical Region of Kotor is embodied in the quality of the architecture in its fortified and open cities, settlements, palaces and monastic ensembles, and their harmonious integration to the cultivated terraced landscape on the slopes of high rocky hills.

-Montenegro as a candidate country to EU accession is actively working towards the establishment of the **NATURA 2000** network, which is a key instrument of the EU's nature and biodiversity policy.

Natura 2000 habitats (Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC Annex I habitat types) in Boka Kotorska Bay:

-1160 Large shallow inlets and bays,

-1170 Reefs

-1210 Annual vegetation of drift lines

- 9260 *Castanea sativa* woods

-9340 *Quercus ilex* and *Quercus rotundifolia* forests

Kotor-Risan Bay area is on official lists of candidate **Emerald sites** (Areas of Special Conservation Interest) under Bern Convention (site code- ME000000Q, site area(ha)- 2778).

Important Plant Areas of Montenegro (IPA sites) – Kotor-Risan Bay area

(Site Code ME24, 2778 ha)

Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs)-Kotor Risan Bay (32034), area of KBA (km²): 27.81;

KBA classification: Global/Regional TBD'

The Bay of Kotor-Risan: An **area of special importance** for the reproduction and feeding of fish and fish fry.

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

In Boka Kotorska bay there are no long sandy beaches which are characteristic of other parts of Montenegrin coastline. What makes this Riviera special are numerous pontoons and smaller sandy or pebbly beaches. One of the most popular beaches in Boka Kotorska bay is the beach called Bajova kula or Bajo's tower.

b. Habitats: Key habitats

In the Adriatic Sea the main commercial fish species are: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*), red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*), breams (*Pagellus* spp.), whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*), anglerfish (*Lophius budegassa* and *Lophius piscatorius*), common sole (*Solea vulgaris*), horned octopus (*Eledone cirrhosa*) and musky octopus (*Eledone moschata*), common cuttlefish (*Sepia officinalis*), European squid (*Loligo vulgaris*), Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*) and deep-water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*) (Vergoc et al., 2004).

Particular importance in Boka Kotorska bay is the fishing of sardines (*Sardina pilchardus*) and anchovies (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) that in this area have important spawning and nursery grounds. Juvenile anchovies and sardines are caught using beach seines of small mesh size (5-6 mm) and artificial light. This type of traditional fishing has been performed for centuries in the Boka Kotorska bay, but no data on quantities of fish caught or fishing effort are available (RAC/SPA draft rep.). The more common species caught by different types of beach seine net are the following: Boops boops, *Sardina pilchardus*, *Engraulis encrasicolus*, *Trachurus trachurus*, *Scomber japonicus*.

The largest part of the seabed of the bay (more than 87% of the surface) is covered by the biocenosis of coastal terrigenous muds (VTC). Biocenosis of Muddy Detritic bottoms (2%) and Muddy Sands cover other small portions of the seabed of the bay.

A recent scientific article on the distribution of *Fucus virsoides*, an endemic alga of the Adriatic Sea, indicates the presence of the alga in 14 localities in Boka Kotorska Bay. Four of the identified growing sites have recently disappeared, probably because of anthropogenic influence (e.g. habitat disturbance, organic wastes, temperature and salinity increase) (Macic, 2006). The presence of the invasive red alga *Womersleyella setacea* (Rhodophyta, Ceramiales) was recorded in the Boka Kotorska Bay for the first time in 2003 (Nikolić et al.2010).

Photophilous algae are present in Kotor Bay only in limited portions of the shoreline and, due to the low water transparency, only in the first few meters of the upper infralittoral zone. Given the scale of the map (1:5000) is not possible to map the presence of photophilous Algae as a separate biocenosis.

Biocenosis of Sciaphilous algae is widely distributed in the inner part of the Bay. In most cases, given the complex geomorphology of the seafloor (e.g. hard and soft substrata, natural and artificial ones, slope of the seabed) this habitat is present in mosaic within other biocenosis. In the Northern and the Western part of the Bay, the seabed is characterized by natural substrata with high slopes, Sciaphilous algae colonize the first 8-10 m of the infralittoral.

Coralligenous habitats cover about 2% of the surface of the bottom. This important habitat is present in 5 localities (Strp, Perast, to the west of Perast, around the small islands of Sveti Dorde and Gospa od Skrpjela and Drazin Vrt). Other small Coralligenous assemblages are located in the central and northern part of the bay. The Coralligenous assemblage is sometimes in mosaic with Sciaphilous Algae or with VTC. The facies with *Savalia savaglia* and *Leptogorgia sarmentosa* (belonging to coralligenous) is present in the site of Drazin Vrt, where it covers an area of about 5,000 m² corresponding to about 0,02% of the seabed of the bay.

The seagrass habitats cover 0,15% of the seabed. Seagrass are present in 4 coastal sites. One of these localities (Dobrota) is interested by the presence of *Posidonia oceanica* (about 21.000 m²). 25 Deep holes with possible presence of living

Cladocora aggregation are located mainly in the central part of the bay, close to the northern coast.

The entire bay plays a key role as nursery for several species. Some studies are available for *Sardina pilchardus* (sardine) (Pešić et al., 2010, 2006) and *Engraulis encrasicolus* (anchovy) (Mandić et al, 2011, 2012). The central and eastern part of the bay seems to have the higher concentration of eggs belonging to these pelagic species

that represent 83% of the biomass caught by the fishing gears in the area; both of them are GFCM priority species⁴. According to the information collected on site, also other species in different periods of the years (e.g. *Pagrus pagrus* during summer months;

Dicentrarchus labrax in February) enter with abundant swarms in the bay for reproduction. Juveniles were not observed during the surveys because the period of observation (April) did not correspond to the peaks of juveniles in the shallow water. Fish visual censuses carried out in late summer- autumn are expected to evidence significant fish recruitment.

The presence of the *Savalia savaglia* facies constitutes an extraordinary value for the bay. Long-living organisms like *S. savaglia*⁵ producing three-dimensional hard skeletons can play an important role as habitat-modifiers (ecosystem engineers sensu).

The presence of elevated and complex tertiary substrates promotes benthic biodiversity and ecosystem processes. The high density of the colonies in the Dražin Vrt area needs special attention and protection measures.

The areas colonized by the particular coralligenous assemblages (in total about 2% of the seabed) characterized by the presence of *Cladocora caespitosa*, large-sized sponges (*Axinella* spp.) and cnidarians, notably the gorgonian *Leptogorgia sarmentosa* and of the yellow cluster anemone *Parazoanthus axinellae* form another hot spot of biodiversity. The key role of *Cladocora* in the ecosystem of the bay is evident.

Today the huge colonies observed are dead and *Cladocora* is present in the shallow water of the bay mainly with medium and small colonies. In any case the role of the dead *Cladocora* is fundamental as substratum for the development of benthic communities.

c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats

- 1160 Large shallow inlets and bays,
- 1170 Reefs
- 1210 Annual vegetation of drift lines
- 9260 *Castanea sativa* woods
- 9340 *Quercus ilex* and *Quercus rotundifolia* forests

d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats

Six priority habitats were mapped in the Boka Kotorska Bay. The *Savalia savaglia* facies is worth a special mention.

The small area in Dražin Vrt (about 5.000 m²) represents a unicum at a Mediterranean level thanks to the extraordinary density and abundance of *S. savaglia* colonies and the shallow water distribution of the species. *S.*

savaglia should be particularly protected not only for its specific rarity, endemism and vulnerability but also because it has a prominent role in sustaining high levels of biodiversity and ecosystem functioning in the surrounding benthos of the twilight zone (Cerrano et al., 2010). In particular the *S. savaglia* facies and the role of *Cladocora* in the bay (including the historical regression of the species in the coastal areas) should be further investigated through special studies.

— *Posidonia* beds (*Posidonia oceanica*) priority habitat [code 1120] — Reefs [code 1170] — Submerged or partially submerged caves [code 8330] — Coralligenous habitat [code 1170]

e. Fauna: Key fauna species

The fauna of the Adriatic Sea has not been sufficiently investigated yet, however according to the most recent data, there are more than 300 species of algae, 40 species of sponges, 150 species of crustaceans, 340 species of molluscs, more than 400 species of fish, 3 species of marine turtles and 4 species of dolphins in the Montenegrin part of the Adriatic. Most of the known and economically important species are distributed along the littoral zone (up to 200 m deep), but some of them can be found in the transitional bathing zone (200-300 m of depth), such as Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*) and *Thenia muricata*. The main areas for conservation of biodiversity are Boka Kotorska and Bojana mouth, which are important spawning sites and a source of food for economically important species.

Boka Kotorska bay area with its diverse and unique habitats, is home to several protected and endangered species:

- *Posidonia oceanica* (L.) Delile is a protected species at the national level according to the Decision on the Protection of Certain Plant and Animal Species ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", no. 76/06), and the underwater meadows of this seagrass represent a priority habitat of the European Union. It is also a strictly protected plant species under the Bern Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (Appendix I).

- *Zostera noltii* Hornem is also a protected seagrass that has been observed in the inner part of the Bay of Kotor. It forms communities together with the also protected species *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Asch.

- *Zostera marina* L. (Med.) and *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Asch. are strictly protected plant species under the Bern Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (Appendix I), and they are significant species for the Mediterranean according to the Barcelona Convention SPAMI Protocol (Annex II).

- *Lithophaga lithophaga*, *Pinna nobilis*, *Tonna galea*, *Cladocora caespitosa*, *Savalia savaglia*, *Tethya aurantium*, *Aplysina aerophoba*, *Aplysina cavernicola*, *Axinella cannabina*, *Holothuria impatiens*, *Holothuria tubulosa*, *Holothuria polii*, *Hippocampus guttulatus*, *Caretta caretta*, *Chelonia mydas* i *Tursiops truncatus*.

- Protected sponge species include: *Axinella verrucosa*, *Aplysina aerophoba*, *Geodia cydonium*, *Suberites domuncula*, *Thenia muricata*, *Dysidea avarai*.....*Aplysina aerophoba* (golden sponge) is a species of importance for the Mediterranean according to the Barcelona Convention and the SPAMI Protocol, and like *Axinella canabina*, it is also a protected species. These sponge species are abundant in the Bay of Kotor-Risan.

Cladocora caespitosa - is protected under national law, the Habitats Directive of the European Union, Bern Convention.

Taxonomic analysis of the collected material in the area of the Bay of Kotor-Risan indicates the presence of: 35 species of Polychaeta (segmented worms), 52 species of decapod crustaceans, 64 species of Bivalvia, 62 species of

Gastropoda, 9 species of Cephalopoda, 1 species of Polyplacophora, and 2 species of Scaphopoda.

The waters of the Bay of Kotor harbour 3 protected but also endangered species of mollusks, namely: *Pinna nobilis* L. (noble pen shell), *Tonna galea* L. (barrel-shaped tun), and *Lithophaga lithophaga* L. (date mussels). These are protected species according to national legislation (Official Gazette of the Republic of Montenegro no. 76/06), as well as under the SPAMI Protocol of the Barcelona Convention (1976) and the EU Directive 92/43/EEC for the conservation of natural habitats, flora, and fauna.

Congerius kusceri is national protected species and it is listed as "Endangered" on the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species.

f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC

Montenegro is not an EU member, it is a candidate country and aligns national legislation with many EU regulations and directives, including the Habitats Directive. As such, Montenegro continuously working in identifies species listed in Annex II and establishment of NATURA 2000 network.

g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species

In Montenegro, 351 bird species has been registered so far (of the total 533 registered in Europe until today or 66% of the European bird fauna). Out of the total number of bird species registered so far, 213 species belong to the certain breeding and seven species are possible breeding, while ten are considered to be extinct, such as for example, *Aegypius monachus*. 106 species are considered to be resident, i.e. species which spend the whole life cycle in Montenegro. This number includes two species that are introduced (pheasant and chukar). 107 species of birds registered in Montenegro are breeding migratory birds. On the other hand, Montenegro is located in one of the four most important corridors for birds in Europe – Adriatic Flyway, through which millions of birds annually migrate to Africa and vice versa.

The status of true seabirds in Montenegro, considering summer visitors, migrating and wintering species, are not be fully assessed yet. According BirdLife International in Montenegro is registries 23 seabirds.

The presence of internationally significant bird species can be indicated based on data from the national EMERALD database for the areas of Tivatska salt planes and the Natural and Cultural-Historical Area of Kotor (Kotor-Risan Bay).

Applying international criteria under the Bern Convention (Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats) and the EU Wild Birds Directive (79/409 EEC, 91/244/EEC, 94/24 EC & 94/C241/08), within the EMERALD project in Montenegro, the presence of the following internationally significant bird species has been confirmed at sites considered relevant to the wider Boka Kotorska area: for the Natural and Cultural-Historical Area of Kotor, characteristic birds include: on the coast, we have gulls (*Larus genei*), the kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*), and cormorants (*Phalacrocorax aristotelis* and *Phalacrocorax carbo*) which are quite rare. The house sparrow (*Passer domesticus*) is by far the most common bird in urban areas, and swallows (*Hirundo rustica*) nest in old walls. In groves and maquis, common species include: thrushes (Turdidae), tits (Paridae), goldcrests (Regulidae), warblers (Sylviidae), and the very ornamental hoopoe (*Upupa* sp). In deciduous forests, present species include: the turtle dove (*Streptopelia turtur*) and the stock dove (*Columba oenas*). Many other species

from the families of grouse, cuckoos, owls, shrikes, and others are also present.

The coastal area of Grbalj is on the Adriatic migration corridor, which is one of the 4 most significant migration corridors for birds on the Europe-Africa route. Many of them find nesting and wintering sites in the maquis. Such birds include warblers of the genus *Sylvia* sp., tits of the genus *Parus* sp., then the black-headed bunting (*Emberiza melanocephala*), the hawfinch (*Coccothraustes coccothraustes*), the western rock nuthatch (*Sitta neumayer*), the European robin (*Erithacus rubecula*), and others. This area is also a migration corridor for birds of prey such as the Levant sparrowhawk (*Accipiter brevipes*) and the Eleonora's falcon (*Falco eleonora*).

h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC

Larus genei, *Sterna albifrons*, *Chroicocephalus genei* (Breme, 1839), *Columba Palumbus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Alcedo atthis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Alectoris graeca* (Meisner, 1804)

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.

The Management Plan for the Natural and Cultural-Historical Area of Kotor was adopted in 2011. It identifies problems and recommendations important for the protection of the natural and cultural-historical area of Kotor as a UNESCO World Heritage site. It is of particular concern that the revision of the Management Plan has not been completed since the 2018 joint UNESCO World Heritage Centre/ICOMOS Reactive Monitoring mission and it is recommended that this is prioritised. In addition, the Management Plan should be integrated into the evolving legal framework, particularly in anticipation of the challenges of tourism management and the potential impacts of major tourism infrastructure projects.

Management of the property and its defined buffer zone will be crucial to maintain the property and its integrity as a unique cultural landscape and an entity in geographical, historical, and cultural terms. Enforcement of regulatory measures for the buffer zone and the development of an integrated approach to conservation, planning and management of the area as a unity will also be required. However, the ability of the overall landscape to reflect its value is being compromised by the gradual erosion of traditional practices and ways of life and of the harmony between the buildings, planning and landscape. However, the conditions of integrity are endangered by development and urbanisation caused by ongoing transformation processes in the socio-economic structure of the area. Current developments, including new tourism centres, roads, and buildings on the coast itself, threaten to lead to the gradual yet irreversible transformation of the coastline as well as the abandonment of the traditional terraced structures.

At the same time, a new legal framework for the area of cultural heritage conservation was created with the Law on the Protection of the Natural and Cultural-Historical Area of Kotor has also been adopted, which prescribed integrated protection of the property and its buffer zone. The Law on Protection of the Natural and Cultural-Historic Region of Kotor (2013) makes provisions for the establishment of the Council for Management of the Kotor Region, with the role of coordinating conservation, preservation and management of the property. In addition, with the buffer zone defined in 2011 encompassing the entire area of the Boka Kotorska Bay, the groundwork has been laid to treat this cultural landscape in an integrated manner through spatial and development plans. However, increased awareness to treat the inscribed property and the buffer zone as an integral part of the unique cultural landscape of the Boka Kotorska Bay is needed. Challenges remain for the further definition of common development strategies for the property and its buffer zone, for integrated planning

and for the establishment of an overall management system. These measures will be essential to ensure that uncontrolled and excessive urbanization, as well as infrastructure development, are adequately addressed to ensure that no adverse impacts to the Outstanding Universal Value of the property occur. Adequate and sufficient resources of the entities responsible for the property will also need to be secured to be able to carry out preservation, protection and enhancement of the property.

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

On scale 1 to 5 where 1 is least relevant and 5 is most relevant, there are main economic activities in Boka Kotorska Bay Area:

- Tourism and accommodation- 5
- Fishing - 4
- Mariculture – 3
- Agriculture- 2
- Food processing and preparation – 2 (there are some olive groves and wineries)
- Family business and small enterprises - 4
- Trade – 4
- Construction – 5
- Maritime transport- 4

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Factors affecting the property Natural and Cultural -Historical Region of Kotor in 2023 according State of Conservation UNESCO (<https://whc.unesco.org/en/soc/4448/>) :

- Changes in traditional ways of life and knowledge system (Relevance: 3)
- Ground transport infrastructure
- Housing (Relevance: 4)
- Impacts of tourism / visitor / recreation (Relevance: 5)
- Land conversion (Relevance:4)
- Legal framework (Relevance:5)
- Major visitor accommodation and associated infrastructure (Relevance: 4)
- Management systems/ management plan (Relevance:5)
- Society's valuing of heritage (Relevance:3)

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of

the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Based on the Information on the State of the Environment in Montenegro, the main pressures/impacts on the coastal area are:

- Pollution (Relevance: 5)

Primarily discharge of wastewater from households, industry, and tourist facilities directly into the sea significantly contributes to the pollution of coastal waters (e.g. in the municipality of Kotor there are approximately 29 local, in Tivat - 13, smaller and larger local sewage discharges into the sea that are not connected to the centralized water treatment system and water treatment plant), leading to water quality degradation, harming marine and coastal life and affecting the health of coastal ecosystems.

Ballast Water Pollution-potentially introducing invasive species and pathogens into local marine environments, disrupting ecosystems.

Plastic waste (on the beaches as well as floating waste) further burden the marine ecosystem.

-Urbanization and Construction (Relevance: 5)

Intensive development of tourist infrastructure and residential buildings along the coast leads to the loss of biodiversity and natural habitats and the degradation of coastal ecosystems. The construction of new buildings is often not accompanied by adequate planning and environmental protection. Urbanization of the coastal area of the Bay of Kotor and the coastal area outside the bay, causes increased pollution through input of organic matter into the marine environment.

In addition, an intensive development of tourist infrastructure and residential buildings as well as development of real estate for secondary housing along the coast leads to the loss of biodiversity and natural habitats and the degradation of coastal ecosystems.

-Tourism (Relevance: 5)

Mass tourism during the summer season increases the amount of waste, water, and energy consumption, and pressure on infrastructure.

Mass tourism during the summer season, due to increased number of residents than permanent population, increases the amount of waste, water, and energy consumption, and pressure on infrastructure. Pronounced seasonality of tourism due to more recently significant growth of nautical tourism and cruisers with the construction of the cable car from Kotor to the "Lovćen" National Park, with a capacity of 48 gondolas that can transport 1,200 passengers has significant implications for balanced and sustainable use of natural resources.

- Coastal Erosion (Relevance: 4)

Natural processes, as well as human activities such as construction and resource exploitation, contribute to coastal erosion. This process threatens coastal settlements, infrastructure, and natural habitats.

-Resource Exploitation (Relevance: 3)

Overexploitation of marine resources, including illegal fishing and sand extraction, inadequate fishing practices

and the age of the fishing fleet and equipment, negatively impacts biodiversity, habitats and the stability of coastal ecosystems.

- Lack of Adequate Waste Management (Relevance: 3)

An underdeveloped waste management system (poor and outdated infrastructure for waste management) leads to coastal area pollution, especially during the tourist season when the amount of waste significantly increases.

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).

a. Yes, no?

Yes

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

National

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?

The Environmental Protection Agency organizes and conducts monitoring of all environmental segments based on the Environmental Protection Law, except for water quality, which falls under the jurisdiction of Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management.

d. How long is it being implemented?

The Environmental State Monitoring Program of Montenegro has been implemented since 2008. Environmental monitoring is conducted based on the annual Monitoring Program prepared by the Environmental Protection Agency and submitted to the Ministry of Tourism, Ecology, Sustainable Development and Northern Region Development no later than November 1st of the current year for the following year. This excludes the Water Quality Monitoring Program, proposed by the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management which, in accordance with the Water Law ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Montenegro", No. 027/07 and "Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 073/10, 032/11, 047/11, 048/15, 052/16, 055/16, 02/17), is implemented by the Hydro-Meteorological and Seismological Institute of Montenegro. The drinking water quality monitoring program is implemented by the administrative body responsible for health affairs (Institute of Public Health) in accordance with the Environmental Protection Law ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", No. 52/16), in accordance with specific regulations. The Centre for Ecotoxicological Studies (CETI) conducts air quality monitoring.

The annual Monitoring Program is adopted by the Government. Monitoring is in accordance with the Environmental Protection Law and is in the public interest.

Based on the data obtained through the implementation of the annual monitoring program, the EPA prepares an annual Environmental State Report, which is submitted to the Ministry for approval and, subsequently, to the

Government for adoption. The report provides an assessment of the overall state of the environment.
e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?
<p>The implementation of the annual monitoring program for all environmental segments is an obligation defined by the Environmental Protection Law and is carried out in accordance with the available funds from the budget of Government for the given year.</p> <p>For example, the Environmental Monitoring Program for the year 2023 included six programs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - air quality (NO, NO2, NOx, SO2, CO, PM2.5, PM10 (Pb, As, Cd, Ni, BaP in PM10), O3, CH4, THC, Hg, C6H6) -airborne allergenic pollen, -the state of the coastal ecosystem of Montenegro (Eutrophication; Physical-chemical parameters (temperature, transparency, pH, oxygen saturation, salinity); Contaminants- monitoring of contaminants in seawater, sediment, and biota (Inorganic pollutants: Fe, Mn, Cd, Hg,Cu,Ni,Pb,Zn, Cr, As, Sn; Organic pollutants: organotin compounds, organochlorine pesticides, PCB congeners, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), mineral oils, chlorophenols); Biodiversity (fitoplankton, zooplankton, alien/invasive species); Marine litter) - the content of harmful and hazardous substances in soil (Cd, Pb, Hg, As, Cr, Ni, F, Cu, Mo, B, Zn, Co and POPs (PCBs, DDT, aldrin, dieldrin, heptachlor, endrin, HBC, mireks, α-HCH, β-HCH, PFOS, PBDE, Dioksini/furani (PCDD/F), PAH, Organotin compounds (TBT, TMT)), - environmental radioactivity, and - noise.

15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
a. spatial coverage
<p>Limited geographic scope can lead to inadequate data from certain regions, especially distant or hard-to-reach areas (much of the monitoring tends to be concentrated along the shoreline, with less attention given to offshore areas). This can result in an incomplete picture of environmental or resource conditions. If monitoring points are unevenly distributed, it can create gaps in the data and make analysis and interpretation of results difficult. Insufficient spatial coverage can lead that the collected samples are not representative of the entire area of interest, leading to biased or inaccurate conclusions. Expanding spatial coverage often requires significant financial resources, equipment, and human resources, which can be challenging for organizations with limited budgets. (Relevance: 5)</p>
b. temporal coverage
<p>Inadequate temporal coverage can lead to significant gaps in understanding environmental changes, patterns and trends over time, and it may lead to incomplete analyses or inaccurate assessments of environmental conditions. Adequate temporal coverage is essential for understanding long-term environmental processes, tracking seasonal variations, assessing trends in environmental indicators, and detecting anomalies or abrupt changes. Temporal coverage can vary depending on the objectives of the monitoring program, the frequency of data collection, and the availability of resources. Ensuring sufficient temporal coverage often involves establishing monitoring protocols that specify the frequency and duration of data collection, maintaining consistency in data collection</p>

methods over time, and addressing any gaps or interruptions in data collection to maintain continuity. (Relevance:4)

c. data quality and resolution

Implementing quality assurance and quality control procedures is important to verify data accuracy, detect errors, and ensure data reliability throughout the monitoring process. Regular calibration of monitoring instruments and adherence to standardized measurement protocols to maintain data accuracy and comparability. Higher (spatial and temporal) resolution data provides more detailed information but may require more financial resources for collection, storage, and processing. The choice of data resolution depends on the specific monitoring objectives and the characteristics of the monitored system. Poor data quality or resolution can complicate data interpretation and analysis, leading to ambiguous results or misleading conclusions. Incompatibility or inconsistency between datasets collected at different resolutions or using different methodologies can hinder data integration and synthesis. Data management practices such as data archiving and documentation are important for preserving and utilizing historical data to support ongoing monitoring efforts and informed decision-making. (Relevance: 5)

d. monitoring frequency

Monitoring programs may not be conducted frequently enough to capture important changes or fluctuations in the monitored parameters, what can lead to gaps in data coverage, especially for rapidly changing or dynamic systems. Therefore, limited financial resources may restrict the frequency of monitoring activities, resulting in less frequent data collection, reducing the ability to detect short-term variations or trends. Availability of monitoring instruments or technologies may limit the frequency at which data can be collected and capture rapid changes in environmental conditions. Many monitoring programs conduct sampling at intervals that are too long to capture short-term variations and episodic events, can result in missed data on critical events that significantly impact coastal ecosystems and can lead to an incomplete understanding of the ecosystem's health and dynamics. Inconsistent monitoring schedules can create gaps in the data, making it difficult to identify trends and long-term changes. Regular and systematic monitoring is necessary to build a reliable dataset over time. (Relevance: 4).

e. stakeholder engagement limitation

If certain stakeholders are not adequately involved or consulted in the design, implementation, or decision-making processes of the monitoring program, their perspectives, needs, and local knowledge may be overlooked, what can lead to a lack of support and potential resistance to the program. Lack of inclusivity and fairness of stakeholder engagement, can lead to marginalize the voices and interests of others, what can undermining the legitimacy and credibility of the monitoring program. Without adequate resources (time, funding and expertise), it may be challenging to conduct public consultations, workshops, or outreach efforts to engage stakeholders and collect their input. Stakeholders may resist or be hesitant to engage with monitoring programs due to concerns about potential impacts on their interests, livelihoods, or regulatory compliance. Inadequate mechanisms for collecting feedback from stakeholders and incorporating their input into decision-making processes can weaken the accountability and transparency of the monitoring program. (Relevance: 3)

f. accessibility and availability of data

Limited funding and infrastructure can impact the accessibility and availability of data and restricted access to data and insufficient metadata leading to reducing data usability. At the core of effectiveness in environmental monitoring and conservation is the quality and availability of data. Standardization is essential for integrating data from multiple sources and ensuring its reliability and usability. To tackle the challenge of

inconsistent data quality, concerted efforts are needed to enhance and innovative data collection infrastructure. Providing easy access to data promotes transparency and fosters collaboration among stakeholders, enabling them to use the data for research, analysis, and decision-making. Monitoring programs must ensure the continuous availability of data to support ongoing monitoring efforts and facilitate timely responses to emerging issues or challenges.

An innovative and inclusive approach to overcoming data challenges is the integration of citizen science. By actively involving the public in data collection through user-friendly apps and community-driven initiatives, a vast network of observers can contribute valuable information. This participatory model not only enhances the quantity of available data but also promotes public engagement and awareness. (Relevance: 3)

g. data integration and interoperability

There may be challenges in integrating data from various monitoring programs and stakeholders, which may use different formats, structures, resolution, standards, and protocols, making it challenging to create a unified and comprehensive dataset. as well as in sharing data across institutions. Without standardized methodologies, protocols and data formats, combining datasets from different sources can result in inconsistencies. Effective data integration and interoperability require clear policies and governance frameworks that promote standardizing data formats, protocols, and metadata to facilitate data exchange and compatibility across different platforms and organizations. Investing in modern Interoperable monitoring systems is essential to enable collaboration and data sharing among stakeholders, promoting transparency, efficiency, and synergy in monitoring efforts. (Relevance: 4)

h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders

Stakeholders with technical expertise play a critical role in ensuring data quality and reliability and implementing quality assurance procedures, such as calibration checks, data validation, and quality control measures, to maintain data integrity and accuracy throughout the monitoring process. Therefore, limited technical expertise among stakeholders impacting the quality and effectiveness of monitoring efforts and data collection, analysis, and interpretation. Also, lack of knowledge of specialized equipment, sampling techniques, and measurement procedures, lead to the collection of low-quality and unreliable data. Stakeholders with technical expertise transfer knowledge and skills, empower local communities, and build institutional capacity to sustain monitoring efforts over the long term. They translate and interpreting complex monitoring information into actionable insights and policy recommendations to diverse audiences, facilitating evidence-based decision-making and stakeholder engagement. (Relevance: 3)

i. Funding

Funding and resource limitations may restrict the scope, scale, duration and frequency of environmental monitoring efforts or adoption and integration of advanced technologies and methodologies into monitoring programs, overall, what affecting quality and quantity of data collected. This often results in gaps in temporal and spatial coverage, particularly in resource-constrained regions or for specific environmental parameters. Allocation of necessary resources are essential for conducting field surveys, collecting data, operating monitoring equipment, and managing data storage and analysis. Adequate funding enables the implementation of quality assurance measures to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and integrity of monitoring data which contribute to the credibility and trustworthiness of the monitoring program. Long-term funding commitments are essential for ensures the continuity and longevity of monitoring programs over time, addressing emerging challenges and adapt to changing environmental conditions or management priorities. (Relevance: 5)

j. infrastructure and supporting services

Insufficient infrastructure may lead to a lack of access to necessary equipment and technology for data collection and analysis making monitoring efforts compromised, resulting in incomplete or inaccurate data. Challenges in logistics and transportation, such as inadequate transportation infrastructure or limited access to remote monitoring sites, can hamper fieldwork and data collection efforts. Inadequate supporting services for data management and analysis, such as insufficient data storage capacity, outdated software tools, or limited access to analytical expertise, can hinder the processing and interpretation of monitoring data

If available monitoring technology has limitations in detecting certain pollutants or measuring specific parameters accurately, it could result in incomplete or inaccurate data. For example, an insufficient number of monitoring stations can lead to incomplete spatial coverage and missing critical data from less monitored areas. Upgrading infrastructure is necessary to ensure reliable data collection. Limited financial resources can constrain the ability to establish and maintain necessary infrastructure, resulting in reduced frequency and quality of monitoring efforts. The lack of advanced and modern monitoring technologies can limit the ability to collect high-resolution and real-time data. Additionally, the lack of supporting services, such as regular maintenance, calibration, and technical support, can affect the performance and longevity of monitoring equipment. Reliable supporting services are essential to ensure the accuracy and reliability of collected data. (Relevance: 4)

k. other

Policy gaps (lack of comprehensive policies and regulations to support systematic and standardized environmental monitoring)- Policies must outline stringent guidelines for standardized data collection, storage, and usage, adopting collection protocols, secure storage systems, and access controls to prevent unauthorized use. Clear consent mechanisms should be established for data collection from public and private sources, with an emphasis on transparency regarding the purposes and potential impacts of data usage.

Indicator Selection: Successful monitoring programs depend on the careful choice of a limited number of representative indicators and on the collection of reliable data-

Social and Cultural Factors: Community resistance or lack of awareness about the importance of environmental monitoring can impede the implementation and success of monitoring programs. Cultural beliefs and practices may also influence the acceptance and cooperation of local populations.

16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?

a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)

Online survey and pools, social media platforms, existing platforms related with CS,

b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)

- Surveys and Questionnaires,

- public portals
- Public Reporting Portals: EPA, MONSTAT, Institute for Marine Biology, radio Kotor, BOKA NEWS portal...
- Environmental Monitoring Tools: using mobile devices for particle detection for analyzing the concentration of pollutants from ship exhaust systems, particularly during the cruising season.
- Survey Tools: distributing surveys for quick and easy gathering data from the different stakeholders.

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?

a. Public institutions

We will organize a meeting with all stakeholders, survey, interviews, mass and print media, etc.

b. Academia or groups of experts

We will organize a meeting with all stakeholders, survey, interviews, mass and print media, etc.

c. Private enterprises

We will organize a meeting with all stakeholders, survey, interviews, mass and print media, etc.

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

We will organize a meeting with all stakeholders, survey, interviews, mass and print media, etc.

e. Citizens

Survey, mass and print media, etc.

18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?

a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?

The data sources that will be used in CS are a legal obligation and are available on the official websites of the institutions.

Environmental data are sourced from the "*Information on the State of the Environment in Montenegro*" prepared by the Environmental Protection Agency, based on the annual monitoring program which is adopted by the Government of Montenegro.

The data on the research statistics of circular voyages of foreign ships and data on tourist arrivals and overnight stays, conducted by the Statistical Office of Montenegro based on the Law on Official Statistics and the Official Statistics System ('Official Gazette of Montenegro', No. 18/12 and 47/19).

Surveys and interviews with stakeholders, experts, policymakers, and community members can provide qualitative and quantitative data on various aspects of the case study, including social, economic, and environmental factors.

Academic research papers, journals, and other grey literature provide valuable insights, data, methodologies and can provide information into past conditions and changes in the study area.

b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?

PRO-COAST can provide additional data and information in areas such as:

- may offer comprehensive and localized data on various aspects of coastal management, including ecosystem health, habitats, coastal infrastructure, and community engagement, which could supplement existing data sources and provide a more holistic understanding of coastal dynamics. By synthesizing diverse datasets, PRO-COAST could identify trends and patterns that may not be apparent from individual sources alone and has the potential to complement existing data and fill gaps on the impact of cruise tourism on local ecosystem.

- could enhance existing knowledge and raise awareness about negative impact of cruise tourism and contribute valuable insights to inform decision-making and management strategies aimed at preserving and protecting coastal and marine ecosystems, helping to fill gaps in policy analysis and implementation.

- provide data on the socio-economic impacts of cruise tourism, including employment opportunities, income generation, and community development, which may enhance understanding in these areas.

- promoting stakeholders and local communities engagement and support through building partnerships to work towards common goals related to coastal management and tourism sustainability; establishing trust is essential for effective collaboration, engagement and commitment to project goals, as well communicating the value of project data ensures that stakeholders recognize the value of their involvement and contributions to the project.

19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?

[Prompt] Please bear in mind that even if there are datasets for a specific topic, CSs could complement them with more data density for the pilot area (e.g., currently unreached areas).

[Recommendation] Establish dialogue among the rest of PRO-COAST partners to explore how to access, maintain or even exploit new data sources.

Air quality data during peak cruise seasons bearing in mind fact that missions from cruise ships including: sulfur oxides (SOx), nitrogen oxides (NOx), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and particulate matter (PM).

Solid Waste Management: data on waste management practices (volume and type of waste produced by cruise ships) both on ships and in port facilities.

Socio-Economic Data: Information on human activities, coastal communities, changes in livelihoods, cultural practices, and social cohesion. Surveys, interviews, and participatory approaches will be employed to gather socio-economic data and understand the cruise dimensions of coastal issues and information on the effectiveness of existing regulations and management measures in mitigating the negative impacts of cruise tourism on the environment. Survey data on economic benefits versus environmental costs to local communities, including job creation, infrastructure strain, and cost of environmental mitigation and data on local residents' perceptions of cruise tourism and its impact on their quality of life and environment.

Data on increased tourism pressure on natural and cultural sites: visitor numbers and activities at natural sites frequented by cruise tourists, such as beaches, parks, and conservation areas.

Analysis of coastal habitat loss or alteration due to port development and infrastructure.

Comparative analysis of climate change contribution from cruise tourism versus other forms of tourism and transportation (considering their fuel use and operational practices).

Health impact data: data on health outcomes related to air and water quality in port cities.

Policy and regulation compliance: information on the enforcement and effectiveness of existing environmental and tourism regulations specific to cruise ships.

Overall, CS can provide a comprehensive assessment of the environmental impacts of cruise tourism, identifying areas that require more stringent regulation or improved management sustainable practices and provide that currently understudied aspects are adequately covered, offering a robust foundation for policy recommendations in develop more effective strategies for sustainable tourism management and future research.

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

Analysing the identified datasets will involves several steps: data processing, visualization, statistical analysis, and interpretation.

Possible thematic exploration:

1. Environmental Impact Analysis

In collaboration with the Maritime Faculty conduct measurement the concentration of air pollutants in areas affected by cruise ship operations and assess the impact of these emissions on local air quality and public health.

Potential KPIs-

- Number of Days Exceeding Air Quality Standards: Frequency of days when air quality is below acceptable standards.

2. Regulatory Compliance and Effectiveness

- Conduct evaluations and assessments of the effectiveness of environmental policies and regulations.
- Track the number, effectiveness and frequency of environmental inspections conducted on cruise ships.

Potential KPIs:

- Number and proportion coverage of Inspections conducted annually.
- Number of the penalties issued and fines imposed for regulatory non-compliance.
- Evaluation of the effectiveness of existing policies, strategic plans and regulations on reduction environmental impacts including perceptions of policy effectiveness among stakeholders.

3. Tourism Impact Assessment

- Analyse and assess the overall economic impact of cruise tourism on local economies (if possible, assess revenue generated from cruise tourism versus the environmental costs incurred).
- Assess the impact of cruise tourism on local infrastructure, including ports, roads, and waste management systems.

Potential KPIs:

- Number and frequency of tourist from cruise ships on annual level.
- Measures degree of stress on local infrastructure, ports, roads and waste management system.
- Economic impact assessment of cruise tourism on local businesses and employment (for example, number of seasonal workers).

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

The environmental data to be used in the CS will be sourced from the national annual Environmental Monitoring Program, which is aligned with European legislative standards and the international conventions and agreements to which Montenegro is a signatory.

<https://epa.org.me/informacije-o-stanju-zivotne-sredine/>

Regarding data on tourist visits and the number of cruise ships, data from the Montenegro Statistical Office will be used based on the Law on Official Statistics and the System of Official Statistics ("Official Gazette of Montenegro", Nos. 18/12 and 47/19).

[https://www.monstat.org/userfiles/file/turizam/kruzna%20putovanja/Metodologija%20\(TU-19\).pdf](https://www.monstat.org/userfiles/file/turizam/kruzna%20putovanja/Metodologija%20(TU-19).pdf)

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives? If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

a. Topic of the initiative

We were partners on the ADRIION project [BLUEAIR](#) set with a goal to support the development of a regional innovation system for the Adriatic-Ionian area. This objective was reached by the involvement of the quadruple helix actors in the definition of a common strategic vision by means of enabling tools, capacity building initiatives and effective EDP practices and instruments. Supported by scientific experts and technical documentation, BLUEAIR offers to quadruple helix actors a view on the future scenarios of the Blue Growth sectors enabling them to take advantage of the sector transnational opportunities. 2 seas, many untapped market opportunities in Blue Growth, different coastal and inland territories involved moving toward one single approach: the BLUEAIR Macro-Regional S3 on Blue Growth!

b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)

Private sector representatives, public institution, NGOs

c. Communication channels

Round tables, survey, documents, media, press releases, CEM web page, web page of the BLUEAIR project, etc.

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

According to Article 72 of the Law on Environmental Protection, state administration bodies, administrative bodies, and local government bodies responsible for environmental protection are obliged to timely inform the public and interested parties about decision-making processes related to environmental issues concerning:

1. Strategic environmental impact assessments of plans and programs;
2. Environmental impact assessments;
3. The process of issuing permits for integrated pollution prevention and control through the approval of the operation of new or existing facilities;
4. Strategies, plans, programs, and other documents in the field of environmental protection;
5. Other issues in the field of environmental protection in accordance with special regulations.

Furthermore, Montenegro is a member of the Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matter (Arhus Convention).

The aim of the Aarhus Convention is to strengthen the role of citizens and civil society organizations in

environmental matters. It is founded on the principles of participatory democracy. The Aarhus Convention defines a range of rights for individuals and civil society organizations concerning the environment. The signatory parties are required to ensure, through legislation, that public authorities at the national, regional, or local level contribute to the realization of these rights. The Aarhus Convention provides:

- Access to Environmental Information: The right of citizens to access environmental information held by public authorities.
- Public Participation in Environmental Decision-Making: The right of citizens to participate in the preparation of plans, programs, policies, and legislation that may affect the environment.
- Legal Protection: The right of citizens to seek legal redress if their rights related to access to information or public participation are violated.

The Society of Friends of Boka Heritage organized public forums, supported by the Municipality of Kotor, with the aim of raising awareness about the urgent and comprehensive need to protect and stop the devastation of the universal values of the Kotor-Risan Bay.

The Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality of the University of Montenegro organized a public forum today titled "Cruising and Cultural Tourism in Montenegro's Tourism Offer - Challenges and Perspectives." During the event, participants discussed the economic, social, and environmental sustainability of these industries, the international positioning of Kotor as a cruising and cultural tourism destination, and contemporary challenges and digital innovations in this sector.

The Secretariat for the Protection of Natural and Cultural Heritage of the Municipality of Kotor organized citizen forums titled "Environmental Issues in the Local Community" as part of the activities for developing the content of the Draft Local Environmental Protection Plan for the Municipality of Kotor (2019 – 2023).

Local debates and prominent issues connected to the impact of cruise tourism on the environment may include:

Environmental Degradation: Concerns about the degradation of coastal and marine ecosystems, including damage to coral reefs, pollution from cruise ship discharges, and disturbance to marine wildlife habitats.

Infrastructure Development: Debates around the construction of cruise ship terminals and related infrastructure, which may lead to habitat destruction, coastal erosion, and increased pressure on local resources.

Cultural Heritage Preservation: Discussions on preserving cultural heritage sites and traditional ways of life in the face of increased tourism, including the potential loss of authenticity and identity in UNESCO sites.

Economic Dependency: Considerations regarding the reliance of local economies on cruise tourism revenue, balancing economic benefits with the long-term sustainability of natural and cultural resources.

Community Engagement and Participation: Efforts to involve local communities in decision-making processes related to impact of cruise tourism on environment, ensuring that their voices are heard and their concerns addressed.

To conciliate the parties involved, it's crucial to engage various stakeholders, including administrations, the private sector, and local communities through inclusive dialogue, collaborative decision-making processes, and transparent communication channels. Stakeholders should be encouraged to actively participate in discussions, share their perspectives, and work towards mutually beneficial solutions. Communication should be focused on mediating between conflicting interests rather than avoiding conflicts or tensions. It's essential to acknowledge and address the concerns of all parties involved, fostering understanding and empathy among stakeholders. Local debates can be leveraged to inform the development of an engagement strategy tailored to each stakeholder type. By understanding the diverse interests and priorities of different stakeholders, it's possible to create a more

inclusive and effective approach to managing the impact of cruise tourism on the environment

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

Extreme Citizen Science (ExCiteS) is a situated, bottom-up practice that considers local needs, traditions and culture. ECS involves empowering local communities to identify and define the negative impacts of cruise tourism on the coastal environment. Through participatory workshops, community meetings, or online platforms, residents can share their observations, concerns, and experiences related to pollution, habitat destruction, or other environmental issues caused by cruise tourism.

Citizens will actively participate in data collection efforts to gather information about the impacts of cruise tourism on the coastal environment through conducting surveys to assess awareness, or using mobile apps to report environmental incidents.

During workshop ECS facilitates collaborative analysis between community members and scientists. Local residents can contribute their local knowledge and observations, while experts provide guidance on data interpretation and analysis techniques. Together, they can identify trends, patterns, and hotspots of environmental degradation associated with cruise tourism.

Armed with data and insights, local communities can advocate for policy changes, raise awareness among policymakers and the public, and implement grassroots initiatives to address the negative impacts of cruise tourism. This may include lobbying for stricter regulations on cruise ship emissions, or promoting sustainable tourism practices.

ECS also focuses on building the capacity of local communities to engage in ongoing monitoring and management of the coastal environment. Training workshops, educational programs, and citizen science networks can empower residents with the skills and resources needed to continue monitoring and addressing environmental issues in the long term.

ECS encourages collaboration and networking between different stakeholders, including residents, scientists, government agencies, NGOs, and industry representatives. By fostering partnerships and knowledge sharing, ECS facilitates collective action towards mitigating the negative impacts of cruise tourism on the coastal environment.

Overall, the use of Extreme Citizen Science for addressing the negative impact of cruise tourism on the coastal environment empowers local communities to become active participants in research, monitoring, advocacy, and management efforts, leading to more sustainable and resilient coastal communities.

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

Local radio stations broadcast call-in shows, interviews, and news bulletins covering local topics. Radio is an accessible medium for listeners to voice their opinions, ask questions, and engage in real-time conversations with hosts and other listeners.

Local newspapers publish articles, opinion pieces, and letters to the editor addressing local concerns and highlighting community viewpoints. These print publications serve as forums for informed commentary and public discourse.

Social media: Platforms like Facebook and Instagram are increasingly popular venues for sharing news, opinions, and discussions about local issues. Social media allows users to connect with a wider audience, participate in online debates, and organize grassroots movements or advocacy campaigns.

The official website of the Chamber of Economy of Montenegro <https://komora.me/>

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

Representatives from local communities, NGO environmental organizations, tourism industry stakeholders, government agencies, and academic institutions may all have different perspectives and interests regarding the negative impact of cruise tourism on the coastal environment.

By including stakeholders from different backgrounds and interests in the research process, will be ensure that diverse viewpoints are considered, and potential conflicts are addressed through constructive dialogue.

Strategies to reconcile and facilitate dialogue between different discourses may include:

1. Establishing inclusive platforms for discussion: Organize workshops, roundtable discussions, or community meetings where stakeholders can come together to share their perspectives, concerns, and ideas in a respectful and collaborative environment.
2. Facilitating mutual understanding: Provide opportunities for stakeholders to learn from each other's experiences and expertise. This could involve expert presentations, site visits, or sharing of case studies that highlight successful examples of collaboration and conflict resolution.
3. Identifying common goals and interests: Encourage stakeholders to identify shared objectives and areas of mutual interest, such as preserving coastal ecosystems, promoting sustainable tourism, or supporting local economies. Focusing on common ground can help build trust and consensus among diverse stakeholders.
4. Mediation and conflict resolution: In cases where disagreements arise, consider engaging a neutral mediator or facilitator to help parties explore solutions and reach compromises. Mediation can help de-escalate tensions and foster constructive dialogue towards finding mutually acceptable outcomes.
5. Transparent communication and decision-making: Ensure that information about the CS project, including its goals, methodologies, and findings, is communicated transparently to all stakeholders. Involve stakeholders in decision-making processes wherever possible, and provide opportunities for feedback and input throughout the project lifecycle.

By actively involving diverse stakeholders in the CS project and promoting dialogue and collaboration, you can harness the collective wisdom and resources of the community to address the negative impact of cruise tourism

on the coastal environment effectively.

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

Societal norms and stereotypes may perpetuate the idea that certain groups, such as children or older adults, do not have valuable contributions to make in public discussions, leading to their exclusion. Public debates may be dominated by certain demographics or interest groups, making it difficult for under-represented groups to have their voices heard.

Some groups, such as individuals with disabilities or those from minority ethnic backgrounds, may face communication (language) barriers, discrimination, or lack of representation, that hinder their participation in public debates.

Older people may have valuable insights and experiences to contribute to discussions about impact of cruise tourism on the environment, but they may be under-represented in public debates due to ageism or assumptions about their interests.

Children and youth (future generation), who will inherit the long-term consequences of decisions made about cruise tourism and environmental management, are often excluded from public debates because do not have a direct voice due to their age and societal norms. despite being deeply impacted by them.

Socioeconomically disadvantaged residents living in coastal areas may face disproportionate impacts from cruise tourism, such as increased living costs, displacement, or loss of access to natural resources. These communities may be less likely to participate in public debates due to barriers such as lack of education, time constraints, or limited access to information and resources.

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

Boka News ,as local community multimedia portal founded by NGO Boka, provide platforms for voices and perspectives that may be underrepresented or marginalized in mainstream media as well offer alternative narratives, analysis, and coverage of hot-button issues in Boka Kotor Bay. The primary goal of the media is to inform citizens about the Bay of Kotor, its values, authenticity, architecture, culture, tourist potentials, environmental protection, and development in harmony with nature. Additionally, the NGO Boka organizes seminars, round tables, scientific conferences, and exhibitions to promote the fundamental goals of sustainable development of the Bay of Kotor in harmony with nature.

<https://bokanews.me/>

<https://www.bokanews.me/live/>

<https://www.facebook.com/bokanews/>

<https://www.youtube.com/BokaNewsOnline>

29. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

The Bay of Boka Kotorska is a semi-enclosed bay that forms a distinct system from the Adriatic coast and has unique orographical, climatic, hydrogeological, and environmental characteristics. The Bay is 28 km long and 7 km wide in the largest point, with a coastline of 107 km and a total water area of 87 km². It is divided into three subsystems: the bay of Herceg-Novi, the Bay of Tivat and the bay of Kotor and Risan. Due to its peculiar shape and origin, it is sometimes defined as the southernmost fjord of Europe. The origin of the bay is related to intensive tectonics and karstification processes. The karstic geomorphological structure of the bay with high flow of underground freshwater into the basin created typical conditions that determine distinctive biotic and abiotic factors of the bay.

30 Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

Tourism is the main driver of the social and economic development in Montenegro as well as in Boka Kotorska bay area, justifying increasingly the role of the strategic branch of industry year by year. Its share in GDP is continuously growing, as is the case with other indicators - the number of tourists, overnight stays and the income of this sector. The high season in Montenegro traditionally lasts from May to October.

In Montenegro, in 2023, tourists realised 2 613 306 arrivals and 16 389 279 overnights. Of the total number of overnights, 96.3% were realized by foreign tourists, and 3.7% of overnights were realized by domestic tourists. Concerning the structure of overnights of foreign tourists, in 2023, the most of them were realized by tourists from: Russian Federation (23.6%); Serbia (21.5%); Bosnia and Herzegovina (8.5%); Germany (4.9%); Ukraine (4.1%); Kosovo (3.6%); and Turkey (2.9%). Tourists from other countries were realised 31.0% overnights.

When it comes to the municipalities of Boka Kotorska, they are one of the top tourism destinations in Montenegro in arrivals and overnights. According to the data from the National statistical office, municipality of Herceg Novi is second highest in arrivals (14,9%) while municipality of Kotor makes 9,1% and municipality of Tivat makes 6,2% of total arrivals. When it comes to overnights, municipality of Herceg Novi is still second highest in overnights (18,5%) while municipality of Kotor makes 7,9% and municipality of Tivat makes 8,0 % of total overnights.

Approximately 70% to 80% of total arrivals and overnight stays in the municipality of Boka Kotorska are achieved in the high season between May and October, indicating a strong reliance on tourism during these months. This concentration of tourist activity highlights the region's appeal as a summer destination and underscores the importance of seasonal factors in shaping the local economy and hospitality industry.

. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

Determining the ideal number of tourists for sustainability in a given area involves considering various factors such as the environmental carrying capacity, port capacity and Infrastructure, seasonal variation in the number of tourists, the local community's capacity to accommodate tourists without negatively affecting residents' quality of life as well as economic benefits and costs.

Without detailed data and studies, it is difficult to provide an exact number of optimal cruise ships for the Bay of Kotor and tourists that should be ideal for sustainability of this area.

30. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

In Kotor, there are more active than employed residents. The working-age population constitutes 39.3%, of which 33.2% are employed. Women make up 44.8% of the total number of employed individuals.

Considering there are no final data from census from 2023, according to the previous official census data from 2011, the highest percentage of municipality residents from Kotor (out of the total number of employed persons) are employed in the following sectors: wholesale and retail trade (20.73%), health and social work (8.53%), transport, storage, and communication (20.06%), public administration and social security (7.42%), education (6.93%), accommodation and food services (7.70%), manufacturing industry (4.32%), water supply, waste water management, process control, waste disposal, and similar activities (3.86%), production of electricity, gas, and water (1.02%), real estate activities (0.50%), etc.

ANNEX V QUESTIONNAIRE - STREEDAGH BEACH, IRELAND

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

5- regional

b. Academia or groups of experts

5

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

2

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

4

e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)

5 (locals and tourists)

2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

- Local Biodiversity Action Plan 2022-2027
- Climate Action Plan 2022-2027
- Sligo CC, Climate Adaptation Strategy

0. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify

them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:

b. Climate change

4

b. Biodiversity

5

c. Urban and rural planning

4

d. Mobility

3

e. Tourism

4

f. Participatory research

3

g. Agriculture

4

h. Others

3. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

- Sligo County Council (SCC)- 5
- Elected council officials, City/Public offices- 5
- National Parks & Wildlife Service (NPWS)- 4
- Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)- 4
- Climate Action Regional Office – CARO- 3

- Office of Public Works (OPW)- 3
- Department of Environmental Climate and Communications- 3

4. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

SCORE project

CleanCoast (NGO)

Local businesses (like horse riding and shops-Cafe in Grange)

Farmers (most land there is farmland which is private)

5. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?

a. Agenda setting

ATU

b. Policy formulation

ATU

c. Decision making

ATU

d. Policy implementation

Sligo County Council (SCC)

e. Policy evaluation

ATU

6. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?

Providing valuable insights into human behavior and decision-making processes related to biodiversity

Enhancing climate literacy and promoting sustainable behaviors

Identifying barriers to sand dune restoration and proposing solutions

7. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation?

Special Area of Conservation (SAC)

8. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

Coastal dunes and sandy shores and mesic grasslands- 3km long sandy beach

b. Habitats: Key habitats

[1140] Tidal Mudflats and Sandflats

[1220] Perennial Vegetation of Stony Banks

[1330] Atlantic Salt Meadows

[1410] Mediterranean Salt Meadows

[2120] Marram Dunes (White Dunes)

[2130] Fixed Dunes (Grey Dunes)

[1014] Narrow-mouthed Whorl Snail (*Vertigo angustior*)

** Numbers in brackets are Natura 2000 codes

c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats

2130: Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation ("Grey dunes")

2190: Humid dune slacks

d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats

One: Fixed Dunes (Grey Dunes)

e. Fauna: Key fauna species

- Common Seal (*Phoca vitulina*): Often seen resting on the shore or swimming in the waters.
- Otter (*Lutra lutra*): Frequently observed in the coastal waters and river mouths.

- Various bird species: Such as the Ringed Plover (*Charadrius hiaticula*) and the Sanderling (*Calidris alba*), especially during migration periods.
- Dolphins: Occasionally spotted offshore.
- Sandhoppers (*Talitridae* family): Small crustaceans that are common in the sand dunes and beach areas.

f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC

One: the common seal (*Phoca vitulina*)

g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species

Streedagh Beach is home to approximately 40 species of wild birds. These include both resident and migratory species, contributing to the area's rich avian biodiversity.

h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC

Target species of wild birds at Streedagh Beach, based on Directive 2009/147/EC (the Birds Directive), include:

- Ringed Plover (*Charadrius hiaticula*)
- Sanderling (*Calidris alba*)
- Redshank (*Tringa totanus*)
- Dunlin (*Calidris alpina*)
- Oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*)
- Curlew (*Numenius arquata*)
- Turnstone (*Arenaria interpres*)
- Golden Plover (*Pluvialis apricaria*)

9. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.

The regional Grange biodiversity action plan was implemented (2017-2021), and the evaluation report was also provided by them. Based on the results, they published the new biodiversity action (2022-2027) and the actions related to Streedagh beach is as follow:

“Organise regular clean-ups/litter picking in collaboration with other local Tidy Towns groups Raise awareness of aquatic/marine habitats and biodiversity, and negative effects of waste such as microplastics in the marine environment”.

10. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Farming

Tourism and recreational activities
Grazing

11. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Lack of resources/funding, limited knowledge of climate change, limited data availability, inefficient recording of data, limited citizen involvement, climate-vulnerable groups, inefficient transport and agricultural practices, ongoing election.

12. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Sea Level Rise (climate change impacts)
Extreme weather and flooding
Sand dune erosion
salt marsh degradation

13. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).

a. Yes, no?

Water quality monitoring
Ambient Air Monitoring
Sea level rise
The natural habitat types and animal and plant species

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

Special area of conservation

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?

Water quality monitoring (SCC)
Ambient Air Monitoring (EPA)
Sea level rise (SCORE project)
The natural habitat types and animal and plant species (NWPS- last report: 2015)

d. How long is it being implemented?
Sea level rise (One year) The natural habitat types and animal and plant species (From 2005)
e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?
Water quality: E coli Sea level rise; shoreline (remote sensing) The natural habitat types and animal and plant species (species/ habitats variables)

14. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
a. spatial coverage
4
b. temporal coverage
4
c. data quality and resolution
5
d. monitoring frequency
4
e. stakeholder engagement limitation
3
f. accessibility and availability of data
4
g. data integration and interoperability

4
h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders
2
i. funding
4
j. infrastructure and supporting services
4
k. other

15. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?
a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Email - Microsoft Teams - Zoom - MS forms - LinkedIn
b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)
<p>Citizen science apps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SCORE Project: Co-creation toolkit: https://www.ihs.nl/en/advisory-training-and-research/tools-and-toolkits/co-create-your-city-toolkit - SCORE Community Geosurveys: https://geosurveys.score-eu-project.eu/ <p>Publicly accessible reporting portals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://score-eu-project.eu/scientific-publications/ - The National Biodiversity Data & publications portal - Government publications portal: https://www.gov.ie/en/publications/

16. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics

addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?

a. Public institutions

- Face to face
- Telephone call
- email
- PRO-COAST website

b. Academia or groups of experts

- Face to face
- Telephone call
- Email
- LinkedIn, X
- PRO-COAST website

c. Private enterprises

- Face to face
- Telephone call
- Email
- PRO-COAST website

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

- Face to face
- Telephone call
- email
- PRO-COAST website
- WhatsApp

e. Citizens

- Face to face
- Telephone call, SMS
- PRO-COAST website
- Social media (Facebook, Instagram, X)
- WhatsApp
- Radio and TV and related Podcasts / YouTube videos

17. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?

Community and stakeholder surveys

- Questionnaires
- Workshops
- Focussed Group Discussions
- Interviews

Public information/data portals:

- Government publications portal: <https://www.gov.ie/en/publications/>
- Sligo County Council Environment portal: <https://www.sligococo.ie/Environment/>
- National Parks & Wildlife Service data & publications portal: <https://www.npws.ie/maps-and-data;>
<https://www.npws.ie/publications>
- The National Biodiversity Data Centre: <https://biodiversityireland.ie/>
- Central Statistics Office Statistics: <https://data.cso.ie/>
- IRELAND'S OPEN DATA PORTAL: <https://data.gov.ie/>

Research projects portals:

- <https://score-eu-project.eu/scientific-publications/>:

Remote Sensing data:

- Satellite imagery
- drone

Citizen Science

Ireland's Citizen Science Portal

a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?

The data sources provide public open data and information for analysis and environmental policy making purposes.

b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?

There are potential data gaps such as current cloud free high resolution satellite data. Use of UAVs to collect such data can be considered.

18. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?

Current CS_Streedagh vegetation status, habitat degradation and biodiversity status

19. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

Statistical analysis: MS excel, SPSS, R, Python

Geospatial analysis: ArcGIS Pro, QGIS, Google earth Engine

20. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

Data structure: CSV, Shapefile, Geolson

Metadata: ISO 19115 and ISO-19139 for Geographic information

21. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives?
If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

a. Topic of the initiative

Our team is part of ongoing SCORE project which has been engaging local communities and stakeholders in implementing Ecosystem-based Adaptations including dune restoration at Streedagh beach.

b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)

Communities involved are both the youth and the elderly local members.

c. Communication channels

Telephone calls, virtual meetings through Ms teams or zoom calls, workshops and beach events meetings.

22. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

Prominent issues:

- Marram grass loss due to uncoordinated car parking by the visiting tourists.
- Visitors driving on and destroying the salt marshes.
- Visitors destroying dunes which are already facing coastal erosion challenges.
- Camping and fires being lit by visiting tourist which destroy sensitive habitat vegetation and animal species.

- Pollution and littering of the beach by the visitors.
- Lack of restraining fencing at the beach to guard against undesignated parking.
- Lack of differentiated accessibility options to the main beach accommodating the parents with children, the elderly and disabled persons needing wheelchair routes.
- Injuring, killing or taking wildlife

Local Debates:

- Municipal council debate on necessity for current environmental survey of the dunes to ascertain the level of damage that has been done over the past 20 years.

Municipal council debate on provision of access to the main beach from the car parks responsive to the elderly and disabled.

23. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

We are applying the recommended Extreme Citizen Science approach

24. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

[Recommendation] Use/leverage the different media channels identified & tailor call for participation to different audiences' issues.

Radio/TV/ Podcasts

Newspapers:

- The independent: <https://www.independent.ie/>
- Sligo Weekender: <https://www.pressreader.com/>

25. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

- Clean Coasts: interested in environment conservation at Streedagh beach.
- Sligo City Council: interested in a provision of attractive beach services to the locals and visitors targeting economic returns.
- National Parks and Wildlife Services: interested in biodiversity conservation at Streedagh beach.
- The National Tourism Development Authority: interested in domestic and international tourism including at Streedagh beach.
- Councillors: Sligo council representatives and have political and community interest.
- Business owners: have business sustainability interest at Streedagh beach.
- Landowners: concerned about their lands being cut-off from the mainland hence hindering access.

- Local farmers: interested in their sheep grazing peacefully and preservation of the grazing areas around at Streedagh beach.
- The Irish Cattle and Sheep Farmers Association: interested in the national low-income sheep farmers welfare including the farmers around at Streedagh beach

Researchers: have interest in the scientific research findings

26. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

- The local residents (especially the youth 20-35 away studying or working) whose livelihoods and ecosystem are being affected.
- The tourists who are the major perpetrators of destruction of Streedagh biodiversity and ecosystem.

27. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

No public protests have been reported at CS_streedagh

28. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

- Local residents near Streedagh beach stay at a nearby Grange community township with a population of 569 people by 2022 census.
- Aggregation by gender: Males 250; Females 319
- Aggregation by age group: 0-17 years 174; 18-64 years 332; 65+ years 63

29. Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

At this level, there is no data.

Sligo received 186,000 international tourists and 263,000 domestic tourists according to latest available data of 2015^[1]. Streedagh point is one of major leading tourist attraction and the closest to Sligo, town. In a study of streedagh vistors by Fáilte Ireland/CAAS in 2022 (unpublished) on 22nd of July 2022, 171 visitors were counted.

^[1] <https://www.sligococo.ie/tourism/CountySligoTourismStrategy2018-2023/sts2018.pdf>

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

No data

30. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

- Businesses (including shops, restaurants, horse riding, sheepdog demonstration, staycation accommodations)
- Sheep farming

ANNEX VI QUESTIONNAIRE -

ARNE PARISH, UNITED KINGDOM

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

Arne Parish Council (local) (consulted)

Natural England (National) (to be consulted)

b. Academia or groups of experts

Poole Harbour Advisory Group on Squirrels (national) (consulted)

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

Rempstone Estate (consulted)

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

British Association for Shooting and Conservation (consulted)

Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust (consulted)

Royal Horticultural Society (to be consulted)

Dorset Wildlife Trust (to be consulted)

National Trust (to be consulted)

e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)

Mrs Shelley Cranshaw (local citizen) (consulted)

Colonel Johnny O'Brien (local citizen) (consulted)

Mr Julian Andersson (local citizen) (consulted)

2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Red Squirrel National Biodiversity Action Plan - 3

3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the COS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:

[Recommendation] To take into account the identified policies for the CS activities and outputs. How the CSs could foster policies' implementation? Identify the objectives or indicators (within the policy) to which the CSs will/could favour. Extract any useful guidelines or best practices to perform the CS activities.

a. Climate change

Public awareness of need for carbon sequestration to reduce climate change (3)

b. Biodiversity

Public awareness of alien species importance for climate change (3)

c. Urban and rural planning

Planning of woodlands (1)

d. Mobility

e. Tourism

Potentially beneficial if CS planning implemented successfully (3)

f. Participatory research

High engagement with local public planned (5)

g. Agriculture (forestry)

Beneficial for growth of woodland (2)

h. Others

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Parish Council (LAU5) for consultation of local people (3)
Licence for activities needed from Natural England, a government agency (5)

5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Landowner for initiation site is essential (5)
Practical support of Wildlife management NGOS is essential (5)
NGOs too may lobby Natural England for or against or encourage members for or against (4)
Local citizens, through consultation, will influence licencing by Natural England (2)

6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner (CS initiator)?

a. Agenda setting

Chairman, who consults all 3 involved

b. Policy formulation

Chairman, who consults all 3 involved

c. Decision making

Chairman, who consults all 3 involved

d. Policy implementation

All

e. Policy evaluation

Chairman, who consults all 3 involved

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in

future strategies?

If the CS cannot be implemented due to public opinion and/or failure to achieve licencing, the main benefit will be the decision support software developed for citizen conservation.

Environmental dimension

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation ?

Partly heathland under Bern Convention, partly Ramsar wetland, partly local nature reserve.

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

Heathland, farmland, river estuary, coastal marshland and mudflats

b. Habitats: Key habitats

Heathland, estuary, saltmarsh and mudflats

c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats

1110, 1130, 1140, 1150, 1160, 1320, 2310, 4010, 4020, 4030, 6410, 6510, 9190, 91D0 = 14

d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats

Under what definition?

e. Fauna: Key fauna species

Under what definition?

f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC

Within 90 minutes?

g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species

Under what definition? Within 90 minutes??

h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC

Target for what?

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.

Yes. See CS_Template

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Nature conservation, tourism, grazing, fishing, hunting

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Long-term: increasing flooding and sea-level change (4)

Nitrification of water from human population (including tourism) and agriculture (4)

Conflict of nature conservation and other uses, notably government pressure for housing (3)

High traffic loading due to tourism (3)

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Climate change (5), pollution (4), invasive species (3)

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).

a. Yes, no?

Yes

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

Extensive monitoring of species and habitats

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?
Natural England, Environment Agency (all under Dept for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs)
d. How long is it being implemented?
Long-term
e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?
All

15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
a. spatial coverage
b. temporal coverage
c. data quality and resolution
d. monitoring frequency
e. stakeholder engagement limitation
f. accessibility and availability of data
g. data integration and interoperability

h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders
i. funding
j. infrastructure and supporting services
k. other

Technological dimension

16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?
a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)
The local work will be underpinned by a content/forum node of the System for Community Liaison (https://sycl.net).
b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)
Participatory engagement will be through a series of apps for Reciprocal Environmental Decision Support (REDS), initially for gardens then wider areas.

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?
a. Public institutions
Email
b. Academia or groups of experts
Email, web-sites, face-to-face, LinkedIn
c. Private enterprises

Email, web-sites, face-to-face, LinkedIn
d. NGOs or other third sector groups
Email, web-sites, face-to-face, LinkedIn
e. Citizens
Email, web-sites, face-to-face, LinkedIn, Mass-media

18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?
Mapping of species and habitats in the REDS mapper and REDS App
a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?
To be open-source and open data
b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?
Through citizen participation, mapping of habitats and species in greater detail than is currently available

19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?
Through citizen participation, mapping of habitats and species in greater detail than is currently available

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.
RANGES for animal location data; REDS for modelling; survey packages; statistical packages.

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?
Those used in the UKCEH Biological Records and by National Biodiversity Gateway, plus the most globally applied standards.

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives? If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

a. Topic of the initiative

1. FP6 GEMCONBIO: Governance & Ecosystem Management for Conservation of Biodiversity
2. FP7 TESS: Transactional Environmental Support System

b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)

1. GEMCONBIO collected data on 26 local conservation studies and 6 European activity types
2. TESS had 9 local cases with citizen participation (of whole community by survey in Arne)

c. Communication channels

1. By email, telephone, questionnaires
2. By email, local talks, Excel questionnaires, tele/online survey & final multilingual website

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

Issue 1. The imposition of top-down conservation policy on un-consulted local communities.

Issue 2. Poor understanding of the serious damage that can be done by attractive introduced alien species for efforts to reduce climate change by carbon sequestration.

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

The Bristol Approach and Extreme Citizen Science as advised by WP6.

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

Issue 1. Local papers, social media, Parish website & meetings.

Issue 2. National papers, TV & radio, local papers, social media

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

Landowners, including gardening interests (most are interested in conservation)

Local conservation enthusiasts, including hunters, fishers, gatherers, watchers

National-level NGOs and institutions which fail to consult local people

Newly settled citizens with urban backgrounds

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

Due to influx of new settlement during the last 50 years, rural families of long-standing with more traditional countryside occupations are now a resentful minority, including older folk but also their children who are priced out of local homes (also by holiday-home owners).

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

Most debate is on social media or local newspapers. Pre-emptive posting is planned of information on serious damage that can be done by introduced alien species (e.g. to other wildlife & efforts to reduce climate change by carbon sequestration).

29. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

1,370 inhabitants in 27 km² of Arne Parish

30. Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

Ca 150,000 visit Arne nature reserves and maybe 250,000 pass annually through to coast at Swanage,

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

Unknown but depends on whether they use sustainable transport and accommodation.

31. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

Retirement, tourism, other service industries, clay-mining, conservation work and farming

ANNEX VII QUESTIONNAIRE -

BERGEN, NORWAY

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

Directorate of fisheries (national), Coastguard (military national – local)

b. Academia or groups of experts

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

Commercial fishers, funders, fishing equipment vendors

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

Nmf (Green warriors of Norway), Vuvi AS, Skjærgårdsservice, diving groups

e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)

Recreational fishers

2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

There is no explicit mention of ghost fishing in policy documents except in relation to National Parks, and the area we are researching is not in a national park.

However, we have identified the following practices which address the problem.

So, we cannot rate the relevance of a policy that does not exist, but we can rate the relevance of the practices to addressing the problem. We rate these as 2/5, because while they enable the monitoring and collection of discarded equipment, but they do not promote reporting of losses and they cover a limited

area annually.

Even within the national parks, which are more closely monitored, they say the rate of clear up is nowhere near matching the rate of loss of equipment.

The relevant practices outside the National Parks are these: the directorate of Fisheries does an annual survey, and the Coast Guard patrols regularly.

The directorate of Fisheries has a reporting tool for recreational fishers and another tool for commercial fishers. They have the powers to charge fishers, both kinds, for retrieval costs of equipment lost through neglect, but they point out that this conflicts with high reporting rates. So, we infer these powers are not much used.

CSs could improve the effectiveness of these practices by:

Visibility could be used to increase awareness of reporting hotline.

Accountability is supported by identifying retrieved equipment, so increasing visibility of this will improve motivation to report.

3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:

a. Climate change

Increases storm probability which increases chances of loss of equipment through accidents. 2/5

b. Biodiversity

Impacted by loss of equipment. So, central to the CS 5/5.

c. Urban and rural planning

As described at 2, coastal management action could be increased – too little to match the scale of the problem. 4/5

d. Mobility

Increased affluence enables more people to fish for sport, which impacts loss of equipment. 2/5

e. Tourism

Small contributor to leisure fishing. 1/5
f. Participatory research
The Green Warriors of Norway initiative has potential to improve quality of data on where the problem is and the practices which produce it. 3/5
g. Agriculture
N/A
h. Others
None

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
The Directorate of Fisheries and the Coast Guard both have competence within this area, although they are national/military. 3/5 4/5.

5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
See Q 1 for stakeholders. This is an undeveloped area of policy, so none are currently involved in lobbying the Directorate of Fisheries, to our knowledge.

6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?
a. Agenda setting
We don't yet have information on policy making activities within Green Warriors of Norway, but we will ask them next week.
b. Policy formulation
c. Decision making

d. Policy implementation

e. Policy evaluation

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?

Inspire other NGOs, raise public awareness to increase demand for clear up operations.

Environmental dimension

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation ?

No protected status.

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

Rocky beaches, ocean floor.

b. Habitats: Key habitats

Tidal areas, ocean floor.

c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats

Norway is not part of EEC, only EEA, so none

d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats

Kelp forests, coral reefs.

e. Fauna: Key fauna species

Basking shark, spiny dogfish, Atlantic cod, humpback whale, grey seal, common minke whale, harbour porpoise, haddock, porbeagle, school shark, Atlantic halibut, white beaked dolphin.

f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC

Not known.

g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species

Ivory gull, Atlantic puffin, buff-breasted sandpiper.

h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC

Not known.

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.

Unsure what you mean here – management of what?

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Fishing, commercial and recreational 5/5 Transport (ferries and private boats). 2/5

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Has no protection status; the fishing (over-fishing, ghost-fishing) that is the main threat the ecosystem 5/5; climate change also driving some species further north, impacting ecosystem dynamics 3/5. Also litter, discarded plastics from fishing and non-fishing sources 3/5

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

See 12

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).

a. Yes, no? Yes

Only Directory of Fisheries regular survey (since 2019 they do a stretch of coast annually, not yet the Vestland coast).

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

National.

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?

Directory of Fisheries (henceforth, DoF)

d. How long is it being implemented?

1980s, ongoing

e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?

By the ghost fishing survey (since 2014): nets, pots, metal lines, lines, ropes, trawling nets, anchors, buoys.

15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

a. spatial coverage

DoF only mostly intensely fished areas covered and a limited area each year.

Self-report is national <https://www.fiskeridir.no/Fritidsfiske/Tal-og-analyse/Tapte-og-funne-reiskap/Oversikt-over-tapte-og-funne-reiskap> (for leisure fishers)

b. temporal coverage

Only back to 2014 and data from 2022 not yet published

From 2017 (approx.) for self-report systems.

c. data quality and resolution

For DoF episodic & limited in spatial scope, for self-report depends on local awareness and individual use, Estimates suggest only 10% is reported.

d. monitoring frequency
DoF less than once a year; not yet for Vestland
e. stakeholder engagement limitation
DoF report limited awareness of available reporting opportunities
f. accessibility and availability of data
Accessible and available for everyone online
g. data integration and interoperability
Not integrated with data on marine wildlife
h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders
They are working together with two private entities that have boats and ROVs to extract ghost gear, they are buying a new boat equipped with charging and other electronic needs for a ROV to be operated from.
Targeting of areas to clean depends on self-report vs environmental data/sensitivity
i. funding
They have funding for their ongoing pilot-project, but not to continue past June 28 2024
j. infrastructure and supporting services
Vuvi AS, Skjærgårdsservice, Ragn-sells, Øyvar, Miljømarkedet Bruktbygg (The warriors of Norways second hand shop).
k. other

16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?
a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)
Website & app for public comms
b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)

Public reporting portal commercial <https://www.barentswatch.no/fiskinfo/lostfishingfacility/8db881ff-db72-49db-a80e-f50c1e6bbd3e>

Public reporting portal recreational, app downloaded from here:
<https://www.fiskeridir.no/Fritidsfiske/Meld-tapt-og-funnen-reiskap>

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?

a. Public institutions

Face to face, telephone (call or SMS), email, Websites,

b. Academia or groups of experts

Face to face, telephone (call or SMS), email, Websites,

c. Private enterprises

Face to face, telephone (call or SMS), email, Websites, Instagram

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

Face to face, telephone (call or SMS), email, Websites, Instagram

e. Citizens

Face to face, email, Websites, Instagram

18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?

No biodiversity monitoring so far linked to ghost fishing: DoF app & maps for public transparency

a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?

Transparent but depend on public reporting and DoF visits to area

b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?

Improve local data on distribution of fishing gear. Maybe biodiversity monitoring???

19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?

[Prompt] Please bear in mind that even if there are datasets for a specific topic,

Maybe biodiversity monitoring???

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

We have not yet. Self-report app feeds a map – data visualisation. DoF tables could be converted to nicer looking graphics.

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

We are not (yet)

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives?
If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

a. Topic of the initiative

Will consult and add on this

b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)

c. Communication channels

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

Beach-clean ups are supported by a network of local organisations; it would be good to harness this to extend this below the surface of the ocean.

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

No, but open to fabulous ideas

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

Facebook, Local newspapers (digital)

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

Don't know (yet)

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

We will seek more info from the Green Warriors of Norway

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

We will seek more info from the Green Warriors of Norway

29. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

Ca 650 000 (Vestland population)

30 Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

3.3 million per annum (2019) in Bergen, mostly in the summer

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

Doesn't really impact the case study, but there are other sustainability implications

30. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

Health and social care (72k); trade & commerce (37k); teaching, industry & construction (all ca. 30k); transport & storage 17k; Mining & extraction (oil?) 14k; Hotel & catering 12k; agriculture, fishing & forestry 9k

ANNEX VIII QUESTIONNAIRE - LAULASMAA-KLOOGARANNA, ESTONIA

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

- Lääne-Harju Municipality (relevance 5), a local authority where the whole case study area is located, the relevance is based on the fact that the municipality is responsible for various development activities and public service delivery. First and foremost, it has a spatial planning and construction-related decision making functions, furthermore the daily maintenance of public areas is their responsibility. Municipality initiated a reconstruction of beach infrastructure few years ago (investment combined municipal budget and ERDF-funding)
- Estonian Environmental Board/EEB (relevance 4), it's an Estonian governmental agency to govern all Estonian nationally protected areas. Kloogaranna-Laulasmaa case study area accommodates a part of Meremõisa National Landscape Protected Area (Laulasmaa segment of the area, size 42 ha). The EEB is responsible for administrative issues, regulative powers according to Estonian Nature Conservation Act;
- State Forest Management Centre, SFMC (relevance 3) is a state-owned profit-earning institution to manage state-owned forest. Since the landscape-protection area mentioned above is largely afforested SFMC is responsible for forest management there, furthermore it is responsible for creating recreational facilities into state-owned forest (not implemented within case study area, but expected by the local population and public).

b. Academia or groups of experts

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

- LaSpa resort (relevance 3-4) – a resort hotel with 150 rooms, spa-centre, restaurants, conference centre and beach facilities;
- Local café's and smaller guesthouses, seasonal beach service providers (relevance 3)

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

- Local settlement NGO's in Laulasmaa and Kloogaranna villages (relevance 3), settlement- based NGO to

represent local inhabitants and to arrange joint activities and projects;

- NGO Laulasmaa Surf Club, an NGO to arrange surfing activities in Laulasmaa beach area, administer some of the related infrastructure

e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)

- Local permanent citizens
- Local seasonal citizens (area accommodates thousands of summerhouses used only during summer period)
- Tourists (both Estonian and foreign) to visit LaSpa, International Arvo Pärt Centre and beaches

2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

- The decision of Estonian Government to initiate the national protection of Laulasmaa Landscape Protection area and define the protection framework (July, 2005) – defines the protected habitats and species, general regulative framework (relevance 3 – rather general, applies only partially);
- Laulasmaa Landscape Protection Area’s management plan for the years 2019-2028 (endorsed by the decision of the general director of EEB) – define the acts and regulations necessary to ensure that the protection goals from the governmental framework are fulfilled (relevance 4, applies partially, but has a direct impact on the range of activities);
- Municipal comprehensive plan. As a spatial planning framework a comprehensive plan is devised for the territory of a rural municipality and it provides the basic lines of the territorial-economic development, specifies the conditions of permanent and sustainable development and integrates both of the issues. Since Lääne-Harju municipality was formed during the merge of 4 different municipalities in 2017, the process to devise a new plan for the whole municipality is still underway. Until this finishes an old plan prepared in 2005 for one of the former municipalities is in place (relevance 5).

3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:

a. Climate change

Local climate and energy plan of Lääne-Harju Municipality (2023)

b. Biodiversity

n/a
c. Urban and rural planning
Indicated above
d. Mobility
Mobility issues are addressed in local and regional spatial plans, mobility plan is not composed for the territory
e. Tourism
Tourism strategy of Harju County 2025 (regional strategy)
f. Participatory research
n/a
g. Agriculture
Main regulations for the agricultural land use are to be defined with the comprehensive planning document
h. Others
n/a

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental department of the municipality - Nature protection planning department, nature protection management department in Estonian Environmental Board - Recreational department, Estonian State Forest Management Centre (RMK)

5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
Coincides with information in Q1

6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?

a. Agenda setting

Estonian Government, responsible ministry

b. Policy formulation

Estonian Government, responsible ministry, Estonian Environmental Board

c. Decision making

Estonian Environmental Board, Lääne-Harju Municipality, RMK

d. Policy implementation

Estonian Environmental Board, Lääne-Harju Municipality, RMK

e. Policy evaluation

Estonian Government, responsible ministry, Estonian Environmental Board

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?

Better mutual understanding of stakeholders with different positions

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation ?

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

Laulasmaa coastal landscape (sandy beaches and dunes)

b. Habitats: Key habitats

Sandy beaches and dunes, afforested coastal habitats
c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats
Permanent vegetated sand dunes (1640) ² , afforested dunes (2180) and limestone platforms (8210)
d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats
n/a
e. Fauna: Key fauna species
N/a
f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC
Narrow-mouthed Whorl Snail (<i>Vertigo angustior</i>)
g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species
n/a
h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC
n/a

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.
/indicated above/

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recreation (4) - Residential (4) - Business/services (2)

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

- Lack of financial resources (3)

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

- Habitat degradation (user pressure, expansion of residential areas/use)
- Climate change impacts (floods, droughts)

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).

a. Yes, no?

- eBiodiversity is a portal for the taxa found in Estonia, based on mainly on citizen science inputs, the quality level of the data can vary (national)
- PlutoF, Common Data Space for Biodiversity (national)

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

National

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?

EBiodiversity - GBIF—the Global Biodiversity Information Facility and University of Tartu Natural History Museum and Botanical Garden

PlutoF- University of Tartu

d. How long is it being implemented?

TBC

e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?

TBC

15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

a. spatial coverage
b. temporal coverage
c. data quality and resolution
d. monitoring frequency
e. stakeholder engagement limitation
f. accessibility and availability of data
g. data integration and interoperability
h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders
i. funding
j. infrastructure and supporting services
k. other

The general level of systematic data collection on local level is low in Estonia, also implies for the case study area.

16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?

a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)

eBiodiversity, if relevant

b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)

Participatory digital tools for input collection from stakeholders

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?

a. Public institutions

Face to face meetings, calls, emails

b. Academia or groups of experts

Face to face meetings, calls, emails

c. Private enterprises

Face to face meetings, calls, emails

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

Face to face meetings, calls, emails

e. Citizens

Seminars, local media, social media

18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?

Mostly qualitative data about public policies

a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?

Available (limited) data can be considered transparent
b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?
General lack of local level quantitative data from sources provided above, need to collect additional data

19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?
Quantitative data to assess the status of protected habitats and species to justify the strict regulations for recreational activities

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.
TBC

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?
TBC

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives? If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.
a. Topic of the initiative
Recreational ecosystem services
b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)
Local population, all age groups
c. Communication channels
Local agents, local media, local NGO's (sports, youth)

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

Need to balance the recreational use of the area and protection of habitats/species

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

TBC

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

Local Social Media (municipal and community level groups), local newspaper

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

Local citizens (seasonal and permanent), visitors, municipal officers

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

Governmental officers (EEB, RMK)

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

No

29. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

1500

30. Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

Not been monitored

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

TBC

31. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

Majority of the population commutes for the employment purposes to capital Tallinn, regional towns (Keila), local jobs are limited to some public (school) and private sector (hotel, catering) jobs

ANNEX IX QUESTIONNAIRE –

CORBU, ROMANIA

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national) - 5

Local government, County Government, Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve Administration

b. Academia or groups of experts - 3

University "Ovidius" from Constanta

University "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" from Iasi

National Institute for Marine Research and Development "Grigore Antipa"

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives - 5

ALEXIA & TEO TOUR S.R.L.

ARCIPELAGO S.R.L.

ARYA PALADE S.R.L.

BAKRY MYRYON CONSTRUCT S.R.L.

BIC LINE CONSTRUCT PARTENER S.R.L.

BRF RENTAL RESOURCES S.R.L.

CADTOP UNIC SRL

CAMIS HAPPY FARM S.R.L.

CAMP & EVENT EXPERT S.R.L.

CASA CRISTINA CORBU SRL-D

CASUTELE AMALIEI S.R.L.

CAZARE BALLIU SRL

CHERHANA MIDIA S.R.L.

CHIRPIX TURISM S.R.L.

CLEVER DESIGN PROJECT S.R.L.

COMPLEX DELIA CORBU S.R.L.

CORBU ACCOMMODATION S.R.L.

CORBU AGRO-TURIST S.R.L.
CORBU GOLF SRL
CORTUL DE LA MARE 2021 S.R.L.
COS WIND INSTALLATION S.R.L.
COSMIN PROFESSIONAL SERVICE S.R.L.
CT CORBU CONSTRUCT S.R.L.
D&S RAG FIRST INVEST S.R.L.
DIM CLASS CONSTRUCT S.R.L.
DOSOTO RESORT SRL
DUDIZZA SERVES S.R.L.
EDI RENOVATION S.R.L.
ELVIRA MAREA NEAGRA S.R.L.
EVENIMENTE PE PLAJA SRL
FULL MOON CONSULTING SRL
GILCA AGROTURISM SRL
GREEN EXECUTIVE SRL
HAPPY FAMILY CORBU S.R.L.
I.C. COMPLET BUILDING S.R.L.
IN CURTE LA BUNICUL CEL TRAZNIT S.R.L.
KUMSAL INVEST CONSTRUCT S.R.L.
LA CABANA CU 5 MARGARETE SRL
LA COLIBELE DIN CORBU S.R.L.
MAGIC SUMMER LOTUS S.R.L.
MARINE GLAMPING S.R.L.
MELISSA & ANAYS DONER S.R.L.
METALGLASS STIL CONSTRUCT S.R.L.
MIREA RESIDENCES S.R.L.
MONTAGGI EUROPA S.R.L.
MULTISERVICE DADCRIS SRL
NATALIS NASCOR S.R.L.
NAVIMAX SOLUTIONS S.R.L.
NOVA PROACTIV ADG S.R.L.
PAPA IN DRUM SRL
PENSIUNEA RALU S.R.L.
PERLA ALPHA CORAL S.R.L.
PISCICOLA CORBU S.R.L.

<p>PRIM COZ REZIDENT S.R.L.</p> <p>RAVEN COMSTAR S.R.L.</p> <p>ROMPAINT INDUSTRIES SRL</p> <p>SALO AG TURISM SRL</p> <p>SEACOMPANY S.R.L.</p> <p>SOCRITA CORBU SRL</p> <p>TAMARA AVANTAJ TOUR SRL</p> <p>TATA & SOHN POWER DRIVE S.R.L.</p> <p>TORA IMPACT TEAM S.R.L.</p> <p>TOTAL DOBROGEA CONSTRUCT S.R.L.</p> <p>TRAGENT SA</p> <p>TRAGENT UTIL SRL</p> <p>VADU AGROTURISM SRL</p> <p>VAGD NOSOTROS S.R.L.</p> <p>VARA LA CORBU S.R.L.</p> <p>VE TECHNISCHE GROUP S.R.L.</p> <p>VILA DALILA S.R.L.</p>
<p>d. NGOs or other third sector groups - 4</p>
<p>Romanian Ornithological Society / BirdLife Romania</p> <p>ONG Mare Nostrum</p>
<p>e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.) - 5</p>
<p>local citizens</p> <p>tourists</p>

<p>2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).</p>
<p>Local development strategy for Corbu (Strategia de dezvoltare locală a Comunei Corbu 2023 – 2030) – 5</p> <p>Management plan or Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve – 5</p> <p>The 2021 - 2027 Regional Development Plan for the Southeast Region, Romania – 3</p> <p>Strategy for Intelligent Specialization of the Southeast Region for the period 2021-2027, Romania – 2</p> <p>The Development Strategy of the Constanța Metropolitan Area - 2</p> <p>The National Strategy for Sustainable Development of Romania – 2</p>

3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:

a. Climate change - 3

Climate change could have significant impacts on the development of Corbu Beach in Romania, particularly due to its location along the Black Sea coast. The potential influences include:

- **Increased Coastal Erosion:** As sea levels rise, the force of waves on the coastline increases, leading to accelerated erosion. Coastal defenses may be needed, increasing the cost of development and maintenance. The loss of sand and dunes could also negatively affect the beach's natural beauty and ecological value.
- **More Frequent and Severe Storms:** Climate change is expected to increase the frequency and intensity of storms in coastal areas. Corbu Beach may experience more violent storm surges, leading to flooding, infrastructure damage, and habitat destruction. This would affect both tourism and local biodiversity.
- **Changing Marine Ecosystems:** Warmer water temperatures and shifting salinity levels can alter marine ecosystems. Species that currently thrive in the Black Sea may decline, and invasive species may move in, disrupting local biodiversity. This could affect both natural conservation efforts and commercial fishing activities near Corbu Beach.
- **Impacts on Tourism:** Climate change could make summer temperatures more extreme, reducing the comfort of beachgoers or altering the tourist season. Conversely, it might also extend the warm-weather season, potentially increasing the number of tourists. The challenge will be balancing tourism development with the preservation of natural resources.
- **Water Resources and Infrastructure:** The increased frequency of droughts and higher temperatures could strain local water resources. Development projects may need to adapt to fluctuating water availability, which could increase costs and complicate planning.

For Corbu Beach's sustainable development, careful planning will be needed to mitigate the effects of climate change, protect ecosystems, and balance tourism with environmental conservation.

b. Biodiversity - 5

Biodiversity plays a critical role in shaping the development of Corbu Beach in Romania, especially as it is located near ecologically sensitive areas like the Danube Delta and part of the Black Sea coast. Its influence on development can be understood through several key factors:

- **Ecotourism Potential:** The rich biodiversity of Corbu Beach, including various bird species, marine life, and plant ecosystems, makes it an attractive destination for ecotourism. Development that respects and highlights this biodiversity can create unique opportunities for sustainable tourism. Birdwatching, wildlife tours, and nature photography could attract eco-conscious tourists, boosting the local economy while conserving nature.
- **Environmental Protection Regulations:** The biodiversity in and around Corbu Beach includes protected species and habitats under Romania's NATURA 2000 network and international agreements like the Ramsar Convention. These protections could influence development plans, requiring them to align with conservation efforts. Development might be limited or need to undergo stricter environmental assessments to ensure no harm is done to local species, such as the nearby wetlands which support migratory birds.

Coastal Ecosystem Services: Biodiversity provides essential ecosystem services that benefit both development and the environment. For example:

- Dune vegetation helps prevent coastal erosion, stabilizing the beach and protecting any infrastructure from storm surges or rising sea levels.
- Wetlands nearby act as natural filters for water, maintaining water quality and protecting the marine environment, which is crucial for both tourism and local fisheries.
- Marine biodiversity, including fish populations and shellfish, can support sustainable fishing practices if protected and managed properly.
- **Limiting Overdevelopment:** Maintaining biodiversity could act as a natural check against overdevelopment. Preserving natural habitats and species diversity will require limits on urbanization, resort development, and infrastructure. Striking a balance between development and conservation can protect Corbu’s unique natural beauty, which is a primary attraction for both local visitors and tourists.
- **Invasive Species Management:** Development could inadvertently introduce invasive species to the area, which could disrupt local biodiversity. Invasive species often thrive in disturbed areas, outcompeting native species and degrading ecosystems. Managing biodiversity properly includes careful monitoring and controlling potential threats from invasive species that might come with increased human activity.
- **Mitigation of Climate Change Effects:** Biodiversity plays a role in mitigating the effects of climate change, which will be crucial for the future of Corbu Beach. Healthy ecosystems, including coastal dunes, wetlands, and marine habitats, act as buffers against rising sea levels and extreme weather events. A biodiverse ecosystem is more resilient to changes, offering better protection against erosion, flooding, and habitat loss, which can directly impact the long-term viability of any development.
- **Research and Conservation Opportunities:** The biodiversity at Corbu Beach offers significant potential for scientific research and conservation programs. Partnerships between local authorities, universities, and NGOs can help monitor ecosystems, gather data on species, and implement conservation initiatives. These projects can also attract international funding and expertise, which could support both conservation and local development.

In conclusion, biodiversity is not just an obstacle to development but an asset that can drive sustainable growth. Development projects at Corbu Beach should integrate biodiversity conservation to create long-term economic, social, and environmental benefits.

c. Urban and rural planning - 5

Urban and rural planning play a crucial role in shaping the development of Corbu Beach in Romania, particularly given the ecological sensitivity of the area and its proximity to the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve. Proper planning can ensure a balance between development, conservation, and community needs, while poor planning may lead to environmental degradation, loss of biodiversity, and unsustainable growth. Here’s how urban and rural planning could influence the development of Corbu Beach:

- **Zoning Regulations and Land Use Planning:** Urban and rural planning involve defining specific zones for various types of land use, such as residential, commercial, tourism, and conservation areas. In the case of Corbu Beach:
 - Conservation zones could be established to protect sensitive habitats, wetlands, and wildlife, limiting the extent of construction or human activity in these areas.
 - Tourism zones could be designated for eco-friendly resorts or recreational activities, ensuring that development does not encroach upon protected areas like the nearby NATURA 2000 sites.
 - Residential and commercial zones need to be planned carefully to prevent urban sprawl or

overdevelopment that could strain local infrastructure and damage the environment.

Proper land-use planning ensures that development is controlled and in harmony with the ecological characteristics of the area, maintaining its appeal for tourism while safeguarding biodiversity.

- **Infrastructure Development:** Planning for infrastructure such as roads, utilities, and public services is essential to supporting sustainable growth. Key aspects include:
 - Transport infrastructure: Proper road networks and public transport facilities connecting Corbu Beach to nearby towns and cities (such as Constanța) can support tourism while reducing the negative environmental impact of heavy traffic. Inadequate planning may lead to congestion, pollution, and habitat fragmentation.
 - Water and waste management: Developing sustainable water supply systems, sewage treatment facilities, and waste disposal mechanisms is crucial for preventing environmental degradation, especially considering Corbu's proximity to wetlands and the Black Sea.
- **Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs):** Urban and rural planning for Corbu Beach must include rigorous environmental impact assessments (EIAs) for any proposed development. These assessments will:
 - Evaluate the potential impacts of construction, tourism, and other activities on local ecosystems, biodiversity, and water quality.
 - Ensure that any development is aligned with environmental protection regulations, particularly under the NATURA 2000 network.
 - Require mitigation measures, such as setting construction limits, preventing pollution, and protecting vulnerable species or habitats.

Incorporating EIAs into planning ensures that development does not exceed the area's ecological capacity and helps avoid irreversible environmental damage.
- **Sustainable Tourism Development:** Urban and rural planning that emphasizes sustainable tourism can turn Corbu Beach into a model of eco-friendly development. Key strategies include:
 - Low-impact construction: Building eco-lodges, boardwalks, and facilities with minimal disturbance to natural landscapes ensures that tourism infrastructure does not negatively impact the beach's biodiversity or scenic value.
 - Visitor management plans: Planning for controlled tourism flow, designated walking paths, and limits on vehicle access can prevent habitat degradation and overcrowding, while maximizing the beach's appeal as a quiet, nature-based destination.
 - Cultural and rural integration: Working with rural communities in the area to promote traditional fishing, agriculture, and eco-tourism initiatives can enrich the visitor experience and support local livelihoods.

Sustainable tourism planning also fosters long-term economic benefits by attracting nature-loving tourists while preserving the environment that draws them to Corbu Beach.
- **Climate Resilience and Coastal Protection:** Urban and rural planning should also account for the long-term effects of climate change on Corbu Beach. With rising sea levels, stronger storms, and coastal erosion becoming major challenges:
 - Coastal defenses: Planning for natural coastal defenses, such as dune restoration and wetland preservation, can help mitigate the impact of storm surges and erosion. Hard infrastructure like seawalls may be necessary in some areas, but soft defenses that work with natural ecosystems are often more sustainable.
 - Flood management: Rural and urban planning should integrate flood risk assessments and design infrastructure to withstand extreme weather conditions. Developing buffer zones between buildings and

the coast can also protect both human activities and natural habitats from flooding.

- Sustainable drainage systems: Implementing proper water drainage systems will help manage rainwater and prevent runoff from polluting coastal waters, which is especially important for preserving the local marine ecosystem.
- **Balancing Rural and Urban Development:** Corbu Beach lies at the intersection of rural and urban areas, and planning needs to ensure a balanced approach to development that benefits both local communities and visitors:
 - Supporting rural livelihoods: Ensuring that rural communities benefit from beach development through opportunities in eco-tourism, local craft industries, and services can create incentives for preserving the natural environment. Agriculture and small-scale fishing, key parts of the local rural economy, must also be considered in planning to avoid disrupting these traditional livelihoods.
 - Preventing over-urbanization: Limiting urban development to designated areas and preventing sprawl are critical to maintaining the natural character of Corbu Beach. Over-urbanization could lead to loss of rural charm, congestion, pollution, and depletion of natural resources.

Urban and rural planning are pivotal in shaping the sustainable development of Corbu Beach. By prioritizing environmental protection, sustainable tourism, climate resilience, and community involvement, planning can ensure that Corbu Beach remains a natural and economic asset for Romania, balancing conservation with responsible development.

d. Mobility - 4

Mobility plays a significant role in the development of Corbu Beach in Romania, as it directly impacts accessibility, tourism growth, environmental sustainability, and the local economy. The way mobility is managed, including transportation infrastructure and policies, can either promote sustainable development or lead to over-tourism and environmental degradation.

- **Accessibility and Tourism Development:**
 - Improved road and transport networks can significantly boost tourism by making Corbu Beach more accessible to both domestic and international visitors. Better connectivity to nearby cities such as Constanța, as well as airports and train stations, could result in increased visitor numbers.
 - However, over-accessibility might lead to overcrowding and over-tourism, straining the local environment and resources. Unregulated or poorly managed tourism could result in habitat destruction, pollution, and a decline in the beach’s natural beauty, which would reduce its appeal in the long run.
- **Public Transport and Sustainable Mobility:**
 - Promoting public transport options like buses or shuttles from nearby cities would reduce traffic congestion and lower the carbon footprint of visitors. Eco-friendly transport solutions, such as electric buses or bike-sharing programs, would align with the natural, eco-tourism appeal of Corbu Beach.
 - Encouraging sustainable mobility, such as cycling or walking paths, could enhance the visitor experience while preserving the environment. This would also contribute to a lower impact on wildlife and natural habitats, which are sensitive to noise and pollution from vehicles.
- **Infrastructure Development and Environmental Impact:**
 - Developing new roads, parking areas, and transportation hubs must be carefully planned to avoid encroaching on sensitive ecosystems, particularly since Corbu Beach is inside the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve. Poorly planned infrastructure could fragment habitats, displace wildlife, and lead to habitat degradation.
 - Green infrastructure solutions such as permeable pavements, solar-powered streetlights, and electric

vehicle charging stations would minimize environmental damage while supporting mobility needs.

- **Impact on Local Communities:**

- Increased mobility could bring economic benefits to local communities, as improved access would likely lead to more visitors and create opportunities for local businesses, including accommodations, restaurants, and tour operators.

- However, without proper planning, the influx of tourists and vehicles could put pressure on local infrastructure and resources, such as roads, water supply, and waste management systems, particularly in rural areas. This could result in local residents experiencing lower quality of life due to overcrowding or pollution.

- **Impact of Future Mobility Trends:**

- Emerging mobility trends, such as electric vehicles (EVs), autonomous cars, and shared mobility solutions, could influence Corbu Beach’s development in the future. EVs would reduce emissions, supporting a cleaner, more sustainable tourism industry, while shared mobility could decrease the number of individual cars, reducing congestion and parking issues.

- Micromobility solutions (e.g., e-scooters, bicycles) could be ideal for short distances and would align with the eco-tourism goals of the area, allowing visitors to explore without causing environmental harm.

Mobility will be a key factor in shaping the sustainable development of Corbu Beach. While improved access and transportation infrastructure can drive economic growth and tourism, careful planning is essential to avoid environmental degradation and overcrowding. By prioritizing public transport, green mobility options, and sustainable infrastructure, Corbu Beach can maintain its natural beauty and ecological importance while benefiting from responsible tourism development.

e. Tourism - 5

Tourism can significantly influence the development of Corbu Beach in Romania, shaping its economy, infrastructure, environment, and local communities. As Corbu Beach is known for its natural beauty, relatively undeveloped coastline, and proximity to protected areas like the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve, the impact of tourism can be both positive and negative. Here's how tourism could influence Corbu Beach's development:

- **Economic Growth:**

- **Boosting the Local Economy:** Increased tourism could lead to economic growth in the region, creating jobs in hospitality, services, and retail. Local businesses such as hotels, restaurants, and tour operators would benefit from a rise in visitors, contributing to the local economy.

- **Attracting Investments:** The potential for growth in tourism might attract investments in infrastructure, accommodations, and other facilities. This could lead to the development of more hotels, eco-lodges, campsites, and restaurants, making Corbu Beach a more accessible and attractive destination.

- **Infrastructure Development:**

- **Improved Accessibility:** Tourism demand could lead to better infrastructure, such as improved roads, parking facilities, public transportation, and utilities (e.g., water supply, electricity, waste management). This would not only benefit tourists but also improve the quality of life for local residents.

- **Overdevelopment Risks:** However, unplanned or rapid development could harm the natural landscape. Excessive construction of hotels, resorts, or entertainment venues could lead to urban sprawl, destroying the beach’s natural charm and potentially damaging ecosystems.

- **Environmental Impact:**

- **Conservation Opportunities:** If tourism is managed sustainably, it could generate revenue for

conservation efforts, especially since Corbu Beach is near sensitive ecosystems like the Danube Delta. Eco-tourism initiatives could help fund habitat restoration, wildlife protection, and environmental education programs.

- **Habitat Degradation:** On the flip side, mass tourism could lead to habitat destruction, littering, and pollution. Unregulated beach access and recreational activities like motorized water sports could harm wildlife and disrupt fragile ecosystems. Coastal erosion, habitat loss, and biodiversity decline are real risks if tourism is not carefully controlled.

- **Pressure on Protected Areas:** The NATURA 2000 network, which protects biodiversity-rich areas, means that increased tourist footfall could put pressure on these sensitive zones. Overcrowding and human disturbance could negatively affect local species, including nesting birds.

- **Eco-tourism and Sustainable Development:**

- **Promotion of Eco-tourism:** Given Corbu Beach's natural setting and proximity to important ecological zones, it has great potential as an eco-tourism destination. Developing responsible tourism initiatives focused on nature conservation, such as guided birdwatching tours, kayaking, or nature walks, could position Corbu as a model for sustainable tourism.

- **Sustainable Infrastructure:** Investments in eco-friendly accommodations (e.g., solar-powered lodges or zero-waste camping sites) could attract tourists interested in low-impact, environmentally conscious travel. This approach could preserve the area's natural assets while promoting sustainable development.

- **Seasonal and Over-tourism Concerns:**

- **Seasonal Tourism Boom:** Like many coastal destinations, Corbu Beach may experience a seasonal influx of tourists, particularly in the summer months. This seasonal tourism could lead to an overstretched infrastructure and resources during peak times, such as water shortages, increased waste, and crowded public spaces.

- **Over-tourism:** If Corbu Beach becomes too popular, it may face issues related to over-tourism, such as overcrowded beaches, traffic congestion, and a decline in the quality of the visitor experience. Over-tourism could degrade the natural environment and push tourists to seek less crowded alternatives, reducing the area's long-term appeal.

- **Tourism's Role in Environmental Education:**

- **Awareness and Education:** A well-managed tourism strategy could raise awareness about the importance of biodiversity and conservation. Educational programs, signage, and guided tours could inform visitors about the unique habitats of the area, helping to foster a sense of responsibility for protecting these ecosystems.

- **Visitor Management:** Implementing visitor management strategies such as designated walking paths, restricted areas to protect wildlife, and eco-friendly tourism practices could ensure that tourism does not come at the expense of the environment.

- **Climate Change Adaptation**

- **Tourism and Climate Change:** The development of Corbu Beach as a tourism destination must take into account climate change impacts, such as rising sea levels and increased storm frequency. Coastal infrastructure could be at risk, and planning for climate-resilient development would be essential to safeguard the area's long-term viability as a tourism hub.

- **Sustainability Practices:** Encouraging sustainable tourism practices, such as energy-efficient accommodations, reduced water consumption, and promoting public transport over private car use, would help mitigate the carbon footprint of tourism.

Tourism could act as both a driver of economic development and a potential threat to the natural and cultural assets of Corbu Beach. If managed responsibly, it could boost the local economy and help fund conservation

efforts while preserving the area's unique natural landscapes and biodiversity. However, unregulated or mass tourism could lead to environmental degradation, loss of local culture, and the over-commercialization of the area. Sustainable tourism planning, focusing on eco-friendly practices, infrastructure, and community involvement, will be critical to the successful development of Corbu Beach.

f. Participatory research – 3

Participatory research could play a vital role in influencing the development of Corbu Beach in Romania by ensuring that local stakeholders, residents, environmental experts, and other relevant groups are actively involved in decision-making processes. By fostering collaboration between communities, researchers, and policymakers, participatory research can help balance development needs with the preservation of natural and cultural resources. Here's how participatory research could impact Corbu Beach's development:

- **Inclusive Decision-Making:**

- Local Engagement: Participatory research involves local communities in the research process, ensuring that their voices and concerns are heard. This would be especially important in Corbu, where residents may have specific knowledge about the beach's ecological and cultural significance. By including them in the planning process, development can be aligned with the needs and desires of those most affected by it.

- Collaborative Governance: Involving local authorities, environmental organizations, and citizens in research allows for a more democratic decision-making process. This collaboration can help resolve conflicts between conservation goals and economic development by identifying shared values and priorities.

- **Context-Specific Solutions:**

- Tailored Development Strategies: Participatory research can lead to context-specific solutions that address local challenges. By tapping into the knowledge of local fishermen, environmentalists, and tourism operators, researchers can gather data to develop strategies that work for Corbu Beach's unique setting. For instance, local input might reveal ways to promote sustainable tourism that preserves natural habitats while still benefiting the local economy.

- Cultural Sensitivity: Development efforts often run the risk of overlooking or undervaluing local culture and traditions. Participatory research would help ensure that these aspects are preserved in the planning process, leading to a culturally respectful and community-supported development.

- **Sustainable Environmental Management:**

- Conservation through Collaboration: Participatory research can bring together scientists, conservationists, and local communities to create sustainable environmental management plans for Corbu Beach. Local stakeholders can contribute knowledge about biodiversity, wildlife habitats, and seasonal changes in the ecosystem, which can inform conservation strategies that prevent habitat degradation or over-exploitation of natural resources.

- Monitoring and Feedback: Engaging local residents and experts in continuous monitoring of the beach's environment ensures that conservation efforts are effectively implemented. Local participation in gathering data on biodiversity, pollution, or tourism impacts helps maintain the ecological health of Corbu Beach, allowing for timely interventions if problems arise.

- **Conflict Resolution:**

- Balancing Competing Interests: Development projects often bring competing interests to the surface, such as between economic development, tourism, and conservation. Participatory research fosters dialogue between all stakeholders, helping to mediate conflicts and find compromises. For Corbu Beach, where tourism development may conflict with environmental preservation, participatory research can

facilitate solutions that satisfy both sides, such as eco-tourism ventures that protect habitats while generating income.

- Long-Term Cooperation: Establishing a framework for participatory research ensures ongoing collaboration between stakeholders. This ongoing involvement can help address future challenges as they arise, making it easier to adapt development plans to evolving environmental, economic, or social conditions.

- **Data-Driven Policy Making:**

- Evidence-Based Solutions: Participatory research ensures that data collected from the ground, including local knowledge and scientific research, is used to guide development decisions. For example, data on seasonal bird migrations, pollution levels, and the impact of tourism can inform policies that protect biodiversity while allowing for sustainable beach development.

- Community-Led Initiatives: Empowering communities to generate their own data on local challenges, such as pollution, beach erosion, or tourism pressures, helps ensure that policies and development initiatives are based on accurate, locally-relevant information. Community-driven research can also uncover innovative solutions that might be missed by external researchers.

- **Sustainable Tourism Development:**

- Co-Designing Tourism Models: Participatory research could involve both local stakeholders and tourists in co-designing sustainable tourism models for Corbu Beach. These models could focus on eco-tourism, ensuring that development enhances the natural beauty of the beach while preserving its biodiversity. Stakeholders could help shape tourist guidelines, limit development in sensitive areas, and ensure that local businesses benefit from tourism.

- Creating Long-Term Value: By involving the community in research and planning, tourism initiatives are more likely to create long-term value. Sustainable, locally-driven tourism models can attract environmentally-conscious visitors, ensure income for local businesses, and minimize negative impacts on the ecosystem.

- **Resilience to Climate Change:**

- Adapting to Climate Risks: Corbu Beach, like many coastal areas, may face risks related to climate change, such as sea-level rise and coastal erosion. Participatory research can engage local communities in identifying vulnerabilities and developing adaptive measures. For instance, local knowledge about changing weather patterns, tides, and natural barriers like dunes can help shape strategies to protect the beach from climate impacts.

- Community-Led Resilience Initiatives: Including local communities in research on climate adaptation fosters community resilience. These initiatives can lead to the implementation of nature-based solutions, such as restoring dunes or planting vegetation to prevent erosion, which are more likely to succeed if they are supported and maintained by the community.

Participatory research could profoundly influence Corbu Beach’s development by integrating local knowledge, ensuring sustainable practices, fostering collaboration, and creating tailored solutions. By involving local stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, participatory research helps strike a balance between tourism development, conservation, and community well-being. It promotes long-term, inclusive, and adaptive strategies that are essential for the sustainable development of Corbu Beach.

g. Agriculture - 2

Agriculture could influence the development of Corbu Beach in Romania in various direct and indirect ways, especially considering its proximity to agricultural areas. The relationship between agricultural practices and coastal development can shape environmental health, economic activities, and sustainability in the region. Here’s

how agriculture might affect the development of Corbu Beach:

- **Impact on Water Quality:**

- **Runoff and Pollution:** Agricultural activities, particularly large-scale farming, can contribute to runoff containing fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides that enter nearby rivers and eventually flow into the Black Sea near Corbu Beach. This runoff can lead to eutrophication, which causes algal blooms and depletes oxygen levels in coastal waters, harming marine life and degrading water quality. Poor water quality would negatively affect tourism, recreational activities, and the beach's overall appeal.

- **Soil Erosion:** Improper agricultural land management in surrounding areas can lead to increased soil erosion, with sediments being carried into coastal waters. This sediment can cloud the water, smother aquatic habitats, and disrupt the natural ecosystem, making the beach less attractive for visitors and less viable for marine biodiversity.

- **Pressure on Natural Resources:**

- **Water Usage:** Agriculture often requires significant amounts of water for irrigation. In the Corbu Beach region, this could create competition for water resources between farming and other needs, such as drinking water, tourism, and maintaining natural ecosystems. Over-extraction of groundwater for agriculture could lead to a lowering of the water table, potentially affecting wetlands and other coastal habitats that are important for biodiversity conservation.

- **Land Use and Habitat Conversion:** Agricultural expansion in the area could lead to the conversion of natural habitats, such as pastures or wetlands, into farmland. This would reduce biodiversity, disrupt wildlife migration patterns, and potentially limit the space available for tourism development or conservation initiatives near Corbu Beach.

- **Biodiversity Loss:**

- **Habitat Destruction:** Agricultural intensification often involves clearing land and changing natural landscapes, which can lead to habitat loss for species that depend on the coastal and nearby environments. This can directly affect Corbu Beach, as its biodiversity might be compromised if nearby agricultural land disrupts ecosystems critical to birds, fish, and other wildlife, potentially affecting eco-tourism opportunities.

- **Fragmentation of Natural Areas:** Large agricultural fields can fragment landscapes, making it harder for wildlife to move between protected areas, including the Natura 2000 network that may cover parts of the region. This loss of connectivity could reduce the overall resilience of the ecosystem at Corbu Beach, especially if important migration corridors are disrupted.

- **Economic Opportunities:**

- **Agritourism Synergies:** Agriculture could also provide an opportunity for sustainable agritourism in the Corbu Beach region. Tourists visiting the beach could be encouraged to visit nearby farms for organic produce, wine tastings, or traditional Romanian agricultural experiences. Promoting local agriculture alongside beach tourism could boost the local economy and provide diversified income streams for rural communities.

- **Local Food Supply:** Agriculture near Corbu Beach can supply locally grown food to restaurants, hotels, and visitors, reducing the carbon footprint associated with food transport. Promoting farm-to-table initiatives could enhance the area's attractiveness to eco-conscious tourists, supporting sustainable development.

- **Land Use Conflicts:**

- **Competition for Space:** Agriculture and tourism can sometimes compete for land, especially in coastal areas where both are highly valued. If agricultural activities expand, they could limit the available land for tourism infrastructure, such as hotels, recreational areas, or nature reserves. This competition could drive

up land prices and lead to conflicts between farmers, developers, and conservationists.

- Environmental Regulations: Agricultural activities near Corbu Beach would need to comply with environmental regulations, particularly because of the presence of protected areas like Natura 2000 sites. Striking a balance between maintaining agricultural productivity and protecting the coastal environment could be a challenge, particularly if agricultural practices are not sustainable.

- **Opportunities for Sustainable Development:**

- Integrated Coastal and Agricultural Planning: By incorporating sustainable agriculture into regional planning, the Corbu Beach area could develop a model that supports both farming and coastal tourism. Integrated land management could help maintain natural ecosystems, improve soil health, and reduce runoff, while still allowing productive agricultural use of surrounding lands.

- Agroecology as a Tool: Agroecology, which emphasizes sustainable farming in harmony with natural systems, could be adopted in the region to promote a more environmentally friendly form of agriculture. This approach would minimize the environmental impact of farming on Corbu Beach while ensuring food security and livelihood opportunities for local communities.

- **Pollution Control and Conservation Initiatives:**

- Buffer Zones: Creating buffer zones between agricultural areas and sensitive coastal ecosystems at Corbu Beach can help filter runoff and prevent pollutants from reaching the sea. Buffer zones could be incorporated into land-use planning to ensure that both agriculture and tourism can coexist without compromising environmental quality.

- Sustainable Agriculture Incentives: Local governments could encourage farmers near Corbu Beach to adopt sustainable agriculture practices through subsidies, training, and financial incentives. This could reduce the environmental footprint of farming and promote a more balanced approach to development that benefits both the agricultural and tourism sectors.

Agriculture’s influence on the development of Corbu Beach in Romania is multifaceted. While agriculture can provide economic benefits and support local food systems, it can also pose challenges related to water quality, habitat destruction, and land-use conflicts. Sustainable and integrated planning that promotes eco-friendly agricultural practices, water management, and habitat conservation is essential to ensure that agriculture and tourism at Corbu Beach can coexist in a way that benefits both the environment and local communities.

h. Others - 3

We can add here:

- **Demographic Changes**

Population Growth and Urbanization: The growth of nearby urban centers, such as Constanța, could have a spillover effect on Corbu Beach. Increased urbanization could lead to higher demand for residential areas, increasing pressure to develop the coastal region.

Migration and Seasonal Population: Corbu Beach may experience significant seasonal population shifts due to tourism. This influx can strain local resources like water, waste management, and public services, requiring thoughtful planning to ensure sustainability.

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

To identify the governance units and departments with direct competence over Corbu Beach in Romania, a

comprehensive review of relevant agencies and departments involved in environmental protection, tourism, urban and rural planning, mobility, biodiversity, and other key objectives is required. The governance structure can be aligned with the objectives of Corbu Beach development to ensure an integrated and coordinated approach.

Governance Units/Departments with Direct Competence for Corbu Beach:

1. Urban and Rural Planning

- **Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration (MDLPA):** Oversees urban and rural planning, regional development, and territorial planning. It sets policies on land use that affect how Corbu Beach and surrounding areas are developed. This institution manifests its authority at the local level through:
 - o **Constanța County Council:** Regional authority with planning jurisdiction over coastal developments, including the area around Corbu Beach. Coordinates urban development plans and integrates environmental considerations into local planning. - 4
 - o **Corbu Municipality:** The local administrative unit responsible for issuing local zoning plans (PUZ) and urban development strategies at the village or commune level. - 5

2. Environmental Protection and Biodiversity

- **Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests:** This is the main national-level ministry responsible for environmental protection, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable use of natural resources. It is responsible for implementing national and EU environmental laws (e.g., NATURA 2000). This institution manifests its authority at the local level through:
 - o **National Agency for Environmental Protection (ANPM):** Oversees environmental assessments and compliance with environmental protection laws. - 5
 - o **Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve Authority (ARBDD):** Relevant if the protected areas near the Danube Delta are impacted, including the coastal zones close to Corbu. - 5

3. Agriculture and Land Use

- **Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development:** Oversees land use policies, agricultural development, and rural areas adjacent to Corbu Beach.
 - o **Constanța County Agricultural Directorate:** Monitors agricultural activities in the Corbu region and works to ensure that land use practices are sustainable and do not conflict with environmental conservation goals. - 3

4. Mobility and Infrastructure

- **Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure:** Responsible for developing national transport infrastructure, including roads, public transport, and accessibility to tourist areas.
 - o **Romanian National Company of Motorways and National Roads (CNAIR):** Develops and maintains roads, including those leading to Corbu Beach. Ensures infrastructure aligns with national development goals. - 2
 - o **Constanța County Directorate for Road Infrastructure:** Manages regional transport infrastructure that connects Corbu Beach with major cities like Constanța, as well as other tourist destinations. -

5. Tourism Development

- **Ministry of Entrepreneurship and Tourism:** This ministry is responsible for the development of tourism policies and strategies in Romania, including sustainable tourism in coastal regions.
 - o **Constanța County Tourism Office:** Regional office tasked with promoting tourism and ensuring it aligns with local economic development and environmental protection. - 2
 - o **National Agency for Tourism:** Oversees national tourism promotion and works on initiatives to increase the appeal of destinations like Corbu Beach, while maintaining environmental sustainability. - 2

Corbu Beach Objective	Governance Unit/Department	Role
Environmental Protection & Biodiversity	Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests, ANPM, ARBDD	Overseeing the protection of natural habitats, species, and enforcement of environmental laws, including NATURA 2000 compliance.
Urban and Rural Planning	Ministry of Development (MDLPA), Constanța County Council, Corbu Municipality	Responsible for land-use planning, zoning regulations, and sustainable development in coastal regions.
Tourism Development	Ministry of Entrepreneurship and Tourism, Constanța County Tourism Office, National Agency for Tourism	Promoting tourism while balancing ecological conservation and local economic development.
Mobility and Infrastructure	Ministry of Transport, CNAIR, Constanța County Directorate for Road Infrastructure	Developing transport links, public transport options, and road infrastructure that support sustainable tourism and regional access.
Agriculture and Land Use	Ministry of Agriculture, Constanța Agricultural Directorate	Overseeing agricultural policies and land use to prevent conflicts between farming activities and the conservation of sensitive coastal habitats.
Legislative Creation and Decision-Making	Romanian Parliament, Government of Romania, Constanța County Prefecture, ANPM	Creating, approving, and enforcing laws and regulations concerning environmental protection, tourism development, and coastal land use.
Research and Scientific Input	Ovidius University of Constanța, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iasi, National Institute for Marine Research	Providing scientific research and data to inform policy decisions on biodiversity, coastal erosion, and ecosystem services at Corbu Beach.
Public Participation and Civil Society	Local NGOs (Romanian Ornithological Society, Mare Nostrum), Community Associations	Representing the interests of local communities, ensuring sustainable development goals are met, and raising awareness of environmental conservation issues.

5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

The main stakeholders involved or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives are:

- Corbu Local Council: Manages local affairs, including land use, development permits, and environmental initiatives. – 5
- Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve Authority: Although focused on the Danube Delta, this authority may have influence on coastal areas like Corbu Beach due to proximity and environmental impact considerations. – 4
- Agency for Environmental Protection Constanta (APM Constanta): Oversees the implementation of environmental policies and regulations. – 4
- Constanța County Council: Local government body responsible for regional development, including land-use planning and environmental protection. – 4
- Tourism Operators: Hotels, resorts, and tour operators that may benefit from or impact the conservation efforts at Corbu Beach. – 4
- Real Estate Developers: Companies interested in coastal development, potentially influencing land-use policies. - 4
- Romanian Waters National Administration: Manages water resources and has jurisdiction over coastal areas. – 3
- Agricultural Enterprises: Local farms and agribusinesses that may affect land and water use around Corbu Beach. – 3
- Fishing Industry: Both small-scale and commercial fishers who utilize marine resources near Corbu Beach. – 3
- Local Residents: Directly impacted by conservation policies and land use decisions, and can influence policy through public consultations and local councils. – 3
- Visitors and Tourists: Their behavior and demand for services can influence the type of policies implemented, especially regarding tourism management. – 3
- Community Groups: Local associations advocating for the preservation of Corbu Beach, its natural beauty, and sustainable use. – 2
- Local Environmental NGOs: Smaller organizations that focus on specific conservation initiatives in the region. - 2
- National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa”: Provides scientific research and data that inform policy-making. – 1
- Romanian Ornithological Society (SOR): Active in bird conservation and monitoring, influencing policies related to avian species on Corbu Beach.
- Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi and Ovidius University of Constanța: Contribute research and expert knowledge on coastal ecosystems, biodiversity, and environmental impacts.
- Research Institutes: Various research institutes focusing on ecology, marine biology, and environmental science provide critical data and policy recommendations. – 1

6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?

a. Agenda setting

- The **Romanian Parliament** plays a pivotal role in shaping the national agenda for environmental protection, tourism development, and coastal land use management. As the primary legislative body, it is responsible for drafting, debating, and enacting laws that govern the sustainable use of natural resources, the conservation of biodiversity, and the regulation of activities impacting coastal areas. Through its legislative powers, Parliament ensures that environmental considerations are integrated into national development strategies and works to balance economic growth with ecological preservation.
- The **Government of Romania** is central to the country's policy-making process, setting priorities and strategies that guide national development across various sectors. It coordinates efforts between ministries and governmental agencies, ensuring that environmental, economic, and social objectives are aligned. The government also plays a key role in implementing international agreements related to environmental protection and sustainable development, working to position Romania as a leader in green policies at the regional and European levels.
- The **Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests** is a key actor in shaping Romania's environmental conservation policies. It is tasked with designing and implementing strategies for environmental protection, water resource management, forest conservation, and biodiversity preservation. The ministry plays a critical role in coordinating national efforts to combat climate change, reduce pollution, and manage natural resources sustainably, while also ensuring that Romania complies with EU environmental directives and international environmental agreements. Through its work, the ministry promotes the sustainable development of natural landscapes, including Romania's coastal regions, forests, and protected areas.

b. Policy formulation

In Romania, several key ministries and governing bodies contribute to the formulation of policies across various sectors, ensuring that environmental protection, sustainable development, and regional growth are integrated into national and regional frameworks.

- **Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests:** This ministry is the primary authority responsible for creating and implementing national policies that focus on environmental protection, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable management of natural resources. It oversees the formulation of strategies aimed at reducing pollution, mitigating the effects of climate change, preserving ecosystems, and promoting sustainable practices in forestry and water management. The ministry also plays a pivotal role in shaping Romania's compliance with international environmental agreements and EU directives, ensuring that the country meets its obligations in protecting natural habitats and maintaining biodiversity.
- **Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration (MDLPA):** The MDLPA is essential in formulating policies related to land-use planning, regional development, and urban and territorial planning. It works to create a balanced approach to national development, ensuring that rural and urban areas are equally supported and that infrastructure projects are aligned with sustainable land-use practices. The ministry's policies are designed to enhance economic growth, improve public services, and promote smart city development while integrating environmental considerations into urban planning and regional development frameworks. Through its efforts, the MDLPA supports the long-term sustainability of both built and natural environments across Romania.
- **Ministry of Entrepreneurship and Tourism:** This ministry plays a critical role in formulating policies

related to the growth and promotion of the tourism sector. Its policies aim to develop Romania's tourism potential in a way that supports local economies while safeguarding cultural and natural heritage. By focusing on sustainable tourism practices, the ministry works to balance the economic benefits of tourism with the need for environmental conservation, particularly in sensitive regions such as Romania's coastal areas and protected natural landscapes. The ministry's policies are also geared towards fostering entrepreneurship in the tourism industry, supporting small and medium enterprises (SMEs), and promoting Romania as a premier sustainable tourism destination in Europe.

- **Constanța County Council:** As a regional governing body, the Constanța County Council actively participates in the formulation of policies that focus on regional development and environmental protection, especially in coastal areas. The Council works closely with national ministries and local stakeholders to ensure that policies are tailored to the unique needs of the region. This includes addressing challenges related to coastal land use, urban expansion, tourism development, and environmental degradation. By integrating regional perspectives into national policy frameworks, the Constanța County Council plays a critical role in promoting sustainable development that aligns with both local priorities and national goals for environmental conservation and economic growth.

c. Decision making

The decision-making related to environmental protection, tourism development, and coastal land use involves multiple levels of governance, with each institution playing a crucial role in shaping, approving, and implementing policies that impact both local and national development.

- **Romanian Parliament:** As the highest legislative authority in the country, the Romanian Parliament plays a fundamental role in the decision-making process by debating, approving, or rejecting proposed laws and regulations. It is responsible for enacting legislation that governs key areas such as environmental protection, tourism development, coastal land use, and regional planning. Parliamentary decisions set the legal framework that guides national and regional efforts to promote sustainable development, mitigate environmental challenges, and protect Romania's natural resources. In this capacity, the Parliament not only provides oversight for policy implementation but also shapes long-term strategies for economic growth and ecological conservation, ensuring compliance with both national priorities and international commitments.
- **Government of Romania:** The Government of Romania is tasked with the critical responsibility of implementing the policies, laws, and decisions approved by the Parliament. Once legislation is enacted, the government, through its various ministries and agencies, ensures the operationalization of these decisions, translating them into actionable programs and initiatives. It coordinates efforts across multiple sectors, ensuring that environmental policies, tourism strategies, and land use plans are integrated and effectively executed at both the national and local levels. The government also plays a key role in monitoring the impact of these policies, making adjustments when necessary, and providing feedback to the Parliament for future legislative amendments.
- **Constanța County Council:** At the local level, the Constanța County Council is a key decision-making body responsible for implementing national policies within the region, particularly those related to environmental management, tourism development, and coastal land use. The Council tailors national strategies to fit local needs and conditions, ensuring that policies are effectively adapted to address regional challenges such as coastal erosion, tourism pressures, and sustainable land management. It is also responsible for local governance decisions, approving land use changes, zoning regulations, and environmental conservation efforts within its jurisdiction. The Council works closely with local stakeholders, including businesses, communities, and civil society, to ensure that decision-making processes are inclusive and that local development aligns with both national policies and the sustainable development goals of the region.

d. Policy implementation

The implementation of policies across various sectors—such as environmental protection, regional development, land use planning, and tourism—requires a coordinated effort between national ministries and local authorities. These bodies work together to operationalize national strategies, ensuring they are effectively translated into concrete actions at both the national and regional levels.

- **Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests:** As the leading authority in environmental matters, the Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests plays a crucial role in overseeing the implementation of environmental policies, laws, and regulations. This ministry is responsible for enforcing national environmental standards and ensuring compliance with international agreements, such as the Paris Agreement and EU environmental directives. Its work includes managing protected areas, safeguarding biodiversity, regulating pollution control measures, and overseeing natural resource management (such as water and forests). The ministry also collaborates with regional and local authorities to ensure that environmental policies are adapted to local conditions and effectively implemented, fostering sustainable development across Romania's diverse ecosystems.
- **Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration (MDLPA):** The MDLPA is tasked with implementing policies related to land-use planning, urban and regional development, and territorial planning. This ministry focuses on the strategic development of both urban and rural areas, promoting balanced growth across regions. It works on the infrastructure needed to support regional connectivity, urban expansion, and smart city development while incorporating sustainability and climate resilience into its projects. Through its efforts, the MDLPA ensures that national development strategies are grounded in efficient land use, responsible resource management, and long-term planning that considers the environmental and economic needs of communities across Romania. The ministry also plays a key role in coordinating regional development programs funded by the EU, aligning Romania's infrastructure projects with broader European goals.
- **Ministry of Entrepreneurship and Tourism:** In charge of promoting and developing Romania's tourism sector, this ministry plays a vital role in implementing policies that enhance tourism infrastructure while maintaining a focus on sustainability. The ministry works to promote eco-friendly and sustainable tourism practices, particularly in sensitive areas such as coastal regions, national parks, and heritage sites. Through collaborations with local authorities and businesses, the ministry ensures that tourism development contributes to local economies without compromising environmental conservation. It implements campaigns and projects aimed at promoting Romania as a top sustainable tourism destination, developing programs that encourage responsible tourism, protect natural and cultural resources, and promote the inclusion of local communities in tourism-related activities.
- **Constanța County Council:** At the regional level, the Constanța County Council is responsible for implementing policies related to regional development, land use, tourism, and environmental protection. As the administrative authority overseeing one of Romania's most important coastal areas, the Council ensures that national policies are tailored to meet the specific challenges of the region, such as coastal erosion, urban expansion, and tourism pressures. The Council plays a critical role in translating national strategies into local action plans, particularly in terms of sustainable land management and environmental protection. It engages local communities and stakeholders, ensuring that policies are locally relevant and effectively address the needs of both the population and the region's natural resources. By integrating local perspectives into broader policy frameworks, the Council supports the sustainable development of Constanța County as a key economic and ecological region in Romania.

e. Policy evaluation

Policy evaluation in Romania is a critical process that involves multiple institutions working collaboratively to assess the effectiveness of policies related to environmental protection, biodiversity, and coastal management. The goal is to ensure that policies are achieving their intended outcomes and that necessary adjustments can be made to address emerging challenges, particularly in ecologically sensitive areas like Corbu Beach.

- **The Romanian National Institute for Marine Research and Development (INCDM):** As the leading institution in marine and coastal research, INCDM plays a vital role in policy evaluation by providing robust scientific data and expert analysis. The institute conducts comprehensive studies on key environmental issues, such as biodiversity, coastal erosion, water quality, and ecosystem services, which are crucial for assessing the impact of implemented policies. INCDM's research findings are used to monitor the effectiveness of environmental regulations, particularly in protected areas like Corbu Beach, where human activities and natural processes threaten the delicate balance of coastal ecosystems. The institute also provides critical feedback on how well current policies are preserving biodiversity and preventing coastal degradation, thus informing future policy revisions.
- **Romanian Parliament:** The Parliament is central to the policy evaluation process as it conducts reviews of policy effectiveness at the national level. Through parliamentary committees, oversight bodies, and expert consultations, it evaluates whether the laws and regulations it has passed are producing the desired environmental, social, and economic outcomes. In the context of biodiversity conservation and coastal management, the Parliament reviews reports from government ministries, scientific institutions, and civil society organizations to assess whether existing policies are meeting goals such as reducing coastal erosion, protecting endangered species, or promoting sustainable tourism. Based on these evaluations, the Parliament can propose amendments or new legislation to address gaps or inefficiencies, ensuring that Romania's environmental governance remains adaptive and effective.
- **Central Government of Romania:** The Government, through its ministries and agencies, plays a crucial role in the ongoing evaluation of policy outcomes, particularly in environmental and development sectors. It systematically reviews the implementation and impact of policies, analyzing data and performance reports to identify areas where adjustments may be needed. The Government collaborates with local authorities, such as the Constanța County Council, and research bodies like INCDM to gather feedback on how policies are functioning on the ground, especially in sensitive coastal areas like Corbu Beach. This continuous evaluation allows the Government to refine its strategies, ensuring that policies are flexible enough to respond to evolving environmental challenges while aligning with Romania's long-term sustainability goals. By making data-driven adjustments, the Government ensures that national policies remain relevant, effective, and capable of addressing both regional and national needs.

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?

If policies cannot be changed or directly influenced, Corbu Beach can still benefit from future strategies through several alternative approaches and outcomes:

1. Community-Led Conservation Initiatives

Grassroots Engagement: Encourage local communities and stakeholders to take ownership of conservation efforts. Even without formal policy changes, community-driven projects can enhance the protection of biodiversity and sustainable practices.

Education and Awareness Campaigns: Increase awareness among residents, tourists, and local businesses about the importance of conservation. Education can lead to voluntary changes in behavior and practices that benefit the environment.

2. Sustainable Tourism Development

Ecotourism Promotion: Develop and promote ecotourism that focuses on the natural beauty and biodiversity of Corbu Beach. This can attract visitors who are interested in low-impact travel and can help fund conservation initiatives.

Certification Programs: Implement voluntary sustainability certifications for businesses operating in the area. These programs can incentivize environmentally friendly practices without needing policy changes.

3. Research and Data Collection

Long-Term Monitoring Programs: Establish long-term ecological monitoring to track changes in biodiversity, habitat quality, and the effects of human activities. This data can inform future strategies and potentially influence policy indirectly through evidence-based advocacy.

Citizen Science Initiatives: Engage the public in data collection through citizen science programs. This can build a larger dataset over time and increase public investment in conservation efforts.

4. Public-Private Partnerships

Collaborative Projects: Work with businesses, NGOs, and academic institutions to develop joint initiatives that align with conservation goals. These partnerships can fund and implement projects that might otherwise require government support.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): Encourage local businesses to adopt CSR strategies that include funding or supporting environmental initiatives at Corbu Beach.

5. Conservation Funding and Grants

Accessing External Funds: Seek funding from international organizations, foundations, and NGOs that focus on environmental conservation. These funds can support local projects even if local policies remain unchanged.

Crowdfunding: Launch crowdfunding campaigns for specific conservation projects. Public interest can generate the necessary resources to implement small-scale conservation actions.

6. Climate Change Adaptation Strategies

Resilience Planning: Develop strategies that enhance the resilience of Corbu Beach to climate change impacts, such as sea-level rise and increased storm frequency. This might include habitat restoration, dune reinforcement, and other adaptive measures.

Innovative Solutions: Explore and implement innovative, nature-based solutions to address environmental challenges. For example, using natural barriers like mangroves or wetlands to protect the coastline.

By leveraging these strategies, Corbu Beach can achieve positive conservation outcomes and sustainable development, even in the absence of policy changes.

Environmental dimension

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation ?

Natura 2000 Network: Corbu Beach is part of the Natura 2000 network, which is the cornerstone of EU nature conservation policy. This designation includes:

- Special Protection Areas (SPAs): Corbu Beach is recognized for its importance in protecting bird species

under the EU Birds Directive (Directive 2009/147/EC). SPAs are specifically designated for the protection of vulnerable bird species and their habitats.

- Special Areas of Conservation (SACs): Under the EU Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC), Corbu Beach may also be included as a SAC, focusing on the conservation of natural habitats and species of European importance.

Also, Corbu Beach is part of Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve, which is probably the most important wetland area from Romania, being part of RAMSAR Convention.

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

- a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

Costal dunes habitats

- b. Habitats: Key habitats

2110 Embryonic shifting dunes

2130 Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation – habitat for priority conservation

- c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats

2110 Embryonic shifting dunes

2130 Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation – habitat for priority conservation

- d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats

2130 Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation

- e. Fauna: Key fauna species

Gavia stellata

Gavia arctica

Puffinus yelkouan

Pelecanus onocrotalus

Pelecanus crispus

Phalacrocorax pygmeus

Egretta garzetta

Ardea alba

Ciconia nigra
Ciconia Ciconia
Plegadis falcinellus
Platalea leucorodia
Cygnus cygnus
Branta ruficollis
Anser erythropus
Mergus albellus
Circus aeruginosus
Circus cyaneus
Circus pygargus
Circus macrourus
Pandion haliaetus
Buteo rufinus
Himantopus Himantopus
Recurvirostra avosetta
Pluvialis apricaria
Charadrius alexandriunus
Philomachus pugnax
Limosa lapponica
Burhinus oedicnemus
Larus genei
Larus melanocephalus
Larus minutus
Sterna caspia
Sterna hirundo
Sterna sandvicensis
Chlidonias hybridus
Chlidonias niger
Asio flammeus
Anthus campestris
Sylvia nisoria
Lanius collurio
Lutra lutra

f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC

Lutra lutra

g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species

Gavia stellata

Gavia arctica

Puffinus yelkouan

Pelecanus onocrotalus

Pelecanus crispus

Phalacrocorax pygmeus

Egretta garzetta

Ardea alba

Ciconia nigra

Ciconia Ciconia

Plegadis falcinellus

Platalea leucorodia

Cygnus cygnus

Branta ruficollis

Anser erythropus

Mergus albellus

Circus aeruginosus

Circus cyaneus

Circus pygargus

Circus macrourus

Pandion haliaetus

Buteo rufinus

Himantopus Himantopus

Recurvirostra avosetta

Pluvialis apricaria

Charadrius alexandriunus

Philomachus pugnax

Limosa lapponica

Burhinus oediconemus

Larus genei

Larus melanocephalus

Larus minutus

Sterna caspia
 Sterna hirundo
 Sterna sandvicensis
 Chlidonias hybridus
 Chlidonias niger
 Asio flammeus
 Anthus campestris
 Sylvia nisoria
 Lanius collurio

h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC

Branta ruficollis
 Anser erythropus
 Mergus albellus
 Sterna sandvicensis
 Asio flammeus
 Anthus campestris
 Sylvia nisoria
 Lanius collurio

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.

It is still under elaboration, this being the second time it has been submitted as a draft, but it has never been legally approved according to Romanian laws.

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Turism – 5
 Rural/urban development – 4 (nearby)
 Fishing – 3

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

types and intensity of economic activities within the area – 5 (tourism facilities and rural/urban development)
 uncontrolled visitation – 4
 lack of financial resources for protection and management – 4
 fragmentation of management competencies – 3
 conflict of uses – 2

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

Habitat degradation – 5
 biodiversity loss – 5
 pollution – 4
 soil erosion – 4
 invasive species – 3
climate change impacts – 2

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).

a. Yes, no?

Theoretically, yes, by the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve Administration, but in reality, nothing substantial or consistent has been implemented.

For birds, the area is included in Midwinter Count monitoring programme (once a year in mid-January)

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

Theoretical local
 MidWinter monitoring is an international monitoring programme.

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?

Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve Administration
 For MidWinter – Romanian ornithological Society

d. How long is it being implemented?

Theoretical more than 10 years

Midwinter, at least 10 years
e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?
Species populations

15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).
a. spatial coverage
We do not have a good spatial coverage for environmental data on Corbu beach, except the Midwinter count. – 5
b. temporal coverage
We do not have a good temporal coverage for environmental data on Corbu beach, except the MidWinter count. - 5
c. data quality and resolution
We do not have a good data quality and resolution for environmental data on Corbu beach, except the MidWinter count. – 5
d. monitoring frequency
Just for MidWinter count is annually, in mid-January - 4
e. stakeholder engagement limitation
Limited engagement with stakeholders, including local communities, businesses, and environmental organizations. - 4
f. accessibility and availability of data
Only midwinter monitoring is available. - 5
g. data integration and interoperability
None - 4
h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders
On environment data recording are various stakeholders, as: Somanian Ornithological Society, Mare Nostrum and Academia, but they are not involved in monitoring, except midwinter count which is made by Romanian

Ornithological Society. – 3
i. funding
Low funding opportunities - 4
j. infrastructure and supporting services
The area is easy accessible - 2
k. other

16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?
a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)
We can do monitoring programmes for all species, including habitats and aerial cartography.
b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)
Data analyses and reports made by experts.

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?
a. Public institutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Face to face meetings</i> - <i>Email communication</i> - <i>Websites or blogs</i>
b. Academia or groups of experts
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Face to face</i> - <i>Email</i> - <i>Websites or blogs</i>

c. Private enterprises

- *Face-to-face meetings*
- *Email*
- *Websites or blogs*
- *Social media (Facebook, etc.)*
- *Mass and print media (radio, TV, etc.)*

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

Face to face

Email

Websites or blogs

Social media (Facebook, X, Instagram, etc.)

Mass and print media (radio, TV, etc.)

e. Citizens

Websites or blogs

Social media (Facebook, X, Instagram, etc.)

Mass and print media (radio, TV, etc.)

18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?

For biodiversity, we must develop our own monitoring or survey, if we want to collect data

a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?

Transparency portals for public policies – mostly transparent

b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?

Yes, for biodiversity data, local knowledge, social survey

19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?

We need biodiversity data, but also stakeholders' opinions about the area.

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

geographic information systems (GIS) software for spatial analysis – ArcGIS
statistical software for quantitative analysis – R statistical software

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

We can integrate CSV, SHP or any GIS format.

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives? If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

a. Topic of the initiative

NO but in other similar (to the task) projects in order to reach many people with a call for participation in the CS, we proceeded as follows:

- Screen the local media landscape to identify key issues and debates that are currently relevant and engaging for the local community.
- Research previous participatory initiatives and public engagement efforts in the area to understand what has worked well in the past and what lessons can be learned.
- Engage with mediators who know what issues make people become actively engaged in issues of public concern, such as local leaders, community organizers, or experts in relevant fields.

b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)

NO but, according to our experience in other projects we would consider engaging with various communities of citizens who are likely to be interested in the CS objectives. These may include:

- Students: Through schools, universities, or student organizations, we could reach out to students who are interested in sustainability, environmental issues, or social justice.
- Elderly people: Through community centers, senior organizations, or local retirement homes, we could engage with elderly people who may be concerned about issues such as healthcare, social welfare, or environmental protection.
- Other groups: We could also consider engaging with other groups of citizens who may be interested in the CS objectives, such as:
 - Low-income communities: Through community organizations, churches, or local businesses, we could reach out to low-income communities who may be affected by environmental issues or lack of access to resources.
- a. Immigrant communities: Through community centers, language schools, or cultural organizations, we could engage with immigrant communities who may be interested in issues related to integration, social inclusion, or economic empowerment.
- b. Other groups: We could also consider engaging with other groups of citizens who may be interested in

the CS objectives, such as people with disabilities, LGBTQ+ communities, or other marginalized groups.

c. Communication channels

Since we are a PR Agency and this is our major business focus, we would use a variety of communication channels to reach out to the public and engage with them about the CS. These may include:

- Social media: We would utilize social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn to share information about the CS, engage with the public, and gather feedback.
- Online platforms: We would also use online platforms such as blogs, forums, and online discussion groups to engage with the public and share information about the CS.
- Local media: We would work with local media outlets, including newspapers, radio stations, and television stations, to reach a wider audience and promote the CS.
- Community events: We would participate in and organize community events, such as festivals, fairs, and town hall meetings, to engage with the public and promote the CS.
- Direct mail: We would use direct mail campaigns to reach out to specific groups or communities that may be interested in the CS.
- Email newsletters: We would send regular email newsletters to subscribers who are interested in the CS and want to stay up-to-date on the latest developments.
- Public meetings: We would hold public meetings and town hall meetings to engage with the public and gather feedback on the CS.
- Partnerships: We would partner with local organizations, community groups, and businesses to amplify our message and reach a wider audience.

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

The local debates and prominent issues connected to, or potentially connected to, the aspirations of Corbu Beach in Romania could include the following:

1. Conservation vs. Development:

Debate: There is often a tension between conservation efforts and development pressures. Local communities and developers might push for increased tourism infrastructure, residential development, or commercial activities, which could conflict with conservation goals for Corbu Beach.

Issue: Striking a balance between protecting the natural environment, especially the unique biodiversity of Corbu Beach, and promoting economic growth through development is a key challenge.

2. Tourism Impact:

Debate: The impact of tourism on Corbu Beach is a significant point of discussion. While tourism can bring economic benefits to the region, it can also lead to environmental degradation if not managed properly.

Issue: Debates may center on how to manage tourism sustainably, including the construction of facilities,

managing tourist behavior, and protecting sensitive habitats.

3. Land Use and Zoning Regulations:

Debate: Local debates may focus on land use and zoning laws that govern what can be built or developed in and around Corbu Beach. Conflicts can arise between property owners, conservationists, and government authorities over permissible activities and developments.

Issue: Ensuring that zoning regulations are in line with the conservation objectives of Corbu Beach is crucial, but this can be contentious when it limits private land use or development opportunities.

4. Environmental Protection and Biodiversity:

Debate: The protection of biodiversity, particularly regarding endangered species and habitats, is often a subject of local debate. Environmental groups may advocate for stricter protections, while others may prioritize economic activities that could threaten these natural resources.

Issue: Protecting biodiversity requires enforcing conservation laws, which may not always be popular with all stakeholders, especially if it limits certain activities or development projects.

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

NO but based on the assisting tools we could have been following the Bristol Approach methodology for public engagement. About the Bristol Approach, we find this approach particularly useful because it emphasizes the importance of involving citizens at all stages of the process, from problem definition to data collection and analysis, and focusing on issues of importance to them.

Step-by-step process:

- **Identification:** We can identify the stakeholders and communities that will be impacted by the CS and involve them in the identification of the problem or issue.
- **Framing:** We could work with the stakeholders to frame the problem or issue, ensuring that it is well-defined and relevant to their needs and concerns.
- **Design:** We could design the CS project in collaboration with the stakeholders, incorporating their input and feedback throughout the process.
- **Testing:** We can test the CS project with a small group of stakeholders to ensure that it is effective and meets their needs.

Reasons for choosing the Bristol Approach:

The Bristol Approach as far as we realized, provides a structured and participatory framework for engaging with stakeholders and communities. It also emphasizes the importance of involving citizens in the co-creation of research and innovation projects, which aligns with our values and goals.

Involving artists:

We should involve artists in the public engagement process to facilitate creative encounters between stakeholders and communities. Artists will help to develop engaging and accessible materials, facilitate workshops and discussions, and provide a fresh perspective on the problem or issue. By involving artists, we hope to make the public engagement process more enjoyable, interactive, and effective.

Community protocol:

We can develop a community protocol to guide our conduct over the lifetime of the CS. This protocol may

formalize our commitment to free and informed consent from local communities with the help of our “local allies”, ensuring that we respect their rights and interests throughout the project.

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

Local and national mass-media

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

NGO, local journalists, scientists, local government development and tourism companies

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

Local community members who have family roots in this area.

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

No, but there are many mass-media articles presenting the problems.

29. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

Coastal area of Corbu from Constanta county

Population: 5727 inhabitants

Density: 46,01 inhabitants /km²

30. Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

We do not have exact data on this, but it is estimated to be in the tens of thousands.

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

No data

31. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

Road transport of goods

Retail trade in specialized and non-specialized stores

Accommodation facilities for holidays or short stays

Hotels and similar accommodation facilities

Restaurants

Bars and other establishments serving drinks

Repair of household appliances

Recreational and entertainment activities

Custom software development

Business and management consulting

ANNEX X QUESTIONNAIRE – EIDSVIKA/KILDN

[PRO-COAST] Case Study definition Eidsvika/Kildn (Bergen)

This questionnaire is to be completed by each PRO-COAST partner hosting a Case Study (expected time required 30-60 minutes). All the inputs are expected in the form of texts in the tables below. This document can be found online in the PRO-COAST shared folder → WP5 → T5.1. Please rename the document including the name of the Case Study. Once completed and renamed, please upload the document to the same folder and/or send it by email to Fermín Serrano fermin@ibercivis.es DEADLINE May 31, 2024

0. About and glossary of terms

The PRO-COAST project was launched to address the issue of biodiversity loss in European coastal ecosystems. Around 40% of Europeans live within 100km of the coast, relying directly on ecosystem services that are threatened by both quantitative and qualitative losses. Groups already facing socioeconomic vulnerabilities are likely to be disproportionately affected. PRO-COAST aims to empower local communities to support the restoration and maintenance of biodiversity and ecosystem services across Europe, integrating local knowledge into practice and policy making. The project is now underway, coordinating the efforts of 20 partners across 14 countries working on 9 unique case studies. These case studies cover multiple conservation approaches across various coastal ecosystems, testing different governance models and social incentives to engage local actors in adopting technologies and actions for biodiversity conservation.

An important element of PRO-COAST is its holistic, interdisciplinary approach, based on a conceptual framework that treats social-ecological systems as interconnected. By mapping relationships between ecosystem components and uncovering feedback dynamics, the project seeks to identify leverage points for transformative change. PRO-COAST promotes integrated bottom-up decision-making, recognizing that environmental issues cannot be separated from social, economic, and political factors. Through extensive citizen engagement guided by state-of-the-art conservation science, the project aims to build community capacity for biodiversity management, providing scalable solutions that balance conservation needs with local socio economic priorities. Now in its early stages, PRO-COAST hopes to inform adaptive, participatory approaches to governance that avoid biodiversity losses and ensure sustainable, equitable access to coastal resources.

Glossary of terms:

Case studies (CS)	The project methods will be tested in nine case studies located on the European continent, both in EU and non-EU areas. The coastal ecosystem is the common thread running through all the case studies, but each one presents specific issues and its own framework for addressing them.
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	There are three Mediterranean cases, three cases in the North-east Atlantic Ocean, one case in the Baltic Sea and one case in the Black Sea. They include island and continental coastal environments.
CS partners	<p>CS1 Comino island Malta Partner: Friends of the Earth, Malta</p> <p>CS2 Apulia Italy Partner: University of Salento</p> <p>CS3 Area of Strunjan Slovenia Partner: University of Primorska</p> <p>CS4 Boka Kotorska Bay area Partner: Montenegro Chamber of Economy</p> <p>CS5 Sligo Ireland Partner: Atlantic Technical University</p> <p>CS6 Arne Parish UK Partner: Anatrack</p> <p>CS7 Bergen Norway Partner: University of Bergen</p> <p>CS8 Kloogaranna-Laulasmaa Estonia Partner Tallinn University of Technology</p> <p>CS9 Corbu Romania Partner: Total PR</p>
Social-ecological systems framework (SESF)	<p>The social-ecological systems framework (SESF) is a conceptual framework providing a list of variables that may be interacting and affecting outcomes in social-ecological systems (SES). SESF is useful to advance collective action theory and more as a general tool to diagnose the sustainability of social-ecological systems</p> <p>The SESF is structured into tiers of nested and related concepts and variables. The first tiers include the Resource System (RS), Resource Units (RU), Governance System (Gov), Actors (A), Social, Economic and Political Settings (S), Interactions (I), External Ecosystems (Eco), and Outcomes (O). SESF is useful to advance collective action theory and more as a general tool to diagnose the sustainability of social-ecological systems. The SESF is divided into several 1st-tier components representing social and ecological as well as external factors and system interactions and outcomes, each divided into multiple 2nd-tier variables.</p>

1. Mission and vision of this questionnaire

The questionnaire presented in this document is framed within the **baseline for each CS** and comprises the (preliminary) characterization of the CS: geographical locations and boundaries, objectives of the CS, baseline information of the current situation of the CS, as well as drivers, references levels and knowledge gaps.

At this point, the CS partner would be ready to get initial feedback based on their current status and capacities. It should be noted that the CS stages are flexible and iterative, adapting to the specificities of each pilot and revising each stage whenever necessary.

The questionnaire pursues a double objective:

- 1) **Provide a comprehensive definition of the 9 CS.** The definition of case studies involves the identification, characterization, and contextualization of specific coastal ecosystems facing biodiversity challenges. This will help drawing the social ecological profiles and benchmarks of the 9 case studies (CS) as a general site diagnosis around key aspects: (1) goals and objectives; (2) environmental; (3) political, institutional and power dynamics; (4) technological; (5) public engagement; and (6) sociodemographic dimensions; This baseline information serves as the diagnosis of the current background situation of each CS before they apply the whole set of actions designed under PRO-COAST.

This questionnaire is intended to be completed by the CS partners participating in the task 5.1 complementing the work performed in other work packages (namely WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP6). The gathering of the data will be undertaken by those partners, enquiring into the current context in the key dimensions that are relevant for setting-up and executing CS. The questions provided are a support tool to promote self-reflection and understanding of each innovation CS current situation. Moreover, it will serve as the focal point for applying the Integrated Assessment Methodology (IAM) developed within WP5.

This questionnaire compliments another questionnaire (in the shape of google sheet) identification of main stakeholders (nature, issues, solution, level of engagement). See this DRAFT document the identification of main stakeholders (nature, issues, solution, level of engagement).

Link to the questionnaire for CS stakeholder identification (DRAFT):

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1j0MQRyR0Km6QxwTx2nZaumF_OPWEm3UC/edit#gid=1061616313

- 2) **Perform situational analyses to define a shared strategy for the CS partners to make the necessary adaptations to move forward on their citizen engagement activities guided by state-of-the-art conservation science.** The questionnaire will generate important information for the PRO-Coast partners to design appropriate measures in support of the 9 pilots and to ensure that collective learning across the pilots is systematic in the way that it is looking for commonalities and differences across the pilots. For instance, PRO-COAST will develop an Integrated Assessment Methodology (IAM). The mentioned strategy will be co-defined between PRO-COAST partners, including CS partners. The strategy will provide insights addressing all the CS relevant dimensions, and once agreed and implemented, will allow CS partners to move into the situational onboarding of citizens or involvement.

1.1. How to answer this questionnaire?

CS partners are responsible for answering the questions of the mentioned dimensions. Consultation of the different experts and stakeholders within the CSs is encouraged for further clarification and support for the process of answering the questionnaire. Most of the questions follow a qualitative methodology, except for the sociodemographic analysis that is mainly based on quantitative indicators. The pilot owners in charge of answering these questions should be aware of the needs and objectives pursued for their specific CS.

2. Situational screening questionnaire

2.1 Goals and objectives of the CS

CS overarching goals and objectives have been pre-defined by CS partners of PRO-COAST. Having these objectives been defined by following a top-down approach, or hybrid approach, it is important to realise the different stakeholders that will be involved may have divergent interests or values and the objectives of the CS may incline more towards preferences and wishes of some stakeholders than those of others. These interests may also change with time. The same can happen with the benefits these stakeholders can perceive.

The following aspects were considered for the initial selection of case studies: (1) the biodiversity of the area and the challenges that threaten it; (2) the community that inhabits it and the cultural context in which they live; (3) the economic driver and primary production; in addition, (4) governance arrangements.

For those reasons, the following questions are focused on facilitating the self-assessment with regards to the connection of the stakeholders.

To address the mentioned issues, each CS partner should consider the following questions:

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

[Prompt] For each group, list the names of each stakeholder in the following rows (more than one stakeholder per group), providing relevant info about their specific objectives and goals. Include any observation if required.

[Recommendation] Reflect on the following: Is the involvement of these stakeholders important in the future? How does this exclusion affect the PRO-COAST project's goal? If the stakeholders that were not consulted are important to reach the CS objectives, map them.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

Askøy Kommune (5). It is the municipality of Askøy.

Fylke (county) (3).

National authorities like the nautic authority, or environmental agency (3)

b. Academia or groups of experts

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

Tertnes holding (5). This enterprise proposes the cruise ship terminal. They are of regional relevance with their earlier business/development projects.

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

Eidsvikas venner (5) ,(Friends of Eidsvikas bay), very local, rather loosely organised but very active group of activists against the cruise ship terminal. They send out leaflets and run a facebook group (>1000 members) on which they (re-)post all info that circulated about the development

Naturvernforbundet Askøy (3) (Nature protection association). This is the local team of the large Nature protection association in Norway, which is organized national, in regional teams and local teams. The leader of this group is also the administrator and key person of Eidsvikas venner.

e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)

The citizens engaged with the topic are organised in the NGO Eidsvikas venner, mentioned above. Hence, they will be contacted through there. (5) Citizens engaged against the plan are people either living on the island generally or adjacent to the area.

Follese Felleskap is the association of the people (citizen) co-owning pieces of the area in question. (3) In order to build the cruiseship terminal they would have to sell their land to the entrepreneur. However, the entrepreneur already owns quite some shares. The offer to sell is attractive but they have not published any decision yet. We have not gotten succeeded in building contact to them.

2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

[Recommendation] Take into account the identified policies for the definition of the CS activities and outputs. How could the CSs foster policies' implementation? ^[1]_[5] Identify the objectives (within the policy) to which the CSs will/could favour.

The local land-use plan that is categorising all the land on the island (municipality Askøy) and its intended use for the next 12 years will be crucial on the development or non-development of the cruise ship terminal. The land-use plan is under development and public hearing procedures in the last half year 2024 and will be finally enforced in spring 2025. The arguments on the land-use plan regarding the Eidsvika area from different stakeholders are publicly accessible and will be used by us to understand the standpoints of the stakeholders and their influence on the future usage of the Eidsvika area. (5)

While the positioning of the public institutions (like ministries, county or national agency) are obliged to objectivity, it is possible that the case study, meaning the citizen initiative (Eidsvikas venner) created attention to the case that influenced stakeholders to use the opportunity and argue against the development or to speak up at all on behalf of the hearing of the land-use plan.

This land-use plan procedure is a standard procedure in Norway.

2.2 Political, institutional and power dynamics dimension

In the situational analysis of a CS, the political, institutional and power dynamics dimension holds significant importance. It refers to the recognition of and consideration of the political and institutional structures and processes that influence the functioning and impact of the CS.

The **political dimension** encompasses the policies and decision-making frameworks within which the CS operates. It involves understanding the relationships between different stakeholders, such as government bodies, regulatory authorities, and civil society organisations, and how these interactions shape the CS's objectives, goals, and outcomes.

The **institutional dimension** focuses on the formal and informal structures, rules, and norms that guide the functioning of the CS. This includes the governance mechanisms, organisational structures, and accountability frameworks that ensure transparency, participation, and equitable representation of diverse stakeholders.

The **power dynamics** dimension addresses the power balances/imbances among the different actors of a CS. It maps the internal power dynamics that connect the objectives, the functioning and the results of the initiatives of each innovation pilot. It supports the description of how the current decision-making system works and presents information about the formal and informal rules and regulations related to the central topic of the CO.

By considering the political, institutional and power dynamics dimension, the CS partners can effectively engage with decision-makers, advocate for change, and influence policy processes. It also allows for the creation of robust and inclusive governance mechanisms that promote transparency, accountability, and meaningful participation of citizens in decision-making processes.

3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:

[Recommendation] To take into account the identified policies for the CS activities and outputs. How the CSs could foster policies' implementation? ^{[[SEP]]}Identify the objectives or indicators (within the policy) to which the CSs will/could favour. ^{[[SEP]]}Extract any useful guidelines or best practices to perform the CS activities.

a. Climate change

Climate change increases the importance of the area remaining undeveloped, since it is a bog that stores large parts of CO₂. (5)

The “green shift” aimed for by EU policies and national targets to reach the climate goals resonate with the presentation of the plan of the entrepreneurs. Norway committed to carbon-neutral sea transport in the fjords within 2026 for tourist ships and ferrys under 10 000 gross tons and 2023 for ships over 10 000 gross tons. Hence, the entrepreneurs argue that their harbour proposal responds to this goal. The anticipate being eligible to subsidies from the Norwegian state and the EU.

Bergen, the neighbouring municipality to Askøy, has implemented a limit of 4 cruise ships per day of which a certain amount needs to be connected to grid. This was implemented to mitigate pollution in the city centre. Askøy (not a cruise ship stop yet) does not have that policy though. A terminal there would cut the effect of the rule in Bergen short. However, connection to the grid is a large argument in the proposal of the entrepreneurs (since that is needed to make it CO₂ neutral), being aware of the rule in Bergen that could be implemented on Askøy as well.

b. Biodiversity

If red-listed species would be found in the area it would help to argue against the cruise ship terminal in this area. Under the recent hearing of the land-use plan, one contribution indicated that 5 red-listed species were found, we are currently searching for more details).

c. Urban and rural planning

Changes in the urban planning of Bergen affect the cruise ship capacity in the next years, which is why the municipality is discussing plans on expanding or moving docks to be able to

welcome cruise ships. Hence, the shortage of the docks in Bergen could have a positive influence on the plans of the entrepreneurs.
d. Mobility
Askøy is a island that is connected to Bergen with a bridge that is characterised by congestion (particularly strong these days due to road works) and a well-used pedestrian ferry connection.
e. Tourism
Tourism in Norway is increasing. The country sees an increase in recent years. This is due to many factors. -hot summers in mid-and southern Europe motivate people to make holidays in cooler areas such as Scandinavia (“coolcation”). - the national currency is very weak which makes the holidays in Norway more affordable. -cruise ships become more and more popular and Norway is a suitable country for this holiday. - fishing has become a more popular trend among young people in Europe, for which Norway is a very suitable destination (vast amount of water and long coast line, free access to fishing, no license needed)
f. Participatory research
Eidsvikas venner are open for contact with us and help with researching aspects of the case and collecting data
g. Agriculture
Even though the area is historically a pasture area, it is not actively used as such in the last years. However, it is officially categorised as a pasture and recreational area (LNF område) in the current land-use plan.
h. Others

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

[Recommendation] Make sure that the governance units/departments cover all the CS objectives' topics. You can, for example, align the CS objectives with the listed governance units/departments in a matrix to explore if this is done. ^[17]Include the responsible for legislative creation and decision-making, which could act as participants or receivers of the CS process. A governance structure can be planned.

Municipality Askøy (5)
 Fylke Vestland (county) (4)
 Kystverket (nautic authority) (4)
 Miljødirektoratet (Norwegian environmental agency) (3)

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5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

[Recommendation] Contact them to inform them about the project and invite them to join it in any form.

- Municipality Askøy (5)
- Politicians in the parliaments Askøy (5)
- Fylke Vestland (county) (3)
- Kystverket (nautic authority) (3)
- Miljødirektoratet (Norwegian environmental agency) (3)
- Tertnes holding (entrepreneur) (5)
- Eidsvikas venner (5)
- Naturvernforbundet Askøy (2)
- Naturvernforbundet Hordaland (1)
- Co-ownership association of the area, Follese Fellekap (3)

6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle¹ within your organisation as pilot owner?

[Recommendation] Consider involving them in the governance structure of the CS.

a. Agenda setting

That is joint

b. Policy formulation

The municipality

c. Decision making

The municipality and the land-owners

d. Policy implementation

The municipality

e. Policy evaluation

All the stakeholders contributing to the hearing with the statements.

¹ A simplified diagram of the policy cycle can be found here: <https://catalyst.harvard.edu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Unknown.png>

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?

[Recommendation] These benefits could be the basis for involving different types of stakeholders (e.g., as inputs for the engagement strategy).

It helps for other land-use conflicts to see which aspects helped to mobilise people for it.

2.3 Environmental dimension

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation ?

[Recommendation] As examples: Natura 2000 site, Local Protection Status, other international conventions (Ramsar, SPAMI, etc.).

Is has no protection status in that sense. However, on the areas that are classified as NLF (pasture/farming and recreational are) only these activites are allowed. For example it is not allowed to be build housing or industry. In the new land-use plan the area is suggested as "harbour" which means infrastructure for harbour-activities are allowed to be developed.

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

[Recommendation] Indicate current status in terms of natural landscapes, habitats, and biodiversity (flora and fauna species)

a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

It is a bug with rocky elements and many shrubs, domestic to the area. There is a smaller bay with sandy floor. There are also large rock formation in which birds find shelter to nest.

b. Habitats: Key habitats

Norwegian coastal habitat. There are nesting birds and typical vegetation for the area.

c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats

Norway is not part of EEC, only EEA, so none

d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats

I am not sure how to answer this, but it is a bug which has definitely priority status in regards to emission mitigation strategies.

e. Fauna: Key fauna species

In the process of investigating the red-listed species living there

f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC

N/A

g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species
No solid info
h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC
NA

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.
No

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant). <i>[Recommendation] Consider, as examples, the following elements: tourism, grazing, hunting, agriculture, fishing, urban development, others.</i>
Recreational (5) It is the only nearby natural area that people living in the very densely populated area of south Askøy can access. People go there to hike, climb and swim.

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). <i>[Recommendation] Consider, as examples, the following elements: uncontrolled visitation, fragmentation of management competencies, types and intensity of economic activities within the area, conflict of uses, lack of financial resources for protection and management, etc.</i>
The cruise ship terminal that is proposed by the entrepreneurs to be built there. (5) It would disturb wildlife and claim spaces for parking, tunnels, streets. The pollution from the ships would affect the aquatic ecosystem of the area and the air.

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant). <i>[Recommendation] Consider, as examples, the following elements: Habitat degradation, pollution, climate change impacts, biodiversity loss, soil erosion, invasive species, etc.</i>
See 12

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in

<p>the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).</p> <p><i>[Recommendation] Investigate the presence of ongoing environmental monitoring initiatives, including biodiversity monitoring programs, pollution tracking systems, and climate monitoring efforts, within the CS area.</i></p>
a. Yes, no?
The entrepreneurs hired a scientific consultancy to write a report about the toxins in the sediments under water. The report concludes there are some toxins in the sediment that could be released by the construction of the harbour or boat traffic; they recommend further risk assessment.
b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)
Only in this area.
c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?
RÅDGIVENDE BIOLOGER AS Edvard Griegs vei 3D, N-5059 Bergen Foretaksnummer 828 988 492-mva
d. How long is it being implemented?
It was cross-sectional investigation.
e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/ habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?
Chemical parameter

<p>15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).</p> <p><i>[Prompt] Please try to describe them in the form of challenges. We provide you the following variables to help.</i></p>
a. spatial coverage
Only in this area (4)
b. temporal coverage
Only cross-sectional (3)
c. data quality and resolution
Difficult to estimate (4)
d. monitoring frequency
Cross-sectional (3)

e. stakeholder engagement limitation
Yes, they were hired by the entrepreneurs (5)
f. accessibility and availability of data
Report is available (5)
g. data integration and interoperability
h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders
Difficult to estimate the expertise of the researchers involved (5)
i. funding
Funded by the entrepreneurs (5)
j. infrastructure and supporting services
k. other
There is no ecological/biological data available on the species and biodiversity in the area yet. It is possible that this has been conducted this autumn on behalf of a political decision process about the area. We are waiting for the data to be published and will consider it in our study.

2. 4 Technological dimension

<p>16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?</p> <p><i>[Recommendation] Explore the benefits and needs of using tools apart from the ones you already have in place.</i></p>
a. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)
Existing platform mostly used is the facebook group
b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)
We used identification apps before to identify birds present in the area. We will discuss if we will use other apps for citizen science like for a biodiversity treasure hunt (example Malta) or to count the visitors of the habitat to emphasise the frequent recreational usage by the population.

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?

[Prompt] e.g., Face to face, telephone (call or SMS), email, Websites or blogs (e.g. PRO-COAST website), social media (Facebook, X, Instagram, etc.), Smartphone Apps (WhatsApp, Viber, Line, etc.), Mass and print media (radio, TV, etc.).

[Recommendation] Leverage these communication channels to support the creation/run of the local community. Explore if the identified communication channels are suitable for all the stakeholders and explore if these still are the best option to communicate with them.

a. Public institutions

Email, websites, face to face, online meetings, phone calls

b. Academia or groups of experts

Email, websites, face to face, online meetings, phone calls

c. Private enterprises

Email, websites, face to face, online meetings, phone calls

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

Email, websites, face to face, online meetings, phone calls

e. Citizens

Email, face to face, online meetings, phone calls, other messenger services (SMS, Whatsapp)

18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?

[Recommendation] Identify how useful those data sources are for the CS regarding PRO-COAST and CS challenges. Consider the following questions:

No ongoing monitoring; but we wait for the publication of the contribution to the hearing regarding the land-use plan of the area. Possible to analyse that

a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?

- Fully transparent

b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?

- I think the contributions are exhaustive since they come from a large consortium of experts

19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?
[Prompt] Please bear in mind that even if there are datasets for a specific topic, CSs could complement them with more data density for the pilot area (e.g., currently unreached areas).

[Recommendation] Establish dialogue among the rest of PRO-COAST partners to explore how to access, maintain or even exploit new data sources.

It could be helpful to monitor the recreational use of the area to report on how frequently used this area is by the population.

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

[Recommendation] Specify the possible thematic exploration per use case, and potential KPIs generated so that decision-makers can leverage from the information distilled. A link with PRO-COAST indicators may be established. Consider geographic information systems (GIS) software for spatial analysis, statistical software for quantitative analysis, and qualitative data analysis software for qualitative data. Also, data visualization tools.

We will use SPSS and R-Studio for any quantitative analyses and combined approaches (like correspondence analysis/network analysis) in document/social media analyses and appropriate methods for qualitative analyses of focus groups and interviews.

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

[Recommendation] Reflect on data volume, formats and ways of accessing and processing such data so that thematic co-explorations can be assembled. If possible, consider using metadata standards reflect formats like CSV (Comma-Separated Values) or JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) for information about data source, collection methods, temporal and spatial coverage, and quality assurance procedures.

CSV

2.4 Public Engagement dimension

To reach many people with a call for participation in the CS we need to align our calls with local debates and issues that matter for already engaged people. That requires a screening of the local media landscape, researching previous participatory initiatives & talking with mediators that know what issues make people become actively engaged in issues of public concern.

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives? If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

[Recommendation] If the initiative is related to any of the topics addressed by the CS, to recover the contact data of the engaged community in order to reach them again.

a. Topic of the initiative
Parts of the team are involved in PRO-CLIMATE (climate resilience of local communities), following a similar approach. We aim to mutually transfer experiences and lessons-learned across the projects on the way, particularly when it comes to the community-based and participatory research work.
b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)
Case study in Norway not yet fully defined
c. Communication channels

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to the aspirations of your CS?

[Recommendation] Aim at conciliating the parties by involving the different actors in the dispute (administrations, private sector, communities).^[11] Communication should always be oriented towards mediating between conflicting interests and not aiming to avoid conflicts/tensions.^[12] Leverage local debates to create the engagement strategy per stakeholder type.

- Entrepreneurs: green-shift (emission free harbour), sustainable and expanded mobility possibilities from Askøy – with a over regional focus
- Kommune: keep quiet so far. The opposition parties are against the idea of the cruise-ship because they are afraid of public expenses due to gaps in the plan/proposal and some also for nature protection reasons
- Citizen initiative: against a cruise ship terminal in the area in question or anywhere else. No compromise potential. Main reasons are nature protection, scepticism about (financial) viability, they do not want the pollution of the ships and neither the tourists on the island, they feel well connected enough by the bridges and the existing ferry route to Bergen

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

[Prompt] If yes, please describe how and specify the step of the process (identification, framing, design, testing). If no, please provide the reasons (e.g., lack of awareness, utilization of alternative methods, insufficient capacity, etc.).

[Recommendation] If not, please consider using some existing methodologies e.g. the Bristol Approach or the Extreme Citizen Science. You may find a basic overview of these proposed approaches in [this document](#). This may help engaging participants at all stages of the process, from problem definition to data collection and analysis, focusing on issues of importance to them. Consider free and informed consent from local communities early in the public engagement process, formalizing terms through a community protocol to guide conduct over the lifetime of the CS. Additionally, consider involving artists to facilitate these encounters.

We are discussing to use two types of citizen science approaches

- 1) Biodiversity treasure hunt (following example of Malta), including children
- 2) Counting system for hikers to document the frequency of recreational use
- 3) Possibly we will use instories (online tool to create creative storytelling content) about Eidsvika in collaboration with the citizen initiative (Eidvikas friends), maybe including children?

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

[Recommendation] Use/leverage the different media channels identified & tailor call for participation to different audiences' issues.

- Mainly FB (a larger group of more than 1000 members where everything is posted or re-posted about the case)
- Local newspaper

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

[Recommendation] Involve the different groups in participation and dissemination of the CS. ¹¹⁷⁷~~1177~~ To propose strategies to reconcile and dialogue between different discourses

- Some of the newspaper articles are written by stakeholders (for example contributions local politicians from the opposition) and others by journalists
- The facebook group is run by Eidvikas venner (citizen initiative)

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

[Prompt] To understand better why these groups are excluded & get closer to the forms of dialogue and discourse of these excluded communities.

[Recommendation] : Consider historically under-represented groups including: Children; People from minority ethnic backgrounds; People with health conditions or impairments; Older people;

- The politicians in the local government and the executive body of the municipality
- The people who own the land are very quiet
But both of these groups are rather "powerful" in the final decision
- The main people being represented and vocal in the discussion are adult, Norwegian, able-bodied people. There are no prominent voices from children, people with more diverse ethical background or any sort of health conditions. However, elderly people are well-involved in the discourse.

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

[Recommendation] If well-established associations are found, invite their participation or avoid conflict with them through dialogue.

Yes, they leaflet and (small-scale) protest when there are events where the entrepreneur presents the idea or just generally in the mall. They also leaflet in the post.

2.5 Sociodemographic dimension

The information gathered through answering to the requirements of the current dimension will be processed by the CS partners by using an intersectional analysis, which focuses on different social categories (sectionalities) that are interconnected. These social categories are addressed by the breakdown of the indicators that we ask CS partners to investigate in their related databases (e.g. official statistical offices).

This analysis considers the characteristics of the population living in the study area and linked population as well as the specific social context of each CS. It ensures that the CS partners are suitable and inclusive, promoting participation and effectively carrying out the activities of the innovation pilots. It is important to look at the population from an intersectional perspective and strive for equality in terms of representation among different groups, including minority groups.

Since the information available varies among each CS country, the segregation or breakdown of the different indicators should be provided according to the available data, in each specific CS.

29. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

[Prompt] Make clear the limits of the CS (e.g. coastal region, NUTS region, etc)

[Recommendation] Ensure that the data covers the entire study area of the case study (CS) and includes information on both permanent residents and seasonal populations, if applicable. Consider disaggregating population data by age groups, gender, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status to gain insights into the demographic composition of the area.

30300 inhabitants. 317.7 inhabitant per square kilometres. Since the bridge to Bergen was built in 1992, the population has increased tremendously. It is one of the fastest growing municipalities in Norway (11.8 % population growth).

A smaller amount of the population is international (approx. less than 2500). Most of them are from Poland (654 people) and Lithuania (358). It is likely that this is related to work migration. Norway recruits large amount of east-European workers. 220 are from Ukraine (assumed to be refugees of war). Followed by Syrians (188), Germans (133) and Eritreans (119).

Demographics of age groups show a gap in the age group of (20-40); suggesting that people move away in this age and it is more popular for families children and middle-aged/elderly people.

More information on age & cultural heritage of population on:
<https://www.ssb.no/kommunefakta/askoy>

30. Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

Askøy is not a tourist destination so far. All tourists usually go to Bergen.

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

In that particular area of Eidsvika zero, in the light of protection for biodiversity. However, a regulates more ecological form of tourism directed from Bergen to Askøy could improve the economical situation of Askøy.

31. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

Most people commute to Bergen for work (10000). There is a general lack of jobs on Askøy. However, most people work with trade, followed by retail, health and social services and teaching. Little to no farming.

ANNEX XI QUESTIONNAIRE

SENT TO THE CASE STUDY PARTNERS

[PRO-COAST] Case Study definition _____ INCLUDE_CS_NAME_HERE

This questionnaire is to be completed by each PRO-COAST partner hosting a Case Study (expected time required 30-60 minutes). All the inputs are expected in the form of texts in the tables below. This document can be found online in the PRO-COAST shared folder → WP5 → T5.1. Please rename the document including the name of the Case Study. Once completed and renamed, please upload the document to the same folder and/or send it by email to Fermin Serrano fermin@ibercivis.es DEADLINE May 31, 2024

0. About and glossary of terms

The PRO-COAST project was launched to address the issue of biodiversity loss in European coastal ecosystems. Around 40% of Europeans live within 100km of the coast, relying directly on ecosystem services that are threatened by both quantitative and qualitative losses. Groups already facing socioeconomic vulnerabilities are likely to be disproportionately affected. PRO-COAST aims to empower local communities to support the restoration and maintenance of biodiversity and ecosystem services across Europe, integrating local knowledge into practice and policy making. The project is now underway, coordinating the efforts of 20 partners across 14 countries working on 9 unique case studies. These case studies cover multiple conservation approaches across various coastal ecosystems, testing different governance models and social incentives to engage local actors in adopting technologies and actions for biodiversity conservation.

An important element of PRO-COAST is its holistic, interdisciplinary approach, based on a conceptual framework that treats social-ecological systems as interconnected. By mapping relationships between ecosystem components and uncovering feedback dynamics, the project seeks to identify leverage points for transformative change. PRO-COAST promotes integrated bottom-up decision-making, recognizing that environmental issues cannot be separated from social, economic, and political factors. Through extensive citizen engagement guided by state-of-the-art conservation science, the project aims to build community capacity for biodiversity management, providing scalable solutions that balance conservation needs with local socio economic priorities. Now in its early stages, PRO-COAST hopes to inform adaptive, participatory approaches to governance that avoid biodiversity losses and ensure sustainable, equitable access to coastal resources.

Glossary of terms:

Case studies (CS)	<p>The project methods will be tested in nine case studies located on the European continent, both in EU and non-EU areas. The coastal ecosystem is the common thread running through all the case studies, but each one presents specific issues and its own framework for addressing them.</p> <p>There are three Mediterranean cases, three cases in the North-east Atlantic Ocean, one case in the Baltic Sea and one case in the Black Sea. They include island and continental coastal environments.</p>
CS partners	<p>CS1 Comino island Malta Partner: Friends of the Earth, Malta</p> <p>CS2 Aquatina di Frigole Apulia Italy Partner: University of Salento</p>

	<p>CS3 Area of Strunjan Slovenia Partner: University of Primorska</p> <p>CS4 Boka Kotorska Bay area Partner: Montenegro Chamber of Economy</p> <p>CS5 Sligo Ireland Partner: Atlantic Technical University</p> <p>CS6 Arne Parish UK Partner: Anatrack</p> <p>CS7 Bergen Norway Partner: University of Bergen</p> <p>CS8 Kloogaranna-Laulasmaa Estonia Partner Tallinn University of Technology</p> <p>CS9 Corbu Romania Partner: Total PR</p>
<p>Social-ecological systems framework (SESF)</p>	<p>The social-ecological systems framework (SESF) is a conceptual framework providing a list of variables that may be interacting and affecting outcomes in social-ecological systems (SES). SESF is useful to advance collective action theory and more as a general tool to diagnose the sustainability of social-ecological systems</p> <p>The SESF is structured into tiers of nested and related concepts and variables. The first tiers include the Resource System (RS), Resource Units (RU), Governance System (Gov), Actors (A), Social, Economic and Political Settings (S), Interactions (I), External Ecosystems (Eco), and Outcomes (O). SESF is useful to advance collective action theory and more as a general tool to diagnose the sustainability of social-ecological systems. The SESF is divided into several 1st-tier components representing social and ecological as well as external factors and system interactions and outcomes, each divided into multiple 2nd-tier variables.</p>

1. Mission and vision of this questionnaire

The questionnaire presented in this document is framed within the **baseline for each CS** and comprises the (preliminary) characterization of the CS: geographical locations and boundaries, objectives of the CS, baseline information of the current situation of the CS, as well as drivers, references levels and knowledge gaps.

At this point, the CS partner would be ready to get initial feedback based on their current status and capacities. It should be noted that the CS stages are flexible and iterative, adapting to the specificities of each pilot and revising each stage whenever necessary.

The questionnaire pursues a double objective:

1. **Provide a comprehensive definition of the 9 CS.** The definition of case studies involves the identification, characterization, and contextualization of specific coastal ecosystems facing biodiversity challenges. This will help drawing the social ecological profiles and benchmarks of the 9 case studies (CS) as a general site diagnosis around key aspects: (1) goals and objectives; (2) environmental; (3) political, institutional and power dynamics; (4) technological; (5) public engagement; and (6) sociodemographic dimensions; This baseline information serves as the diagnosis of the current background situation of each CS before they apply the whole set of actions designed under PRO-COAST.

This questionnaire is intended to be completed by the CS partners participating in the task 5.1 complementing the work performed in other work packages (namely WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP6). The gathering of the data will be undertaken by those partners, enquiring into the current context in the key dimensions that are relevant for setting-up and executing CS. The questions provided are a support tool to promote self-reflection and understanding of each innovation CS current situation. Moreover, it will

serve as the focal point for applying the Integrated Assessment Methodology (IAM) developed within WP5.

This questionnaire compliments another questionnaire (in the shape of google sheet) identification of main stakeholders (nature, issues, solution, level of engagement). See this DRAFT document the identification of main stakeholders (nature, issues, solution, level of engagement).

Link to the questionnaire for CS stakeholder identification (DRAFT): https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1i0MQRyR0Km6QxwTx2nZaumF_OPWEm3UC/edit#gid=1061616313

0. **Perform situational analyses to define a shared strategy for the CS partners to make the necessary adaptations to move forward on their citizen engagement activities guided by state-of-the-art conservation science.** The questionnaire will generate important information for the PRO-Coast partners to design appropriate measures in support of the 9 pilots and to ensure that collective learning across the pilots is systematic in the way that it is looking for commonalities and differences across the pilots. For instance, PRO-COAST will develop an Integrated Assessment Methodology (IAM). The mentioned strategy will be co-defined between PRO-COAST partners, including CS partners. The strategy will provide insights addressing all the CS relevant dimensions, and once agreed and implemented, will allow CS partners to move into the situational onboarding of citizens or involvement.

1.1. How to answer this questionnaire?

CS partners are responsible for answering the questions of the mentioned dimensions. Consultation of the different experts and stakeholders within the CSs is encouraged for further clarification and support for the process of answering the questionnaire. Most of the questions follow a qualitative methodology, except for the sociodemographic analysis that is mainly based on quantitative indicators. The pilot owners in charge of answering these questions should be aware of the needs and objectives pursued for their specific CS.

2. Situational screening questionnaire

2.1 Goals and objectives of the CS

CS overarching goals and objectives have been pre-defined by CS partners of PRO-COAST. Having these objectives been defined by following a top-down approach, or hybrid approach, it is important to realise the different stakeholders that will be involved may have divergent interests or values and the objectives of the CS may incline more towards preferences and wishes of some stakeholders than those of others. These interests may also change with time. The same can happen with the benefits these stakeholders can perceive.

The following aspects were considered for the initial selection of case studies: (1) the biodiversity of the area and the challenges that threaten it; (2) the community that inhabits it and the cultural context in which they live; (3) the economic driver and primary production; in addition, (4) governance arrangements.

For those reasons, the following questions are focused on facilitating the self-assessment with regards to the connection of the stakeholders.

To address the mentioned issues, each CS partner should consider the following questions:

1. Which stakeholders have been consulted or are expected to be consulted during the formulation of the CS objectives and goals, and why? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating from least to most relevant.

[Prompt] For each group, list the names of each stakeholder in the following rows (more than one stakeholder per group), providing relevant info about their specific objectives and goals. Include any observation if required.

[Recommendation] Reflect on the following: ^[1] Is the involvement of these stakeholders important in the future? ^[2] How does this exclusion affect the PRO-COAST project's goal? ^[3] If the stakeholders that were not consulted are important to reach the CS objectives, map them.

a. Public Institutions (specify if they are local, regional or national)

b. Academia or groups of experts

c. Private enterprises or private initiatives

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

e. Citizens (specify if they are local citizens who live there, foreign citizens, tourists, etc.)

2. Please identify the national, regional, and/or local policies and plans, along with their targets, that could potentially be influenced by the outcomes of the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

[Recommendation] Take into account the identified policies for the definition of the CS activities and outputs. How could the CSs foster policies' implementation? ^[1] Identify the objectives (within the policy) to which the CSs will/could favour.

2.2 Political, institutional and power dynamics dimension

In the situational analysis of a CS, the political, institutional and power dynamics dimension holds significant importance. It refers to the recognition of and consideration of the political and institutional structures and processes that influence the functioning and impact of the CS.

The **political dimension** encompasses the policies and decision-making frameworks within which the CS operates. It involves understanding the relationships between different stakeholders, such as government bodies, regulatory authorities, and civil society organisations, and how these interactions shape the CS’s objectives, goals, and outcomes.

The **institutional dimension** focuses on the formal and informal structures, rules, and norms that guide the functioning of the CS. This includes the governance mechanisms, organisational structures, and accountability frameworks that ensure transparency, participation, and equitable representation of diverse stakeholders.

The **power dynamics** dimension addresses the power balances/imbbalances among the different actors of a CS. It maps the internal power dynamics that connect the objectives, the functioning and the results of the initiatives of each innovation pilot. It supports the description of how the current decision-making system works and presents information about the formal and informal rules and regulations related to the central topic of the CO.

By considering the political, institutional and power dynamics dimension, the CS partners can effectively engage with decision-makers, advocate for change, and influence policy processes. It also allows for the creation of robust and inclusive governance mechanisms that promote transparency, accountability, and meaningful participation of citizens in decision-making processes.

3. What are the programs or plans that could potentially impact the operation of the CS? Please identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant). A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:

[Recommendation] To take into account the identified policies for the CS activities and outputs. How the CSs could foster policies' implementation? ^{[[SEP]]} Identify the objectives or indicators (within the policy) to which the CSs will/could favour. ^{[[SEP]]} Extract any useful guidelines or best practices to perform the CS activities.

a. Climate change

b. Biodiversity

c. Urban and rural planning

d. Mobility

e. Tourism

f. Participatory research
g. Agriculture
h. Others

4. Identify the governance units/departments within your area that have direct competence within the CS. Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

[Recommendation] Make sure that the governance units/departments cover all the CS objectives' topics. You can, for example, align the CS objectives with the listed governance units/departments in a matrix to explore if this is done. ^{SEP}Include the responsible for legislative creation and decision-making, which could act as participants or receivers of the CS process. A governance structure can be planned.

5. Which stakeholders, including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs, other third-sector organizations, and citizens, are involved in or influence policy-making regarding the topics addressed by the CS objectives? Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

[Recommendation] Contact them to inform them about the project and invite them to join it in any form.

6. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?

[Recommendation] Consider involving them in the governance structure of the CS.

a. Agenda setting

b. Policy formulation

c. Decision making

d. Policy implementation

e. Policy evaluation

7. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe CS can have in future strategies?

[Recommendation] These benefits could be the basis for involving different types of stakeholders (e.g., as inputs for the engagement strategy).

2.3 Environmental dimension

8. What is the legal protection status of the CS area based on EU, national and international legislation ?

[Recommendation] As examples: Natura 2000 site, Local Protection Status, other international conventions (Ramsar, SPAMI, etc.).

9. What are the key natural values of the CS area?

[Recommendation] Indicate current status in terms of natural landscapes, habitats, and biodiversity (flora and fauna species)

a. Natural Landscapes: Most characteristic natural landscapes (e.g. sandy, rocky beaches, gorges, sea caves, rocky outcrops, forests, agricultural land, river deltas, estuaries etc.).

b. Habitats: Key habitats
c. Habitats: Number of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC habitats
d. Habitats: Number of priority habitats
e. Fauna: Key fauna species
f. Fauna: Number of species within Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC
g. Fauna: Number of wild bird species
h. Fauna: Target species of wild birds based on Directive 2009/147/EC

10. Has a Management Plan(s) been elaborated and is it being implemented? Please elaborate.

11. What are the main uses of the CS area? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant). <i>[Recommendation] Consider, as examples, the following elements: tourism, grazing, hunting, agriculture, fishing, urban development, others.</i>

12. What are the primary threats/ pressures impacting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them and rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

[Recommendation] Consider, as examples, the following elements: uncontrolled visitation, fragmentation of management competencies, types and intensity of economic activities within the area, conflict of uses, lack of financial resources for protection and management, etc.

13. What are the primary issues or challenges or impacts affecting the protection status of the coastal area of the CS? Please list them based on importance/ intensity. 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

[Recommendation] Consider, as examples, the following elements: Habitat degradation, pollution, climate change impacts, biodiversity loss, soil erosion, invasive species, etc.

14. Are there any existing environmental monitoring programs or initiatives in place in the case study area? If so, please describe it in detail (e.g., scale of the program, active/inactive, degree of public engagement, measured variables, etc).

[Recommendation] Investigate the presence of ongoing environmental monitoring initiatives, including biodiversity monitoring programs, pollution tracking systems, and climate monitoring efforts, within the CS area.

a. Yes, no?

b. Spatial scale of program (national, local, protected area, etc.)

c. Which authority/ies is responsible for the program?

d. How long is it being implemented?

e. What kind of data is being collected (physicochemical parameters, biological parameters, species/ habitats variables, pressures, etc.)?

15. Are there any gaps or limitations in the existing environmental data collection and monitoring efforts?
Please rate their relevance on a scale of 1-5 (from least to most relevant).

[Prompt] Please try to describe them in the form of challenges. We provide you the following variables to help.

a. spatial coverage

b. temporal coverage

c. data quality and resolution

d. monitoring frequency

e. stakeholder engagement limitation

f. accessibility and availability of data

g. data integration and interoperability

h. technical expertise of the CS stakeholders

i. funding

j. infrastructure and supporting services

k. other

2. 4 Technological dimension

16. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CS?

[Recommendation] Explore the benefits and needs of using tools apart from the ones you already have in place.

b. General technologies for engagement (e.g., existing platforms related with CS)

b. Data gathering technologies (e.g., citizen science apps, public reporting portals, etc)

17. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CS objectives with stakeholders?

[Prompt] e.g., Face to face, telephone (call or SMS), email, Websites or blogs (e.g. PRO-COAST website), social media (Facebook, X, Instagram, etc.), Smartphone Apps (WhatsApp, Viber, Line, etc.), Mass and print media (radio, TV, etc.).

[Recommendation] Leverage these communication channels to support the creation/run of the local community. ^{1.1} Explore if the identified communication channels are suitable for all the stakeholders and explore if these still are the best option to communicate with them.

a. Public institutions

b. Academia or groups of experts

c. Private enterprises

d. NGOs or other third sector groups

e. Citizens

18. What primary data sources do you already use to monitor the status of the CS (e.g., biodiversity monitoring, transparency portals for public policies, etc) that you want to influence?

[Recommendation] Identify how useful those data sources are for the CS regarding PRO-COAST and CS challenges. Consider the following questions:

a. How transparent are those data sources for analysis purposes? and, for environmental policy making?

b. Are there any potential data gaps where PRO-COAST may be able to complement data/information?

19. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the PRO-COAST CS?

[Prompt] Please bear in mind that even if there are datasets for a specific topic, CSs could complement them with more data density for the pilot area (e.g., currently unreached areas).

[Recommendation] Establish dialogue among the rest of PRO-COAST partners to explore how to access, maintain or even exploit new data sources.

20. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 15)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

[Recommendation] Specify the possible thematic exploration per use case, and potential KPIs generated so that

decision-makers can leverage from the information distilled. A link with PRO-COAST indicators may be established. Consider geographic information systems (GIS) software for spatial analysis, statistical software for quantitative analysis, and qualitative data analysis software for qualitative data. Also, data visualization tools.

21. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

[Recommendation] Reflect on data volume, formats and ways of accessing and processing such data so that thematic co-explorations can be assembled. If possible, consider using metadata standards reflect formats like CSV (Comma-Separated Values) or JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) for information about data source, collection methods, temporal and spatial coverage, and quality assurance procedures.

2.4 Public Engagement dimension

To reach many people with a call for participation in the CS we need to align our calls with local debates and issues that matter for already engaged people. That requires a screening of the local media landscape, researching previous participatory initiatives & talking with mediators that know what issues make people become actively engaged in issues of public concern.

22. Do you have any previous experience in organizing community-based research or participatory initiatives? If yes, please provide detailed information about your experience.

[Recommendation] If the initiative is related to any of the topics addressed by the CS, to recover the contact data of the engaged community in order to reach them again.

a. Topic of the initiative

b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people,...)

c. Communication channels

23. What are the local debates and prominent issues that are connected or could potentially be connected to

the aspirations of your CS?

[Recommendation] Aim at conciliating the parties by involving the different actors in the dispute (administrations, private sector, communities).^[1] Communication should always be oriented towards mediating between conflicting interests and not aiming to avoid conflicts/tensions.^[1] Leverage local debates to create the engagement strategy per stakeholder type.

24. Are you following any specific methodology or toolkit for public engagement purposes).

[Prompt] If yes, please describe how and specify the step of the process (identification, framing, design, testing). If no, please provide the reasons (e.g., lack of awareness, utilization of alternative methods, insufficient capacity, etc.).

[Recommendation] If not, please consider using some existing methodologies e.g. the Bristol Approach or the Extreme Citizen Science. You may find a basic overview of these proposed approaches in [this document](#). This may help engaging participants at all stages of the process, from problem definition to data collection and analysis, focusing on issues of importance to them. Consider free and informed consent from local communities early in the public engagement process, formalizing terms through a community protocol to guide conduct over the lifetime of the CS. Additionally, consider involving artists to facilitate these encounters.

25. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

[Recommendation] Use/leverage the different media channels identified & tailor call for participation to different audiences' issues.

26. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

[Recommendation] Involve the different groups in participation and dissemination of the CS.^[1] To propose strategies to reconcile and dialogue between different discourses

27. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about? (e.g. under-represented groups)

[Prompt] To understand better why these groups are excluded & get closer to the forms of dialogue and discourse

of these excluded communities.

[Recommendation] : Consider historically under-represented groups including: Children; People from minority ethnic backgrounds; People with health conditions or impairments; Older people;

28. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

[Recommendation] If well-established associations are found, invite their participation or avoid conflict with them through dialogue.

2.5 Sociodemographic dimension

The information gathered through answering to the requirements of the current dimension will be processed by the CS partners by using an intersectional analysis, which focuses on different social categories (sectionalities) that are interconnected. These social categories are addressed by the breakdown of the indicators that we ask CS partners to investigate in their related databases (e.g. official statistical offices).

This analysis considers the characteristics of the population living in the study area and linked population as well as the specific social context of each CS. It ensures that the CS partners are suitable and inclusive, promoting participation and effectively carrying out the activities of the innovation pilots. It is important to look at the population from an intersectional perspective and strive for equality in terms of representation among different groups, including minority groups.

Since the information available varies among each CS country, the segregation or breakdown of the different indicators should be provided according to the available data, in each specific CS.

29. Number of inhabitants in the CS?

[Prompt] Make clear the limits of the CS (e.g. coastal region, NUTS region, etc)

[Recommendation] Ensure that the data covers the entire study area of the case study (CS) and includes information on both permanent residents and seasonal populations, if applicable. Consider disaggregating population data by age groups, gender, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status to gain insights into the demographic composition of the area.

30. Number of visitors/ tourists in the CS and indication of seasonality.

a. What is the number of tourists that should be ideal for sustainability?

31. Main employment and economic activities of the population of the CS area.

